

**Impact of Open Innovation Models on Enterprise
Innovation Performance under the Perspectives
of Absorptive Capability, Dynamic Capabilities
and Cognitive Inertia**

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ABSTRACT

This thesis aims to find the impact of adopting various open innovation models on innovation performance in technology-based SMEs in China, taking absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and cognitive inertia as the mediators or moderators. Firstly, a pilot survey of 100 SMEs in Shandong Province based on grounded theory was carried out to identify intermediate variables that might impact the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance: absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and cognitive inertia. Then, hypotheses covering the relationship between the open innovation model, absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities, cognitive inertia and innovation performance were developed based on the literature and previous research conclusions. In order to test these research hypotheses, a questionnaire based on 349 Chinese technology-based SMEs was distributed, and a series of partial least squares regression models were then constructed.

This research obtained the following conclusions. (1) Adopting outside-in, inside-out, and coupled open innovation modes can positively impact innovation performance. (2) Adopting outside-in, inside-out and coupled open innovation modes positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive and dynamic capabilities. (3) The absorptive and dynamic capabilities positively impact innovation performance and positively complementary mediate the impact of adopting open innovation models on innovation performance. (4) Cognitive inertia can positively impact innovation performance but also negatively moderates the relationship between adopting open innovation models and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs in varying degrees.

The research in this thesis has considerable theoretical and practical value for improving the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs in China.

There are three new features in the study. First, based on the knowledge perspective, it constructs a mechanism analysis framework for the impact of open innovation mode on the innovation performance of SMEs. It proposes a comprehensive theoretical explanation for SMEs' differences in innovation performance through open innovation mode. Second, it reveals the internal mechanism of the open innovation model of technology-based SMEs impacting innovation performance and finds that enterprises' absorptive and dynamic capabilities have crucial mediating effects. Such mediating effects are the same under different open innovation models. Third, it reveals how cognitive inertia as a moderating variable impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs in adopting the open innovation model and the variability of this moderating effect under different open innovations.

Keywords: Innovation Performance Models; Absorptive Capability; Dynamic Capabilities; Cognitive Inertia; Innovation Performance

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Chapter 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

As market competition intensifies and the demands of customers change at an accelerated pace, enterprises have to innovate if they want to survive in the market continuously. Open innovation has received increasing attention as an essential innovation approach (Hossain & Kauranen, 2016) and has become one of the key research themes in innovation (Chesbrough et al., 2014; Kraus et al., 2019). Open innovation emphasises the balanced coordination of internal and external resources to generate innovative ideas and the integrated use of internal and external market channels to serve innovation activities (Chesbrough, 2003). After introducing the idea of open innovation, research was initially focused on large enterprises such as IBM, Adidas and Procter & Gamble, especially high-tech enterprises (Peng et al., 2013). Open innovation is available in large enterprises and employed by SMEs (van de Vrande et al., 2009; Lee et al., 2010; Wynarczyk, 2013; Kraus et al., 2019). Compared to large enterprises, SMEs face more significant challenges in the market competition, with limitations such as financial constraints and limited resources, lack of sufficient technical support to innovate (Hitchen et al., 2017), and need to rely on external partners to innovate to enhance their competitiveness; open innovation has gradually become an essential way of innovation for many SMEs (Wynarczyk, 2013). Some scholars argue that SMEs are more likely to use open innovation than large enterprises (Wynarczyk, 2013; Spithoven et al., 2013); van de Vrande et al. (2009) found that 605 innovative SMEs in the Netherlands were involved in a variety of open innovation practices; and Theyel (2013) found that over 50% of US SMEs were involved in open innovation to some extent. In recent years, scholars have focused on the uniqueness of open innovation in SMEs (Wang, 2019), emphasising the importance of open innovation research in SMEs (Hossain & Kauranen, 2016; Kraus et al., 2019).

In recent years, China's SMEs have overgrown and made outstanding contributions to driving economic growth, promoting employment and fostering technological innovation. Based on He et al. (2019) research, in promoting economic growth, the number of SMEs now exceeds 20 million, accounting for more than 90% of the total number of enterprises in China, paying more than 45% of total tax revenue and creating products and services worth 60% of the gross domestic product, the innovative effect of SMEs is crucial to the economic development of the country. In promoting employment, more than 80% of urban jobs are created by SMEs, and the dynamism of SME innovation has a significant impact on employment and the upgrading of the labour resource structure of the country. SMEs drive scientific and technological innovation significantly, contributing to over 70% of invention patents. Particularly in regions where SMEs are concentrated, there is a remarkable trend: the average annual growth rate of patent applications by SMEs exceeds 50%, and the rate at which patents are granted to these SMEs surpasses 30%.

Chinese technology-based SMEs, as a group with solid technological innovation dynamics among SMEs; however, the technological innovation model currently adopted is mainly collaborative innovation. This model has many obstacles, such as technology spillover, disconnection between industry, university and research, unbalanced distribution of patent property rights, lack of long-term strategic considerations and poor sustainability of cooperation (Chen & Liu, 2010), especially the disconnection between industry, university and research. Through industry-university-research cooperation, enterprises can acquire cutting-edge technological knowledge and achieve breakthrough innovation in new products through the effective combination of knowledge, thus enhancing innovation performance (Faems et al., 2005). However, the differences in research and development (R&D) orientation between enterprises and research institutions can lead to a disconnect between industry-university-research collaboration and the inability to internalise enterprises' socialised capital into enterprises' intellectual capital (Wu et al.,

2004). Therefore, many barriers prevent enterprises from internalising the externally acquired technological resources into corporate technological capabilities in collaborative innovation and enhancing their core competencies through accumulating technological capabilities. The primary source of the barriers to collaborative innovation in technology-based SMEs is that both the internal innovation resources and the external innovation resources are limited to partners, the number of partners is limited, and the sustainability of the collaboration is poor (Hagedoorn, 2002; Vanhaverbeke et al., 2002). Therefore, the degree of openness to external resources in the technological innovation process of technology-based SMEs will affect the core competencies of the enterprises, which in turn will lead to differences in innovation performance.

R&D absorptive capability, as an essential resource for the enterprise, plays a crucial role in the development process of the enterprise. Enterprises can use their R&D absorptive capability to continuously import external R&D knowledge to expand their R&D knowledge base (Martinkenaite & Breunig, 2016). In addition, a high level of R&D absorptive capability reflects a deeper understanding of external R&D knowledge and its application, which breaks down the enterprise's fixed mindset to explore new business opportunities and improve its performance (Qi & Song, 2021). Thus, R&D absorptive capability enables enterprises to observe future technological trends more accurately, respond to changes and challenges in the industry (Xin & Zhang, 2018), and gain a voice in the competition and development of the industry (Li & Zeng, 2021).

Knowledge abundance is a typical characteristic of the knowledge economy, but knowledge constraints are also essential for enterprises to achieve innovative development. Enterprises relying on knowledge for innovation tend to develop natural inertia, dominated by inertia thinking that constantly reinforces existing thinking paths and known knowledge sources, thus

manifesting itself in always solving problems along the original lines (Huang et al., 2020). This mindset runs counter to the requirements of corporate innovation. Innovation is the continuous optimisation of existing paths, obsolescence and renewal, originality, breaking away from the limitations of inherited thinking and breaking the established inertia to create more unexpected gains, resulting in unique new products and services. Innovation can be hindered by habitually following previous experiences and methods of solving similar concerns, and cognitive inertia can, to some extent, cause knowledge search paths to lock in (Zhou & Chen, 2011). However, good inertia also enables enterprises to maintain a state of learning over time, continuously absorbing new knowledge and promoting innovation (Bakker & Knoben, 2015). Thus, the influence of cognitive inertia needs to be viewed dialectically in the innovation process, and the positive effects of cognitive inertia need to be fully utilised. Its adverse effects weakened, intending to cleverly utilise cognitive inertia to improve the innovation performance of the enterprise.

Adopting an open innovation model by Chinese technology-based SMEs certainly helps improve their innovation performance. This has driven more technology-based SMEs to transform from a closed innovation model to an open one. In implementing an open innovation model, factors such as the enterprise's core competencies, knowledge and management, absorptive capability, and cognitive inertia all contribute to the differences in innovation performance. Technology-based SMEs adopting an open innovation model can transform external knowledge into innovation performance through core competencies and knowledge capabilities. However, the external environment of enterprises is dynamic and changing, and enterprises' core competencies and knowledge capabilities need to be reconfigured to adapt to the environment to enhance innovation performance sustainably. Therefore, the key for technology-based SMEs to enhance innovation performance by adopting an open innovation model is to cultivate the dynamic capability to adapt to the environment in order to reconfigure the enterprise's core and

knowledge capabilities and improve the conversion rate of external knowledge to innovation performance, while also overcoming the negative impact of cognitive inertia on the conversion of external knowledge. Therefore, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to study the mechanism of the impact of open innovation models on the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs and the reasons for the existence of variability in their innovation performance to enhance enterprises' innovation performance.

1.2 Research Significance

This research provided a comprehensive theoretical framework for the variability of innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Through the study of the relationship between open innovation mode, absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and innovation performance, this thesis finds that the implementation of open innovation mode can help enterprises construct and update their absorptive and dynamic capabilities to adapt to the changes in the external environment, thus enhancing innovation performance. In addition, this thesis combines the resource-based theory, enterprise capability theory and open innovation theory to construct a mechanism analysis framework of the impact of open innovation on the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. It explores the reasons for the differences in the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs in the use of open innovation from the perspective of cognitive inertia so that the theoretical research perspective is comprehensive.

This thesis verifies that adopting an open innovation mode can effectively improve enterprises' innovation performance by studying the mechanism between the open innovation mode of technology-based SMEs and innovation performance. Moreover, the open innovation mode of enterprises has a direct impact on innovation performance. At the same time, absorptive and dynamic capabilities, as essential mediators in the relationship between the open innovation mode impacting innovation performance, can also help enterprises

transform internal and external knowledge into innovation performance. However, the inhibitory effect of internal cognitive inertia in adopting open innovation enhances enterprises' innovation performance, thus impacting innovation performance's acquisition and creation efficiency. The above findings will have the following values for developing SMEs in science and technology in China: (1) It helps technology-based SMEs utilise different open innovation models to enhance innovation performance. (2) It helps SMEs to build and update their absorptive and dynamic capabilities. (3) It helps SMEs overcome the obstacles hindering innovation performance.

1.3 Research Objective and Questions

The initial objective of this thesis was to explore the impact of SMEs' open innovation models on enterprises' innovation performance. However, the authors do not know whether and which factors play the intermediate variable role in this relationship. Therefore, before refining the formal research questions, the author conducted a pilot survey based on the grounded theory and interviewed 73 SME executives from various industries in Shandong Province, China. Based on these executives' expectations, concerns and possible reasons for rejection of the implementation of open innovation in SMEs as extracted from the pilot survey and the theories that most SME executives are most concerned about innovation performance, the author included absorptive capability, dynamic capability and cognitive inertia as intermediate variables in this study. Therefore, the following questions need to be focused on exploring the mechanism of the impact of the adoption of open innovation models by technology-based SMEs on innovation performance in this thesis.

(1) What is the direct impact between adopting different open innovation models and their innovation performance by the technology-based SMEs?

Open innovation emphasises the access to and use of external innovation resources for R&D activities and the commercialisation of internal

technologies through new external channels (Chesbrough, 2003). In the implementation of the outside-in open innovation model, enterprises can enhance their innovation performance by linking up with rich external knowledge resources to integrate internal and external technologies and form more complex technology combinations (Chesbrough, 2003) and by promoting the growth of their innovation performance through external R&D activities (Berchicci, 2013). The inside-out open innovation model helps nurture and retain committed innovators and increase their motivation to innovate, leading to increased technology commercialisation, reach, and visibility (Rigby & Zook, 2002).

However, increasingly shortened innovation cycles and time-to-market drive enterprises to open up their innovation processes, and too much openness can lead to a loss of control and core competencies, which can hurt any long-term innovation success of the enterprise (Biemans, 1995). In addition, excessive openness can increase information search and transaction costs, uncertainty in the innovation environment, information overload within the enterprise, and create a 'familiarity trap', reducing innovation performance (Johnsen & Ford, 2000). Due to the lack of internal innovation resources and capabilities in technology-based SMEs, enterprises must access external resources and transfer internal resources through different open innovation models to capture and create innovation performance. Among them, outside-in open innovation practices are more common than inside-out open innovation. Research on outside-in open innovation shows that SMEs prefer non-monetary relationship-based innovation activities (e.g. innovation through networking activities) to complex transaction-based innovation activities (e.g. acquisition, purchase of licences, etc.) (van de Vrande et al., 2009) and hardly ever adopt inside-out open innovation (van de Vrande et al. 2009). While some technology-based start-ups and venture capital-backed entrepreneurial enterprises consider licensing technology as an alternative to developing and marketing products (Gans & Stern, 2003), identifying potential opportunities for licensing is a complex problem for SMEs. In addition, the literature pays

little attention to the role of non-monetary relationship-related activities in inside-out open innovation, ignoring the fact that non-monetary relationship-based inside-out innovation activities may allow SMEs to overcome the adverse effects of inadequate internal resources and capabilities (Gruber & Henkel, 2006).

The coupled open innovation model is based on co-creation with complementary partner enterprises through alliances, collaborations and joint ventures. Enterprises use this innovation model primarily to set product standards, increase revenues and establish strategic alliances with complementary partner enterprises (Gassmann & Enkel, 2004). Enterprises in traditional industries or SMEs often use the coupled open innovation model due to a lack of or low absorptive capability, but this requires innovation intermediaries to build absorptive capability (Spithoven et al., 2011). The inflow and outflow of knowledge in coupled open innovation are complementary, with the purchase and sale of knowledge enabling enterprises to increase their innovation output and combining the inflow and outflow of knowledge through coupled open innovation to reduce associated costs (e.g. cognitive, transaction and organisational costs). However, empirical tests have shown that enterprises that simultaneously purchase and sell knowledge can increase sales of new products and the cost of R&D (Cassiman & Valentini, 2016). Thus, the direct relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance is still debated in theoretical studies, probably due to the heterogeneity of resources among enterprises adopting open innovation models. Since technology-based SMEs are different from ordinary and large enterprises, the direct relationship between adopting open innovation models and innovation performance needs further investigation. At the same time, what kind of open innovation model is chosen by technology-based SMEs, and does it affect innovation performance and to what extent? Existing theoretical research has not yet provided a clear answer.

(2) What is the role of absorptive capability in the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs?

Kedia & Bhagat (1988) initially introduced the concept of absorptive capability, although their definition lacked clarity. Cohen & Levinthal (1990) provided a definitive interpretation of absorptive capability. They defined it as an organizational attribute centred on the capacity to identify, assimilate, and effectively apply external knowledge, particularly for practical business purposes. This ability was perceived as a static resource inherent to the enterprise. The elucidation by Cohen & Levinthal (1990) marked a pivotal moment, catalyzing scholarly attention toward exploring absorptive capability. In previous studies, absorptive capability has rarely been explored as a mediating impact factor and mechanism of operation. In this paper, the role of absorptive capability as a mediating factor in innovation performance under open innovation is systematically investigated, and the mediating role of absorptive capability in different open innovation models is explored. The aim is to understand whether absorptive capability plays a mediating role in the current Chinese market environment, where enterprises themselves are increasing their openness to innovation to improve their innovation performance and to help managers improve and enhance their innovation activities based on this thesis to effectively contribute to the achievement of more significant competitive advantage and long-term sustainability.

(3) What is the role of Dynamic capability in the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs?

Under the condition that internal innovation resources are lacking, enterprises must implement an open innovation model to build dynamic capabilities that can adapt to the external environment. There are mainly two types of studies on the relationship between dynamic capabilities and open innovation: one believes that dynamic capabilities have a facilitating role for open innovation, and the other believes that open innovation has a constructive role for dynamic capabilities. Several scholars have emphasised the need to balance

the ability to benefit from external knowledge with the ability to develop internal knowledge (Chesbrough, 2003; Nielsen, 2006; Teece, 2007). Moreover, valuable external knowledge resources do not mean new ideas can enter the enterprises automatically or simply; external knowledge can only be identified, accessed and absorbed when the enterprise develops new paths and changes its structure and culture, opening up its innovation processes. Open innovation can, therefore, only be implemented effectively if dynamic capabilities can change organisational practices.

In the open innovation model, cross-border search becomes a necessary way for technological innovation and an effective means to build dynamic capabilities, and it provides resources and learning guarantees for the formation and enhancement of dynamic capabilities (Liu & Meng, 2016). Enterprises need to dynamically adapt their exploratory and exploitative learning according to the different stages of technological innovation to create variation in their capabilities and thus improve their dynamic capabilities (Zhu & Chen, 2008). However, there are still prominent "black process box" issues in open innovation, including "how the open innovation behaviour of enterprises affects the formation of organisational knowledge capabilities" and "how the formation of dynamic organisational knowledge capabilities affects innovation performance". These questions can help identify the dynamics and evolutionary mechanisms underlying enterprises' adoption of open innovation models (Nie & Zhang, 2013). It is unclear what role dynamic capabilities play in the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs, whether it can improve the conversion rate from external knowledge to innovation performance, and whether it is a prerequisite or a consequence of open innovation.

(4) What is the role of cognitive inertia in the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs?

Academics have no consensus on the relationship between cognitive inertia and innovation. Early studies focused on the inhibitory effect of cognitive inertia on innovation, arguing that cognitive inertia leads to outcomes such as group and individual disorientation, delayed decision-making, and fear of change (Li & Zeng, 2019; Yuan et al., 2005). However, subsequent studies have found that different dimensions of cognitive inertia affect enterprises' innovation differently. Among them, experience inertia is conducive to innovation because it allows enterprises to make effective matches and analogies, saving thinking time, reducing the uncertainty associated with the use of new methods, and increasing the efficiency of innovation (Li & Zeng, 2019; Liao et al., 2008). In addition, both experience and learning inertia contribute to product innovation (Xie et al., 2016). However, how cognitive inertia as an intermediate variable affects the relationship between open innovation models and the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs needs to be further investigated.

1.4 Thesis Structure

Chapter one is the introduction, introducing this research's background, significance and objectives. Chapter Two provided theoretical foundations for this research. The hypotheses are developed in Chapter Three based on the theoretical foundations and literature in Chapters Two and Three. Chapter Four shows the methodology of this research. Chapter Five gave the data analysis of measurements in each variable. Chapter Six gave the analysis and hypotheses tests for the relationship between each variable. The final chapter shows the research findings and conclusion of this thesis.

Chapter 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter will review the literature related to open innovation in SMEs, including the relationship between open innovation and innovation performance, the relationship between open innovation and absorptive capability, the relationship between the absorptive capability and innovation performance, the relationship between open innovation and dynamic capability, the relationship between dynamic capability and innovation performance, the relationship between open innovation and cognitive inertia, the relationship between cognitive inertia and innovation performance, to identify the gaps in existing research and lay the foundation for subsequent research on theoretical issues.

2.1 Technology-based SMEs in the Context of Open Innovation

The study of open innovation is spreading from large enterprises to SMEs and from high-tech to low- and medium-tech enterprises, and open innovation benefits both large enterprises and SMEs (Chesbrough & Crowther, 2006). The question of how the most innovative and numerous SMEs should use open innovation is receiving increasing scholarly attention. Therefore, this research's first step is to define technology-based SMEs and their specific open innovation characteristics.

2.1.1 Definition of Technology-based SMEs in China

Technology-based SMEs, also known as innovative SMEs in the US, are enterprises with a mission to innovate. According to the specific provisions of China's Notice on the Issuance of the Standard Provisions for the Classification of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (Ministry of Industry and Information Technology Joint Enterprise [2011] No. 300) and the provisions of

China's Measures for the Evaluation of Technology-based Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (State Science & Technology Development and Administration [2017] No. 115), the definition of technology-based SMEs can be summarised as SMEs with a total number of employees not exceeding 500, annual sales revenue not exceeding RMB 200 million, total assets not exceeding RMB 200 million, and the indicators of the enterprise's scientific and technological personnel, R&D investment and scientific and technological achievements all meeting specific standards.

China's Small and Medium Enterprises Promotion Law defines technology-based SMEs as mainly led and founded by science and technology personnel, mainly engaged in scientific research, development, production and sales of high-tech products, with the commercialisation of scientific and technological achievements as well as technology development, technical services, technical consultation and high-tech products, market-oriented and practising It is a knowledge-intensive economic entity that is "self-financing, voluntarily combined, independently operated, self-sustaining, self-developing and self-restraining". The Ministry of Science & Technology defines technology-based SMEs as SMEs that rely on a certain number of science and technology personnel to engage in scientific and technological research and development activities, acquire independent intellectual property rights and transform them into high-tech products or services, achieving sustainable development. According to the "Measures for the Evaluation of Science and Technology-based SMEs" promulgated by the Ministry of Science and Technology (most.gov.cn), the number of employees in science and technology-based SMEs should, in principle, not exceed 500, of which the proportion of science and technology personnel with college degrees or above to the total number of employees should not be less than 30%; those directly engaged in research and development should account for more than 10% of the total employees; enterprises should mainly engage in the research, development, production and service of high-tech products; the annual expenditure on research and development of high-tech products should not be less than 2%

of sales; the enterprise manager should have a strong sense of innovation, high market development ability and management level.

Therefore, this article considers technology-based SMEs to be SMEs with a certain number of R&D personnel engaged in market-oriented research and development, production and sales of high-tech products, commercialisation of technological achievements and technology transfer, technology services and technology consulting as their primary business.

2.1.2 Characteristics of Open Innovation in SMEs

SMEs are 'small' organisations which tend to be more flexible, make decisions quickly and respond to market changes more rapidly. As a result, their innovation processes and models are very different from those of large enterprises (Edwards et al., 2005). At the same time, SMEs have limited materials, human resources, and resources (Harryson, 2008) and management decisions are mainly made by founders, partners, or family members (Poper, 1999), and their R&D processes are very unregulated.

Because of their small size, SMEs cannot perform all innovative activities, so their innovations must also incorporate external cross-border elements. SMEs with multiple partnerships are better innovators than their counterparts with only one partnership (Baum et al., 2000). SMEs in formal or informal networks are more innovative than others (Macpherson & Holt, 2007). Personal networks provide strong support for the diffusion of innovation within SME networks (Ceci & Iubatti, 2012), allowing social and personal relationships to be embedded in the economic behaviour of SMEs. However, they do not consciously exploit these relationships (Macpherson & Holt, 2007) and cannot manage external knowledge (Bessant, 1999). Even when SMEs can build strong external relationships and networks, they often lack the internal capabilities to support them (Bougrain & Haudeville, 2002). They thus may

rely too heavily on external relationships and networks to achieve innovation, making them a barrier to innovation and costing enterprises more opportunities to innovate (Macpherson & Holt, 2007).

Enterprise linkages and networks are essential drivers of innovation in SMEs, but existing research has identified a 'paradox' in that SMEs often have inter-enterprise solid relationships and networks but have difficulty leveraging these relationships (Macpherson & Holt, 2007). How SMEs can consciously harness these networks and social capital to achieve knowledge inflow and outflow has become a unique challenge in harnessing and managing open innovation.

There is a complex relationship between enterprise size and openness to innovation. Numerous research studies have shown that enterprise size positively affects an enterprise's openness to innovation (Drechsler & Natter, 2012), while some scholars have found an inverted U relationship between enterprise size and search breadth (Barge-Gil, 2010).

The proliferation of outside-in open innovation practices in SMEs' innovation activities is much greater than inside-out open innovation. Research on outside-in open innovation suggests that SMEs prefer non-monetary relationships, such as networking activities, to complex transaction-based innovation activities, such as acquisitions and license purchases (van de Vrande et al., 2009). SMEs hardly adopt inside-out open innovation (van de Vrande et al., 2009), and little attention has been paid in the literature to the role of non-monetary relationship activities in inside-out open innovation. However, such innovation activities may allow SMEs to overcome the disadvantages of small size (Gruber & Henkel, 2006).

Open innovation models for SMEs vary. Some enterprises use a combination of different practices, while others use only part of the potential practices. Some enterprises are open only to enterprises in the value chain, while others are open to universities and research institutions (Cosh & Zhang, 2011; Brunswicker & Vanhaverbeke, 2010).

A variety of factors influence SMEs' open innovation decisions and activities. The characteristics of enterprises' financial and innovation systems (Christensen et al., 2005), their market and technological knowledge gaps and inefficient intellectual property management mechanisms can hinder the external opening of innovation (Drechsler & Natter, 2012), and the ownership structure of SMEs determines their more excellent receptiveness to outside-in open innovation models. The breadth of search in family-owned SMEs is less than in non-family enterprises. The CEO's level of education and the senior managers' style will influence the openness to SMEs' innovation (Classen et al., 2012).

In summary, SMEs have low open innovation due to their small size but need to innovate to grow. Therefore, they prefer to engage in non-monetary relationships outside-in open innovation activities and adopt multiple innovation approaches to access external innovation resources. At the same time, a variety of heterogeneous factors influence the open innovation activities of SMEs.

2.1.3 Motivations for Open Innovation in SMEs

Open innovation offers a possible way for SMEs to overcome the barriers to innovation, such as lack of financial resources, lack of access to professional staff and inability to diversify risk in their innovation portfolio (Gassmann et al., 2010). Therefore, breaking through organisational boundaries and building networks for open innovation has been increasingly adopted by SMEs and is

an essential option for SMEs to cope with fierce competition. A survey of Germany, Australia and Switzerland found that 32.5% of SMEs would adopt open innovation to some extent (Lichtenthaler, 2008). The motivation for SMEs to adopt open innovation has also become a hot topic in academia and can be sorted out from both internal and external dimensions.

Internal Motivation

From the perspective of resource-based theory, SMEs need to adopt open innovation to expand the scope of their resources and acquire external resources and knowledge to achieve their innovation goals in the face of fierce external competition due to their relatively small scale, limited management capabilities, internal resources and insufficient knowledge reserves they possess. Therefore, the size of the enterprise is an essential aspect that affects open innovation (van de Vrande et al., 2009; Wynarczyk, 2013; Lichtenthaler, 2008; Guräu & Lasch, 2011). Due to the limited size, SMEs often lack the resources needed to develop and commercialise new products, have a small pool of technological assets, and need to collaborate with other enterprises to innovate (van de Vrande et al., 2009; Spithoven et al., 2013; Hochleitner et al., 2011) to be able better to achieve the innovation goals (Spithoven et al., 2013; Mortara & Minshall, 2011). Based on a resource-based view, Barney & Clark (2007) suggest that lacking resources is the primary reason SMEs adopt open innovation.

From the perspective of knowledge-based theory, new product innovation involves knowledge from different disciplines. It takes a long time for an enterprise to accumulate knowledge and technology solely on its strengths, and SMEs lack the resources to invest in the knowledge required for new product development, so they prefer to adopt an open innovation approach to innovation (Wynarczyk, 2013). SMEs must discover, identify and utilise knowledge from external sources and integrate it with internal knowledge to achieve their innovation goals and establish links with customers, suppliers,

competitors, R&D institutions, etc., to acquire knowledge (Laursen & Salter, 2006). Padilla-Meléndez et al. (2013) argue that knowledge transfer and exchange is an essential aspect of open innovation and that inter-enterprise cooperation is needed to achieve knowledge transfer and exchange in achieving innovation goals.

From the perspective of social network theory, enterprises obtain the resources and knowledge they need to achieve their innovation goals by building open innovation networks, and network relationships and network structure have an essential influence on the formation and operation of open innovation networks. Different network members have different impacts on innovation performance, and there are significant differences in the impacts of suppliers, customers, government, universities and R&D institutions on innovation performance (Zeng & Xie, 2010). In this regard, customers are considered significant network members and interaction with customers benefits innovation performance (Zeng & Xie, 2010; Presenza et al., 2017). In the open innovation process, SMEs need to choose the right partners to innovate with, and the ability to develop partners and identify partners with complementary resources can influence open innovation in SMEs (Guräu & Lasch, 2011).

External Motivation

Whether an SME adopts open innovation or not is related to the external environment in which it operates. Research has focused on the impact of market dynamics, technological turbulence and policy.

The dynamic nature of the market is considered one of the most significant factors impacting open innovation in SMEs (Pervan et al., 2015). Enterprises need to respond to changes in the market and innovate new products to meet market needs. On the one hand, they need to develop their R&D capabilities

internally to meet customer needs; on the other hand, they need to adopt an open innovation approach to respond to market dynamics (Chesbrough, 2007). Meeting the needs of consumers is an essential objective of open innovation, and by responding to market changes through open innovation and collaborating with other enterprises, SMEs can overcome the difficulties that may exist in commercialising their products and better meet consumer needs (Lee et al., 2010; van de Vrande et al., 2009). Technological turbulence refers to the degree of change in the enterprise industry's product and process technology. Rapid technological advances can significantly shorten product life cycles and erode the competitive advantage of enterprises. When faced with rapid technological change, SMEs may consider open innovation by collaborating with other enterprises (Bianchi, 2010). Lichtenthaler (2009), for example, found that with high technological turbulence, enterprises do not have all the technology needed for technological development and, through open innovation, can access the knowledge they need to innovate from outside the enterprise.

In addition, the policy environment of the industry and region in which the enterprise is located is considered to be an influential factor in promoting open innovation in SMEs, and public policy has an impact on accelerating the use of open innovation in SMEs (Vega et al., 2012). Kamp & Bevis (2012) argue that public research institutions and universities should play an essential role in SME innovation and that innovation support from public institutions is an essential driver of open innovation in SMEs. Vrgovic et al. (2012) suggest that government agencies in developing countries could use innovation incubators to help SMEs connect, communicate and collaborate with other innovators to promote innovative practices. Roper & Hewitt-Dundas (2013) studied the role of public R&D centre investment in driving open innovation, using a real-time monitoring experiment to examine the development of external linkages in 18 public R&D centres established in 2002, and found that university-based public R&D centres created more new linkages than enterprise-based public

R&D centres and were able to interact more with SMEs and are more conducive to open innovation.

2.2 Open Innovation and Open Innovation Models

2.2.1 Definition of Open Innovation

Schumpeter introduced the concept of 'innovation' in 1912 in "Theory of Economic Development". He used innovation theory to explain the problems of economic development. Through continuous analysis and application, he developed a complete system of innovation theory. Chesbrough (2003) first mentioned the "open innovation theory", stating that open innovation is a model of innovation in which enterprises artificially use innovation resources to flow across organisational boundaries and effectively utilise internal and external resources and technologies for commercialisation to enhance innovation capabilities and performance. Open innovation is a cognitive concept at the organisational level, where 'openness' refers to the movement of knowledge across organisational boundaries and 'innovation' refers to the development and commercialisation of new products, processes, services or improvements. Since then, the term open innovation has been widely used in academic circles and defined from many new perspectives, such as economics, management and sociology. Huizingh (2011) analyses open innovation's content, context and process and considers it a valuable concept. Chesbrough & Bogers (2014) define it from a business model perspective as a distributed innovation process based on purposefully managing the flow of knowledge across organisational boundaries, using economic and non-economic mechanisms consistent with the organisation's business model. Zhang et al. (2015) classify open innovation based on the premise, purpose and methods from three perspectives: openness, cooperation and innovation. Xu et al. (2017) believe that the essence of open innovation is to break the boundary constraints of resource flow, effectively integrate internal and external innovation resources, explore and develop the corresponding market transformation mechanism of innovation results, and share the new value

created. Xie (2021) argues that for enterprises, open innovation includes the fact that the industry has been known for its innovative products and services, that the innovative products and services of enterprises require new knowledge and capabilities, and that enterprises continuously incorporate new products and services to adapt to future market demands.

The definition of open innovation has not yet been unified in academic circles due to different perspectives. The existing definitions can be categorised into the following three perspectives. First, the knowledge-based definition emphasises the role of internal and external knowledge in open innovation. Penin (2008) defines open innovation as the voluntary disclosure of knowledge by an enterprise, freely available to all interested individuals or organisations, allowing the knowledge to interact among stakeholders. Secondly, the organisation-based definition highlights the crossover of organisational boundaries by open innovation. Chesbrough (2003) argues that open innovation is a new paradigm of technological innovation and that enterprises that adopt open innovation can and should exploit internal and external ideas and use internal and external pathways in technological development. West & Gallagher (2006) define open innovation as a systematic effort by enterprises to identify a wide range of internal and external innovation opportunities, to combine external exploration with corporate capabilities and resources purposefully, and to exploit these opportunities through multiple channels. Thirdly, the process-based definition underlines that open innovation can help enterprises build a framework system for innovation. Chesbrough & Crowther (2006) see open innovation as two separate processes that purposefully harness incoming and outgoing knowledge to accelerate internal innovation and expand the market for external applications of internal innovation, i.e. outside-in and inside-out open innovation. Lichtenthaler (2008) defines open innovation as an essential technology management task accomplished along the innovation process based on a systematic reliance on the enterprise's internal and external

dynamic capabilities. Van de Vrande & de Man (2011) state that open innovation studies how an enterprise acquires and exploits new knowledge.

From the definition of open innovation, it can be seen that as a new paradigm of technological innovation is different from closed innovation, its characteristics lie in the following three points. Firstly, external knowledge complements innovation, with internal and external knowledge equally essential in enterprise innovation. Secondly, internal R&D is not restricted by the current business model and can enter the market through multiple channels. Third, knowledge and technology flow consciously and purposefully based on external commercialisation purposes. Therefore, based on the knowledge perspective, this thesis defines the open innovation model as a technological innovation model that can simultaneously use internal and external complementary innovation knowledge to improve knowledge allocation efficiency, reduce innovation costs and uncertainties, shorten the time to market of new products and spread innovation risks, adopted by enterprises throughout the innovation process from idea to R&D and then to commercialisation.

2.2.2 Open Innovation Models

Open innovation models, as a new paradigm for technological innovation, consider how organisations can use the 'incoming' and 'outgoing' flows of knowledge across their boundaries to increase their likelihood of innovation success (Chesbrough, 2006), and scholars have identified a variety of open innovation models along several dimensions. Chesbrough (2003) originally defined open innovation models as two separate processes, namely, the internalisation of external innovation and the external commercialisation of internal innovation. Chesbrough & Crowther (2006) classify open innovation as inward and outward-oriented. Scholars have developed different open innovation models by differentiating between knowledge flow's internal and external boundaries. Inward-oriented open innovation in the open innovation

model means that the enterprise should bring core knowledge and technological resources from outside the enterprise into the enterprise. In addition, the resources brought in should be fully integrated with the internal knowledge and technology so that the enterprise can better innovate and commercialise the integrated core knowledge and innovation. Outward-oriented open innovation refers to the outward flow of the enterprise's core knowledge and technology resources to external organisations, providing them with their core resources, which can be commercialised to bring more business value to the enterprise. Gassmann et al. (2004) suggest that open innovation should include three components: outside-in, inside-out, and coupled. Inside-out innovation is created within one's internal knowledge circle and by integrating internal and external knowledge, such as core sources from external actors such as customers and suppliers, to enrich the company's knowledge base. According to Henkel (2014), outside-in open innovation accelerates an enterprise's R&D progress through the inflow of resources. Inside-out open innovation is a way to expand the market through the flow of resources and to enhance the enterprise's reputation. Outside-in and inside-out open innovation can co-exist and influence each other, called coupled open innovation.

Other scholars have classified open innovation models into a richer typology in terms of innovation outcomes, innovation processes and organisational perspectives (von Hippel & von Krogh, 2006; Keupp & Gassmann, 2009; Belderbos et al., 2010; Lichtenthaler, 2008; Bianchi et al., 2011). Although the criteria for classifying open innovation models are not uniform, they mainly revolve around the attributes of knowledge flows. Therefore, based on the flow of knowledge, this thesis classifies open innovation models of technology-based SMEs into outside-in, coupled and inside-out open innovation models. The outside-in open innovation model refers to searching and acquiring external knowledge and integrating it with the enterprise's internal knowledge base for innovation. The inside-out open innovation model refers to transferring unused and underused ideas and assets to the external

market to commercialise technological knowledge externally. The coupled open innovation model refers to the co-creation process with complementary partner enterprises through alliances, collaborations and joint ventures.

2.2.3 Open Innovation Models and Innovation Performance

The research findings on the impact of open innovation models on innovation performance vary, but in summary, there are four main views: positive impact, negative impact, inverted U-shaped impact, and insignificant impact.

Positive Impact

Fundamentally, open innovation is based on a wealth of knowledge, which must be accessible to provide value to the enterprise that creates it (Chesbrough, 2003). Open innovation can be divided into two phases: R&D and commercialisation, but open innovation emphasises the acquisition and exploitation of external innovation resources and the external commercialisation of internal technologies. Thus, open innovation will generate innovation performance by opening up R&D and technology commercialisation activities.

(1) The Impact of Openness in R&D Activities on Innovation Performance

In the open innovation model, R&D departments are established to link up with external knowledge resources and to select proper knowledge for internal use (Chesbrough, 2003). This change in the role of the R&D department has led to a change in the function of the internal R&D staff, who, in addition to facilitating the renewal of technology, also facilitate the inflow and outflow of technology (Chesbrough, 2004). As enterprise boundaries open up, the growing number of external knowledge sources will challenge enterprises to balance internal and external R&D. External R&D activities can, to a certain extent, contribute to the growth of entrepreneurial innovation performance and

the entrepreneurial R&D capabilities of the enterprise can help to enhance the contribution of external R&D activities to entrepreneurial innovation performance (Berchicci, 2013). For SMEs, collaborative research and R&D outsourcing are essential means of external R&D activities and an essential complement to internal R&D resources. The higher the level of training and the higher the experts' qualifications, the more likely the SME's R&D executives will use collaborative R&D to establish links with external knowledge, while the opposite is true for outsourcing (Teirlinck & Spithoven, 2013). R&D outsourcing facilitates the development of new products, improves innovation performance, and has modularity, learning, distance and mediation effects on innovation performance (Hsuan & Mahnke, 2011). External technology acquisition has a positive effect on enterprise innovation performance, and increasing internal R&D investment will maintain the positive effect of open innovation on enterprise innovation performance (Hung & Chou, 2013).

In the R&D process, SMEs' strategy for introducing knowledge and utilising different external knowledge sources can also impact innovation performance. The introduction of external knowledge positively impacts SMEs' innovation performance in developed and developing countries (Laursen & Salter, 2006; Chen, 2011). Under the influence of specific knowledge integration and organisational approval costs, the degree of openness of scientists and engineers to external knowledge contributes to an enterprise's innovation performance (Salter et al., 2015). Access to external knowledge affects not only the financial performance of enterprises but also their R&D (Kafouros & Forsans, 2012).

(2) The Impact of Technology Commercialisation on Innovation Performance

The impact of technology commercialisation on innovation performance is primarily achieved through technology commercialisation capabilities. The role of technology commercialisation capability is to enhance enterprise

performance through the exploitation and realisation of the value of ideas (Zhang, 2016). From the perspective of knowledge inflow, enterprises that adopt the outside-in open innovation model can generate breakthrough new technologies through knowledge collisions (Das & Teng, 2000) and develop highly novel products to meet customer needs, thereby increasing the success rate of technology commercialisation (Zahra & Nielsen, 2002). From a knowledge outflow perspective, adopting the inside-out open innovation model allows enterprises to commercialise internal technologies through external means, which helps nurture and retain loyal innovators and increase their motivation to innovate (Rigby & Zook, 2002). This can also be achieved by transferring patent rights to internal technologies to generate royalties (Chesbrough, 2003), expand access to the technology and increase the visibility of the enterprise (Rigby & Zook, 2002). The use of an inside-out open innovation model to commercialise the technology for innovation performance has been the subject of much qualitative discussion and descriptive statistical analysis, with studies suggesting that enterprises can reap both financial and strategic benefits from using the inside-out open innovation model (Yao, 2003; Kline, 2003).

Negative Impact

Too much openness to innovation can harm its long-term innovation success, as it can lead to a loss of control and core competencies. In the open innovation model, enterprises' R&D models may be a new shift from the old internal R&D model, and the business model is not based on purely open innovation but on enterprises that invest in both closed and open innovation activities (Enkel et al., 2009). Collaborative product development increases the dependency of enterprises on external technologies, raising sequential issues such as increased coordination costs, the need to manage new skills across boundaries, staff management adjustments, technology under partner control and leakage of critical technical knowledge, leading to a decline in innovation performance (Biemans, 1995).

Excessive search, acquisition and exploitation of external innovation knowledge can harm innovation performance. The volatility of the technological and market environment increases the uncertainty of innovation projects, thus requiring enterprises to establish more connections with external knowledge sources, thus creating uncertainty (Gales, 1995), and the excessive search will lead to increased costs of knowledge search, along with increased costs of coordination of relationships between more partners. Utilising external innovation resources requires the enterprises to increase their absorptive capability (Cohen, 1990), and too many external innovation resources will lead to problems of reallocation of management attention (Ocasio, 1997). Excessive utilisation of external innovation resources may affect the strategic position of the internal R&D department, resulting in over-dependence on external technologies, domination by partners in critical technologies and even loss of core competencies (Johnsen & Ford, 2000). Adopting the open innovation model for technology-based start-ups can lead to the leakage of critical technological knowledge (Laursen, 2005). Information leakage is most severe when working with potential competitors (Tidd, 1997) and is inevitable when working with non-competitors. Sensitive business information and technical knowledge may be leaked to competitors through shared suppliers or customers, reducing innovation performance.

Inverted U-shaped and Insignificant Impact

Livio et al. (2015), taking the depth of openness into account, conclude that open innovation has an inverted U-shaped effect on innovation performance and that excessive access to and reliance on external resources can, on the contrary, discourage internal innovation and thus reduce the level of innovation performance. Some scholars have also refined this analysis. For example, Zhou (2018) divided open innovation into inward-oriented open innovation and outward-oriented open innovation and explored the impact on innovation performance from these two dimensions. The study concludes that

inward open innovation causes innovation performance to change from negative to positive in an inverted "U" curve; the impact of the outward open innovation on performance is negative in the short term, gradually turning positive with time and increasing in a quadratic curve. This view coincides with the findings of Yang et al. (2020), who concluded that there is an optimal innovation point for enterprises to exploit the depth of open innovation. In contrast, Inauen et al. (2011) found that the impact of open innovation on innovation performance varies for different external agents. The level of internal innovation performance is increased when open to consumers, research institutes and manufacturers; the impact is insignificant when open to technology consulting services; the impact is negative when open to cross-industry enterprises.

2.3 Absorptive Capability

2.3.1 Definition of Absorptive Capability

Kedia & Bhagat (1988) were the first to introduce absorptive capability as a term but did not clearly define its meaning. Cohen & Levinthal (1990) formalised the concept of absorptive capability by defining it as the ability of enterprises to identify and digest external information that helps them to transform it into business value. The study concluded that absorptive capability was based on organisational considerations, specifically an organisation's ability to identify, digest and utilise external knowledge and ultimately apply it for business purposes, where it was seen as a static resource for the enterprise. On this basis, scholars have conducted extensive and in-depth research on absorptive capability.

Among them, Zahra & George (2002) identify absorptive capability as a set of organisational practices and processes by which enterprises acquire, assimilate, transform and utilise external knowledge and divide it into two dimensions: potential absorptive capability and realised absorptive capability.

Potential absorptive capability includes acquisition and digestion, while realised absorptive capability includes transformation and utilisation, a perspective that has contributed significantly to research on absorptive capability. In an analysis of the impact of absorptive capability on the technological progress of industries in the Chinese industrial sector, Zhang (2005) considers absorptive capability as the ability to imitate, absorb and digest advanced external technologies. Lane et al. (2006) define absorptive capability as acquiring, digesting and applying external knowledge and technology to help the enterprise transform it into its internal capabilities. The connotations of absorptive capability are primarily consistent, and there is little academic debate on the definition of absorptive capability. Therefore, this paper draws on Rodríguez et al. (2010) to define absorptive capability as the capability of an enterprise to acquire, digest, transform and apply external R&D knowledge.

2.3.2 Research of Absorptive Capability

The absorptive capability enables enterprises to understand the market needs through knowledge improvement and promptly adjust product features and functions (Peteraf, 1993; Cassiman & Veugelers, 2002). The results of R&D activities by enterprises are primarily in the form of knowledge. The positive externality of knowledge means that once it is generated, other enterprises inevitably apply it, and the enterprise that invests in R&D does not have exclusive access to its R&D knowledge, and other enterprises can benefit economically from imitating the results of R&D (Arrow, 1962). Some studies have enriched and refined Cohen & Levinthal's (1990) work; for example, scholars have argued that absorptive capability should not be seen as a static resource of enterprises but as a dynamic capability (Zahra & George, 2002; Lane et al. 2012; Patterson & Ambrosini, 2015; Martinkenaite & Breunig, 2016).

Among them, Zahra & George (2002) provide a deeper insight into the nature of absorptive capability based on existing studies, which concluded that absorptive capability includes both potential and realised absorptive capability and that absorptive capability, as a type of organisational dynamic capability, helps enterprises to cultivate competitive advantage. Gergana et al. (2007) and other scholars consider the absorptive capability to be a dynamic process of knowledge utilisation with a feedback mechanism and divide it into four stages: value assessment, knowledge acquisition, internalisation and knowledge utilisation, which coincide with Zahra & George's definition and classification of absorptive capability. In this paper, the authors agree with Zahra & George (2002) that absorptive capability is a dynamic capability of an enterprise. However, since more than half of the entrepreneurs interviewed in the pilot survey based on grounded theory conducted before the study explicitly mentioned the relationship between absorptive capability and their own innovation model and innovation performance, the absorptive capability is treated as a separate factor in this research. It does not contradict the view that absorptive capability is a dynamic capability of the enterprise.

Among the classifications of studies on absorptive capability, one is the use of R&D investment intensity, the number of patents, and the number of R&D personnel to measure absorptive capability, and data on such quantitative parameters are easy to obtain in practice. In measuring absorptive capability, Wang (2015) chose the ratio of R&D personnel as a measure and concluded that the number of researchers is directly proportional to providing new ideas and contributing new technologies to the enterprise, which in turn promotes the transformation of external information, technology and other innovative resources into internal knowledge. In a related study, Xu & Chi (2016) focus on the R&D investment, human capital and employee motivation of enterprises as the focus for conducting the measurement of absorptive capability. Gao (2017), meanwhile, used the number of published scientific and technical papers as an indicator to measure absorptive capability. Dushnitsky & Lenox (2005), Hassinger (2012), Hu & Wu (2015), and Qi &

Song (2021) also measure absorptive capability by adopting the number of patents of enterprises.

On the other hand, most scholars argue that quantitative indicators cannot distinguish the multiple dimensions and dynamic characteristics of absorptive capability. Therefore, more and more scholars choose to conduct in-depth questionnaire surveys to describe the absorptive capability of enterprises. Zhou et al. (2016) adopted the suggestions of relevant experts and enterprise stakeholders to establish an absorptive capability survey scale that includes four dimensions: acquisition, digestion, transformation and development capabilities. Liu (2016) and Zhu & Wang (2017) measured absorptive capability in three dimensions: knowledge acquisition, knowledge assimilation and knowledge application. Xie & Zuo (2013), Xin & Zhang (2018), and Li & Zeng (2021) also measure the absorptive capability of enterprises through questionnaires.

2.3.3 Absorptive Capability, Open Innovation and Innovation Performance

The literature on the impact of open innovation on absorptive capability is relatively scarce, and most studies have concluded that open innovation positively impacts absorptive capability. Vanhaverbeke et al. (2008) were the first to link open innovation and absorptive capability, laying an essential foundation for studying the relationship between the pair. Since then, the relationship between open innovation and absorptive capability has been investigated empirically. Wynarczyk (2013) suggests that by embedding internal open innovation into external innovation networks, enterprises can enhance their internal human, capital and equipment resources, and these internal inputs can increase absorptive capability. Further, enterprises can expand their own market channels and external partner organisations' market channels to consolidate innovation outcomes.

It has also been argued that absorptive capability has a mediating role. However, the degree of openness must be reasonably chosen; otherwise, the mediating role is insignificant. In the empirical analysis, Zhang et al. (2015) concluded that the realised absorptive capability of enterprises plays a fully mediating role between open innovation and innovation performance. However, some enterprises with high potential absorptive capability still carry out high-intensity open innovation activities, which may cause an increase in costs. Yang et al. (2020) conducted a case study with Huawei, Haier and P&G, using absorptive capability as an essential mediating variable, concluding that absorptive capability is both a prerequisite and a target for the implementation of open innovation and that absorptive capability plays a driving role in the variation of open innovation.

Knowledge is considered a unique strategic resource that plays a critical role in business competition and becomes an essential source of competitive advantage for enterprises. Therefore, differences in knowledge between enterprises are considered the fundamental cause of differences in performance levels (Beatriz & César, 2011). Enterprises enrich their R&D knowledge base primarily through both internal R&D and external R&D knowledge. Moreover, relying only on internal R&D is often insufficient, and the ability to absorb is essential in determining whether an enterprise can accurately identify external R&D knowledge and apply it (Cho, 2014). Cassol et al. (2016) found that absorptive capability gives enterprises a competitive advantage by facilitating innovation. As there is a dual role for enterprises' R&D investment, it promotes their R&D innovation and enhances their ability to understand and digest external R&D knowledge (Cohen & Levinthal, 1989). Tsai's (2014) study also confirms the dual role of corporate R&D investment, supporting Cohen & Levinthal's (1989) view. Tzokas et al. (2015) studied 158 South Korean semiconductor industry enterprises and found that absorptive capability contributes to enterprise innovation performance improvement. Choi & Park (2016) examined the impact of absorptive capability on enterprise

performance based on two dimensions of absorptive capability and showed that both dimensions significantly contribute to enterprise innovation performance. Cosmas et al. (2020) also concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between absorptive capability and enterprise innovation performance. Juliane et al. (2021) empirically examined the impact of both potential and realised absorptive capability on enterprise performance in a sample of low-technology industries in Brazil and Portugal. They found that potential and realised absorptive capability significantly improved enterprise innovation performance.

2.4 Dynamic Capability

2.4.1 Definition of Dynamic Capability

Dynamic capability theory is derived from the theory of competitive advantage based on the resource-based view. It believes that enterprises can maintain their competitive advantage in a dynamic environment by adjusting their business model due to the substitution effect brought about by technological progress. Teece (1994) was the first to introduce the concept of "dynamic capability", which he believed was the ability of an enterprise to coordinate internal and external resources, adjust and improve its capabilities to adapt to market changes, rapidly and flexibly update its products, and achieve co-evolution with the environment. Later, Teece et al. (1997) proposed the basic concept of dynamic capability, in which they argued that "dynamic" refers to the ability of an enterprise to continuously update its competencies to adapt to the changing market environment, while "capability" refers to the ability to integrate and reconfigure internal and external organisational skills and resources to adapt to changes in the environment. Dynamic capability theory has been continuously developed and refined, and its core ideas have adapted to the environment of gradually increasing market competition and played an essential role in strategy. Scholars have divided the research on the connotation of dynamic capability into two directions: "capability" and process".

From the perspective of 'capability', dynamic capability is the ability of an enterprise to renew itself around a rational allocation of core resources. Griffith & Harvey (2001) argue that dynamic capabilities are the ability to create a combination of resources that are difficult for other enterprises to imitate. Winter (2003) suggests that dynamic capabilities expand and create enterprise-specific resources that provide feedback into the enterprise's value creation, enabling a leap from resources to value. Teece (2007) argues that dynamic capabilities are the ability of an enterprise to perceive its environment and seize opportunities by integrating its existing resources. Wilkens & Sprafke (2015) argue that enterprises purposefully reconfigure their resources to adapt to changing market demands. Helfat & Martin (2015) suggest that dynamic capabilities have evolved along with the Internet economy into a higher-order capability that encompasses the ability to manage, create, modify and implement new business models to achieve business growth.

From a 'process' perspective, dynamic capability is the process by which enterprises reshape their resources and utilise them in response to the market environment at different stages of growth. Zollo & Winter (2002) suggest that dynamic capabilities are a collective action model in learning organisations, whereby enterprises renew their internal and external resources and adjust their development paths to enhance value creation. Steiber & Alänge (2016) argue that dynamic capabilities are the evolution of enterprises' unique resources, which are difficult to replicate because they are based on the culture and managerial characteristics of the company and are born in the process of implementing strategies and organisational adjustments.

This paper defines dynamic capability as the ability of an enterprise to perceive changes in the external environment, to identify and create business opportunities from them, and to integrate internal and external resources to

seize them in order to proactively adapt to changes in the external environment, following Teece et al. (1997). It is structured into three dimensions: the ability to sense, capture, and transform opportunities.

2.4.2 Research of Dynamic Capability

The dynamic capability theory has been widely used in many fields since its conception, but for this study, a selective review of the literature is presented in this section. Based on the literature review, the author finds no uniformity in classifying dynamic capability dimensions in academia. The dynamic capabilities of enterprises include tacit knowledge, internal structural ambiguity, the intersection of multiple capabilities and the specificity of the capability formation process, which are difficult for other competitors to imitate and replicate (Teece, 1997). Hence, the dimensions of the dynamic capabilities of enterprises are diverse. For example, Eisenhardt & Martin (2000) analyse the dynamic capabilities of enterprises with the help of the resource-based view and classify them into integration, reconfiguration, acquisition, and release capabilities. Dong et al. (2012) argue that environmental adaptability should be added to this list. Xin (2011), through the theory of knowledge base view, is divided into three dimensions, namely, search and identification of external knowledge, screening and evaluation of external knowledge, and transformation and integration of external knowledge, to visualise the process of shaping dynamic capabilities of enterprises. Wang (2016) studied the allocation process of internal and external resources in enterprise technological innovation and classified dynamic capabilities into input, transformation, and output capabilities. Mi et al. (2021) classify dynamic capabilities into environmental perception, learning and innovation, and organisational coordination capabilities from evolutionary resource actions.

The formation and enhancement of dynamic capabilities are also inextricably linked to the accumulation and management of enterprise knowledge. The knowledge-based view of dynamic capability considers that the dynamic

capability of an enterprise involves the dynamic process of application and reconstruction of knowledge. The process of knowledge application and reconstruction should always be closely integrated. Employees' knowledge carrier and knowledge system structure are reconstructed through continuous feedback and revision of existing knowledge so enterprises can quickly adapt to the rapidly changing competitive environment (Wei & Zhang, 2007).

Dynamic capability reflects an enterprise's knowledge aggregate, which is the ability of an enterprise to maintain and change the basis of its competitive advantage. It is the process of an enterprise's continuous pursuit and innovation of knowledge, establishing its set of innovative knowledge architecture (Dong, 2004). Knowledge assets are essential in enhancing enterprise competitiveness because enterprise performance is influenced by knowledge attributes and factors such as an enterprise's basic operating capabilities, complementary assets and technologies, and intellectual property protection (Teece, 1998). Eisenhardt (2000) argues that updating knowledge and capabilities to adapt to the competitive market environment contributes to an enterprise's competitive advantage.

At the same time, organisational learning is the primary mechanism through which enterprises build dynamic capabilities. Dosi (2000) argues that there is a close relationship between knowledge learning and dynamic capabilities. Subba (2001) suggests that dynamic capabilities manifest knowledge that generates diverse business. Zollo (2002) suggests that dynamic capabilities are derived from learning, a stable collective learning model that enables enterprises to improve organisational performance by systematically creating or adapting operational rules. Nielsen (2006) categorised knowledge management activities into three vital dynamic capabilities of knowledge development, re-integration and application, combining dynamic capabilities and knowledge management activities to explain better the mechanism of capability development and renewal in organisations.

2.4.3 Dynamic Capability and Open Innovation Models

The open innovation model helps enterprises acquire and commercialise internal knowledge through external channels. Due to the shocks in the external environment, more and more enterprises choose open innovation to eliminate the limitations of their resources, thus forming the technological innovation capability of enterprises and possessing the characteristics of dynamic capabilities in adapting to the environment (Chen, 2015). In adapting to environmental changes, dynamic capabilities coordinate with the enterprises' innovation strategy to help the enterprise achieve innovation performance and open innovation as a branch element of innovation strategy. Therefore, there is a mutual influence relationship between open innovation and the dynamic capabilities of enterprises.

There is little research on the contribution of dynamic capabilities to the implementation of open innovation models, but the contribution of dynamic capabilities is evident in studies of organisational capabilities. Several scholars have emphasised the need to balance the ability to benefit from external knowledge with the ability to develop internal knowledge (Chesbrough, 2003; Nielsen, 2006; Teece, 2007). Open innovation models can only be effectively implemented if dynamic capabilities change organisational practices (Ma & Song, 2014). Thus, dynamic capabilities are essential in facilitating and supporting the implementation of open innovation models in enterprises (Liu & Meng, 2016; Li & Qi, 2017; Wang et al., 2018). When organisations implement open innovation, they need to dynamically develop practices to match them and develop dynamic capabilities through the evolution of organisational practices to respond to changes in the market and environment. Dynamic capabilities are based on the knowledge embedded in organisational practices and processes, and learning is about integrating new knowledge into the existing knowledge base, thereby enhancing existing corporate capabilities and developing new capabilities (Ren & Wu et al., 2011). In an open innovation environment, absorptive

capability is central to the knowledge-learning perspective and is a foundational capability that constitutes a dynamic capability.

Meanwhile, in the field of open innovation process research, there are still obvious 'black process box' issues, including how the open innovation behaviour of enterprises affects the formation of organisational knowledge capabilities and how the formation of dynamic organisational knowledge capabilities affects innovation performance. Addressing these questions can help effectively identify the dynamics and evolutionary mechanisms underlying enterprises' adoption of open innovation models (Nie & Zhang, 2013). The current study found that implementing an open innovation model helps enterprises build dynamic capabilities (Huang et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2015; Liu & Meng, 2016).

2.4.4 Dynamic Capability and Innovation Performance

The direct impact of dynamic capabilities on innovation performance is primarily positive. As there are various ways to classify the component dimensions of dynamic capabilities, existing studies have focused on examining the impact of dynamic capabilities on innovation performance.

Winter (2003) states that dynamic capabilities are a higher-order manifestation of an enterprise's ability to reallocate its resources to shape new sources of value. Most scholars agree that dynamic capabilities have a positive effect on enterprises' innovation performance and that dynamic capabilities combine the business environment and industrial ecosystem in which they operate to capture scarce resources specific to the enterprise, create new value growth points, and maintain a long-term competitive advantage for the enterprise (Ma et al., 2014). Griffith & Harvey (2006) found that dynamic capabilities integrate and reconfigure endogenous resources, enabling enterprises to obtain new sources of value and economic growth in

production processes and product innovation. Schike (2014), based on the dynamic capability theory, showed that product development and strategic coordination capability enhance enterprise innovation performance through a longitudinal case study. Jiang et al. (2014) analysed the effect of dynamic capabilities on the innovation performance of enterprises through dynamic capabilities theory. Yue et al. (2019) collected data to conduct an empirical study and found that technological innovation capabilities positively affect technology commercialisation performance. Jin et al. (2019) dissected the cultivation process of enterprises' perceived capabilities in the context of dual innovation strategy and deeply analysed the role of dynamic capabilities in promoting enterprise innovation performance.

Meanwhile, some scholars have found that developing dynamic capabilities is demanding for enterprises. Colombo et al. (2010) argue that corporate culture, organisational flexibility, and technological development can affect the development of dynamic capabilities and that if resources are not used effectively, dynamic capabilities can lead to a waste of resources and loss of efficiency. Makkonen (2014) shows that dynamic capabilities hurt enterprise innovation performance in a highly volatile environment and that differences impact innovation performance at different stages of growth.

Enterprise innovation performance is influenced by several factors, including political relations, knowledge, social capital, innovation networks and management, and dynamic capabilities that mediate and moderate between these influences and innovation performance (Michailova & Zhan, 2015; Zhao et al., 2016; Zhang & Xu, 2017).

In summary, this paper finds that scholars agree that dynamic capabilities positively affect enterprise performance, explore the paths of value creation through the cultivation of dynamic capabilities from several research

perspectives, and analyse the generation of dynamic capabilities in different dimensions and their effects on enterprise performance. However, there is still potential for research on the paths and mechanisms of dynamic capabilities' impact on open innovation models and enterprise innovation performance.

2.5 Cognitive Inertia

2.5.1 Definition of Cognitive Inertia

The principle of inertia in physics states that an object will continue in a state of rest or uniform motion unless acted upon by an external force. Thus, until an external force interferes, it is possible to guess the subsequent direction of an object based on its law of inertia. Drawing on this concept, more and more scholars have started to investigate consumption inertia (Chen et al., 2014), price inertia (Christoph et al., 2021), structural inertia (Dotsenko et al., 2020), organisational inertia (Patrick et al., 2021), and even outsourcing inertia of enterprises (Mol & Kotabe, 2010) and other derived concepts. As research continues to expand and refine, scholars have also taken note of the concept of cognitive inertia.

Liao (2002), the originator of 'cognitive inertia', argues that cognitive inertia is the nature of knowledge management. It stems from the natural tendency of individuals or organisations to use conventional problem-solving procedures, stagnant sources of knowledge, and to follow past knowledge or experience when faced with a problem to be solved, which may facilitate or inhibit individual or organisational problem-solving abilities. Yuan et al. (2005) have a negative attitude towards cognitive inertia, arguing that "thinking inertia", "dogmatism", and "empiricism" are all common life behaviours of stubbornly using old knowledge, i.e. cognitive inertia, which reflects the difficulty of knowledge mobility within an organisation, which reduces the efficiency and effectiveness of cognitive accumulation, sharing, innovation and application in enterprises. Factors affecting cognitive inertia include personal, organisational

and IT factors, where personal factors directly influence learning relationships and experience inertia, and organisational and IT-related factors, in turn, influence personal factors (Kafchehi et al., 2012).

From the perspective of individual learning, Zhao et al. (2012) and Yang (2015) argue that individual employees' knowledge systems and cognitive structures significantly impact their cognitive processes and habitually follow old ideas, information and knowledge. If the new knowledge acquired contradicts the old knowledge structure and if this new knowledge is not sufficiently stimulating, it is difficult for the individual employee to continue the learning process and acquire new knowledge. The advantages of this inertia are that it saves time, increases efficiency and helps to maintain an advantage, while the disadvantage is that it hinders the progress of the individual employee and the organisation. Zhou & Chen et al. (2011) propose that cognitive inertia is a "magical" force that is invisible and untouchable but exists in real life, which can induce enterprises to rely on the knowledge for a long time, thus not conducive to keeping up with the latest market trends and making timely innovation. This is not conducive to keeping up with the latest market trends and making timely innovations. Guo et al. (2021) argue that cognitive inertia is a common approach to solving general business problems and that this same approach to solving common problems saves time and effort and avoids risk.

To summarise the above points, this thesis defines cognitive inertia as a predictable management behaviour and problem-solving strategy that individuals continue to use to solve new problems the enterprise faces without modifying and updating their historical knowledge, experience and procedure. Based on Liao et al. (2018), Li et al. (2019), and Cao et al. (2021), cognitive inertia is divided into learning, experience, and procedural inertia.

2.5.2 Research of Cognitive Inertia

Kafchehi et al. (2012) found from a study of over 1,700 employees working in private and state-owned banks in Kurdistan that personal factors directly impact the cognitive inertia of the enterprise. When employees believe the current solution is not the best, they will continue searching for new knowledge to obtain a better solution. The findings also suggest that organisational and IT factors do not directly influence cognitive inertia but indirectly influence cognitive inertia by affecting individual factors. Yuan et al. (2005) argued that cognitive inertia is influenced by knowledge subjects' recognition of existing knowledge, acceptance of new things, validation costs, etc. The higher the recognition, the lower the acceptance of new knowledge, the higher the cost of correctness testing, and the greater the cognitive inertia of the enterprise. Zhou & Chen (2011) identified the influence of three sink factors on the strength of cognitive inertia: the temporal validity of knowledge, the reinforcement validity of knowledge and the sunk cost in the knowledge selection mechanism, in the context of life cycle theory. The longer the time, the deeper the reliance on the knowledge and the greater the structural inertia of the knowledge, i.e., the timeliness of the knowledge reinforces the cognitive inertia. In practice, enterprises will continue to reinforce this knowledge due to the high benefits of applying it, which in turn helps reinforce enterprises' cognitive inertia. When knowledge timeliness and knowledge reinforcement weaken and approach the decline, enterprises will consider updating knowledge. However, the existence of sunk cost creates a barrier for enterprises to choose new knowledge to replace existing knowledge, i.e. the sunk cost in the knowledge selection mechanism will resist the inflow of new knowledge and strengthen cognitive inertia. Zhou & Zhou (2021) found that a high level of cognitive inertia would make R&D teams rely heavily on old knowledge, affecting the flow of knowledge among team members and hindering the creation and inflow of new knowledge. Taking e-commerce enterprises as the research object, Xu (2019) suggested that cognitive inertia would lead to path locking and efficiency stagnation, affecting the speed and efficiency of new knowledge learning in enterprises.

Some scholars also define learning inertia as the willingness and initiative to learn new knowledge and find new sources of knowledge, which is a kind of inertia thinking to change knowledge learning behaviour. Li & Zeng (2019) argue that enterprises with strong learning inertia actively explore new sources of knowledge, acquire new external knowledge, and constantly think of new solutions and try new methods. Guo et al. (2021) argue that learning inertia refers to the tendency of organisations to learn new knowledge to break or change their old habitual thinking when faced with problems. Other scholars have selected the three-dimensional scales of procedural, informational, and experiential inertia to study the different effects of different dimensions of cognitive inertia (Zhou et al., 2014; Fan et al., 2016).

2.5.3 Cognitive Inertia and Innovation Performance

Li & Zeng (2019) explored the impact of learning inertia and experience inertia in cognitive inertia on enterprise dual innovation in terms of dual characteristics; both learning inertia and experience inertia have a significant positive impact on incremental enterprise innovation but have an inverted U-shaped impact on breakthrough innovation. An increase in cognitive inertia leads enterprises to deepen the application of their existing knowledge base and to research and develop new technologies along a technological track in which they excel, facilitating incremental innovation. With too much cognitive inertia, enterprises will become dependent on that part of knowledge, which is not conducive to the birth of disruptive ideas. While Xie et al. (2016) proposed that product innovation is closely related to cognitive inertia, data on high-tech industries in the Yangtze River Delta region were collected through a stratified random sampling method. The empirical findings show that experience inertia, learning inertia, and procedural inertia positively impact enterprise product innovation, with product innovation relying mainly on existing R&D experience and knowledge and cognitive inertia facilitating enterprises to learn new knowledge, develop innovative thinking and improve product development

standards. The study also found that procedural inertia benefits product innovation, which is inconsistent with the proposed hypothesis. The main reason is that high-tech enterprises must constantly innovate their thinking and R&D methods to grow fast in a dynamic environment and, therefore, not fall into procedural inertia. Guo et al. (2021) also empirically tested the impact of cognitive inertia on the innovation performance of expatriate employees, where those with higher experience inertia and learning inertia tended to achieve higher innovation capability and innovation performance. Zhou & Chen (2014) argued that cognitive inertia exists in the whole process of enterprise knowledge management and affects knowledge flow, knowledge change and the creation of new knowledge in enterprises, and the greater the competitive advantage and the more mature the management operation, the stronger the cognitive inertia is and the more detrimental to the future innovation development of that enterprise.

Zhou et al. (2014) introduced knowledge integration, a positive factor, as a mediating variable and demonstrated the relationship between cognitive inertia and new product development performance through empirical analysis. Based on this study, Fan et al. (2016) explored the relationship between the three dimensions of cognitive inertia and the performance of service enterprises, taking the knowledge-intensive service industry as the research object. Among them, empirical inertia indirectly influenced enterprise performance improvement through organisational learning. In contrast, procedural inertia and information inertia directly or indirectly negatively influenced enterprise performance through organisational learning, which was not entirely consistent with the findings of Zhou et al. but also confirmed that different dimensions of cognitive inertia would bring different effects on enterprise innovation activities. Liu et al. (2020) found that cognitive inertia tends to make enterprises fall into the "innovation trap" and negatively affects their innovation performance, while experience inertia can stabilise their R&D behaviour and improve their innovation performance through the collection and analysis of R&D innovation and patent data from listed enterprises.

Mohammad (2010) found that experience inertia is positively related to organisational learning, while learning inertia is negatively related to organisational learning, i.e. making use of previous experience can help enterprises improve their learning efficiency and thus positively influence their innovation. Akuzum (2014) found that experience inertia was positively related to organisational learning and organisational performance while learning inertia was negatively related to organisational learning and organisational performance by constructing a structural equation model with a sample of over 400 teachers. Teachers' perceptions of experiential inertia were significantly higher than their perceptions of learning inertia, and, therefore, teachers were more likely to use their professional experience to enhance their organisational learning to improve organisational performance.

Some scholars have also correlated cognitive inertia as a moderating variable. For example, Zhao et al. (2012) found that cognitive inertia negatively moderated the relationship between organisational learning and employee and organisational fit through a study of state-owned enterprises, private enterprises and government institutions. Fang et al. (2011) examined the mechanism of cognitive inertia as a moderating variable between organisational learning ability and organisational innovation by collecting more than 500 valid questionnaires from hospital nurses in central Taiwan. The empirical analysis revealed that cognitive inertia leads to learning inertia, which hinders the improvement of organisational learning ability and, in the long run, is detrimental to the stimulation of innovative behaviour, i.e. it weakens the positive impact of organisational learning ability on organisational innovation performance.

In summary, it has been found that although there is a growing body of research on the influence of cognitive inertia on enterprise innovation performance, the theoretical explanations and research findings are not

entirely consistent or even contradictory. Moreover, few scholars have researched open innovation or open models and cognitive inertia together.

2.6 Innovation Performance

2.6.1 Definition of Innovation Performance

As an effective way for enterprises to achieve rapid growth, innovation has been widely valued by academics and practitioners alike. Since the concept of "innovation" first emerged, scholars have deconstructed innovation from different perspectives, including innovation outcome theory and process theory. The innovation outcome theory suggests that innovation is the creation of a new outcome, including products, processes, services, etc., and the resulting innovation performance is the improvement in performance and market revenue that these outcomes bring to the enterprise (Muller & Peres, 2019). According to Ustalar et al. (2020), enterprise innovation performance can be described as the sum of the performance of all types of knowledge and technology generated in innovation activities in the daily production operations of an enterprise, specifically in terms of the number of new products generated by the enterprise in a single innovation activity, as well as the extent and quality of these new products. Bai et al. (2019) and Du et al. (2021) also measure innovation performance, often directly regarding the amount of data on enterprise patents. The outcome view considers that an enterprise is considered to have innovation performance only if it achieves an increase in ultimate profits through its innovation activities, emphasising the degree of marketability of innovation outcomes. The outcome theory of innovation is now more commonly used in academic research on service innovation (Xie et al., 2021) and business model innovation (Suwarna & Tuhin, 2021).

The innovation process theory considers innovation as a series of activities carried out by enterprises to create something new, and the resulting

innovation performance is the sum of all the results and all the benefits achieved in the whole process, from the creation of a new idea to the emergence of something new, which is a comprehensive evaluation index. Li et al. (2018) proposed that improving enterprise innovation performance is closely related to the continuous accumulation of knowledge in its production process from the perspective of a knowledge base view. Many current scholars also frequently use the ratio of various resource inputs to real innovation outputs to explain enterprise innovation performance, pointing out that innovation gains include both explicit achievements such as scientific and technological breakthroughs and increased economic benefits, as well as the accumulation of tacit achievements such as knowledge and experience (Wu et al., 2021). Gabriele et al. (2020) argue that the innovation process of enterprises should not just be a solo effort but should establish alliances and cooperative network relationships with external parties to conduct joint R&D and innovation through cross-fertilisation and should also obtain the required knowledge resources from government departments, banks and other financial institutions. Zhang & Hu (2020) suggest that the innovation performance of enterprises refers to the comprehensive evaluation of the output of innovation results, the improvement of productivity and the business contribution. Innovation performance is a reasonable standard to measure an enterprise's growth and long-term development, and it is the measurement and concern of the input-output ratio in an enterprise's production and operation process. Whether an enterprise can obtain good innovation performance depends on its future survival and market competitiveness. In studying innovation performance, some discretion must be given to innovation outcomes. This thesis, therefore, defines innovation performance as a measure of the essential outcomes of an enterprise's innovative activities, including the performance of new products and new technology development.

2.6.2 Measurement of Innovation Performance

There are various ways to measure the innovation performance of enterprises, one of which is to divide them into objective indicators that are objective and

unified and subjective indicators that require subjective perceptions and cannot be quantified. Objective indicators use standardised data to show the current state of innovation, while subjective indicators are selected to show the current state of development and innovation, which are difficult to quantify and can only be judged by human subjectivity. For example, financial indicators are often measured as objective indicators, including occupancy rate, quick ratio, current ratio, growth rate, etc. Peng et al. (2019) then used indicators such as the ratio of new product output value to total sales to measure the innovation performance of enterprises. Sun et al. (2020) used indicators of objectivity, such as the number of patents granted for enterprise inventions, to measure enterprise innovation performance when studying the technological innovation performance of the proprietary Chinese medicine manufacturing industry. Wu et al. (2021) selected three significant growth rates, i.e. patent growth rate, new product number growth rate, and new product sales revenue ratio growth rate, to measure the innovation performance of enterprises. Non-financial indicators include the speed and quality of new product development, customer satisfaction, and innovation potential. For example, Gnizy et al. (2018) and Feng et al. (2021) measured the innovation performance of enterprises with indicators related to the speed of new product development and the novelty of new products. Yang & Yang (2016) measured innovation performance by non-financial subjective perceptions such as whether the companies actively seek novel and innovative ideas, dare to enter new markets aggressively, and continuously analyse and study the needs of existing customers. Also, some scholars (Mousavi et al., 2018; Xu et al., 2021) combine financial and non-financial indicators to comprehensively assess various aspects of an enterprise's innovation performance through multiple performance indicators.

The second one can be divided into single and multidimensional indicators to measure the innovation performance of enterprises. Patent size, i.e. the number of patent applications, is by far the most recognised and frequently used single indicator in academic circles, which is more indicative of an

enterprise's innovation capability than other indicators (Gu et al., 2020). The data are objective, realistic, readily available, and, to a particular extent, representative of high-quality innovation. Some scholars also use only Tobin's Q (Liu et al., 2018) or the ratio of enterprise R&D investment to total operating revenue (Liu et al., 2021) to measure. Regarding multidimensional indicators, Li & Zeng (2021) set six suitable options for measuring enterprise innovation performance in terms of product and process innovation performance. Cui et al. (2015) measured enterprise innovation performance by three dimensions: having breakthrough innovative products or services, acquiring new knowledge or capabilities, and continuously adapting to market demand. Jiao et al. (2015) and Zheng & Liu (2021) measured corporate innovation performance from multiple perspectives, such as internal processes, management systems, new product sales revenue percentage, new technology application, corporate profitability, and market share. In addition to economic benefits, social and environmental benefits can be used as significant measures of an enterprise's innovation performance (Cao et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2015).

2.6.3 Research of Innovation Performance

The complexity and diversity of innovation activities of enterprises, despite the uncertainty of market risks, is an inevitable choice for enterprises to survive and grow and is critical know-how for them to maintain their long-term competitive advantage. Therefore, exploring the causal variables that affect enterprise innovation performance has been a hot topic in academia for a long time. This research thesis discusses internal and external factors based on the existing research literature.

External factors affecting enterprises' innovation performance include political connections, government policies, social capital and media attention. When enterprises attach importance to political affiliation in order to portray a good public interest image and gain the favour of the government and the public,

many of their behaviours will deviate from the market, and there will be a non-utilitarian application of resources, which in turn affects their innovation investment and is not conducive to improving innovation performance (Zhang, 2018). Nanda et al. (2013) argue that political affiliation can help enterprises obtain government support and access to more scarce resources inaccessible to other enterprises. In this way, enterprises can seize market opportunities and avoid uncertain risks in their innovation activities, increasing their willingness to innovate and promoting innovation performance. Policy uncertainty can cause enterprises to reduce innovation inputs and suspend plans for related innovation activities, waiting for the situation to become more apparent, thus weakening the output of innovation outcomes (Phan et al., 2019). It has become a consensus among academics and practitioners that tax incentives and financial subsidies can improve the innovation R&D level of enterprises. Tax incentives effectively motivate enterprises to invest more in innovation and alleviate financial constraints, and enterprises are more willing to undertake more risky and challenging innovation projects to gain a greater likelihood of innovation success. At the same time, receiving tax subsidies, i.e. gaining government and market recognition for the innovation project in question, can strengthen enterprises' belief in innovation and dispel the concerns of innovation agents, thus contributing to innovation performance (Bronzini & Piselli, 2016; Bianchi et al., 2019). By obtaining the required social capital through external relationship networks, enterprises can achieve complementary resources and facilitate the development and creation of new knowledge, and they can obtain timely and helpful information through external channels to quickly seize innovation opportunities and gain a first-mover competitive advantage in the market (Dong et al., 2020; Cui et al., 2020). Rodrigo-Alarcon et al. (2018) also demonstrate that social capital can stimulate enterprises' willingness to take risks and actively experiment with new methods and technologies. The impact of the media on business development in the information age cannot be overstated. Media coverage reduces the cost of communication between enterprises and consumers, government, etc.; media monitoring also enables enterprises to use innovation resources more rationally and regulated, effectively improving their

innovation efficiency and output (Bashir et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2020). It has also been suggested that media coverage can put more significant pressure on managers, who tend to act conservatively and choose inaction considering reputation and performance pressure, inhibiting innovation activities (Liu et al., 2019).

Internal factors can be divided into the individual level and the organisational level. As decision-makers and supervisors of innovation activities, executives directly impact innovation performance. Research has found that the cognitive ability of executives helps enterprises identify opportunities in a complex and volatile market environment and helps them avoid risks and make the right decisions by sensing and responding quickly to changes in the environment. Executives with solid cognitive ability can effectively reduce the resistance of enterprises to business model changes, help them reposition themselves in the market, identify their current strengths and weaknesses, and better promote their innovation activities, which in turn significantly affects their innovation performance (Osiyevskyy & Dewald, 2015; Vandor & Franke, 2016). In recent years, many scholars have begun to study female executives as a group. In contrast to the previous view that women are cautious, stable, lacking in risk-taking and are not conducive to corporate innovation, existing research has emphasised the positive effects of female executives on corporate decision-making. Female executives improve team tensions, facilitate effective corporate communication, introduce new perspectives to the enterprise from a female perspective, and actively propose new strategies and approaches to gain positive evaluations from the opposite sex, thus effectively improving corporate innovation performance (Liu et al., 2019). In addition, executives' risk appetite (Ye et al., 2021), international background (Liu et al., 2017), pay incentives (Mazouz & Zhao, 2019) and power intensity (Chen, 2014) are all closely related to enterprise innovation performance.

At an organisational level, the innovation performance of an enterprise is related to endogenous factors such as its learning capacity, knowledge absorption capability, intellectual capital and enterprise culture. Enterprises with a high learning capacity can maximise the inflow of knowledge into the enterprise and reuse old knowledge. Therefore, the stronger the learning capacity, the faster the R&D innovation rate of the enterprise, and the more conducive to a significant increase in innovation performance (Felicio et al., 2019). In a meta-analytic study, Ji et al. (2020) analysed 178 empirical papers on knowledge absorption and enterprise innovation. They showed that the absorption of new knowledge from the outside world expands the knowledge base of enterprises and makes them more receptive to new things, thus strengthening their innovation capabilities. The absorption of new knowledge can help enterprises break the shackles of resources and thinking, enhance the interaction between enterprises and external social relations, and maximise the application of knowledge value. Moreover, dynamic knowledge absorption has a stronger correlation with the innovation performance of enterprises than static knowledge absorption, which can continuously enhance enterprises' innovation capability and output. Intellectual capital is a critical resource necessary for the survival and development of enterprises. It is invisible and intangible, and, therefore, not easily imitated, and is highly value-added, helping enterprises to create value, solve problems efficiently, and significantly improve their technological development capabilities and competitive advantage in new products (Horchani & Zouaoui, 2021). Nowadays, research on intellectual capital has attracted attention at the national level, and Tatiana et al. (2021) show that the impact of intellectual capital on enterprises' innovation performance varies according to the national context. Moreover, the three dimensions of intellectual capital - organisational, human and relational capital - have different effects on enterprises' innovation performance under the influence of the macro environment. Baker et al. (2016) argue that enterprises with a strong innovation culture will be more willing to innovate and create stronger team cohesion, improving the enterprise's innovation capability by gathering ideas, opening up opinions and pooling group work efforts.

2.7 Summary of Literature Review

In this chapter, the relationship between technology-based SMEs and open innovation, open innovation and the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance, absorptive capability and the relationship between absorptive capability and open innovation models and innovation performance, dynamic capability and open innovation and innovation performance, cognitive inertia and the relationship between cognitive inertia on innovation performance, and the literature on innovation performance are reviewed, thus summarising the existing relevant research, identifying the gaps in existing research and laying the foundation for subsequent research on theoretical issues.

Some of the significant research gaps and points of disagreement include the impact of different innovation models adopted by technology-based SMEs on innovation performance, the relationship between different open innovation models and enterprises' absorptive capability, the relationship between different open innovation models and dynamic capabilities, and the relationship between different open innovation models and cognitive inertia. Moreover, for the theoretical studies mentioned in the literature review, few study conclusions have been conducted taking into account technology-based SMEs as research subjects.

In addition, the impact factors required in this thesis are not uniformly defined in academic circles due to differences in research focus. In this chapter, the authors summarise the research on each impact factor, defining them as consistent with this research's needs and providing a theoretical basis for the research hypotheses presented in the next chapter.

Chapter 3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Open innovation is a technological innovation that consciously and purposefully manages the flow of enterprise knowledge across the organisational boundaries model; its essence lies in creating or gaining innovative performance by utilising knowledge from inside and outside the enterprise. Based on the relevant theories and definitions collated in the literature review section of Chapter 2, this chapter analyses the impact relationships between the variables and proposes relevant research hypotheses. The research hypotheses are used to study the following four aspects: 1) The direct impact of the three open innovation models on innovation performance. 2) The impact of the open innovation models on absorptive capability, the impact of absorptive capability on innovation performance, and the mediating role of absorptive capability on open innovation models on innovation performance. 3) The impact of the open innovation models on dynamic capabilities, the impact of dynamic capabilities on innovation performance, and the mediating role of dynamic capabilities on open innovation models on innovation performance. 4) The impact of cognitive inertia on innovation performance, and the moderating role of cognitive inertia in the impact of open innovation models and innovation performance. Finally, a theoretical framework for the impact of open innovation models on enterprise innovation performance under the perspectives of absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and cognitive inertia is developed, and the mechanism of the impact is described in this chapter.

3.1 The Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

The key to the impact of an open innovation model on an enterprise's innovation performance is the extent to which the enterprise is open to innovation. Greater openness to innovation indicates that enterprises have

greater breadth and depth of knowledge search and access to more diverse and complementary knowledge with valuable, rare, imperfect and non-substitutable (VRIN) characteristics, which helps them to create innovative performance different from that of their competitors. However, if the degree of openness is too large, it may lead to increased transaction costs, information search costs and management costs for the enterprise, thus negatively impacting innovation performance. Therefore, the relationship between the openness of open innovation and an enterprise's innovation performance is uncertain.

3.1.1 Outside-in Open Innovation Model – Innovation Performance

Adopting an Outside-in open innovation model is to acquire external knowledge for use in the enterprise's internal innovation process. The greater the number of external knowledge sources available to the enterprise, the greater the innovation openness of the enterprise (Laurson & Salter, 2004), indicating that the enterprise has a greater breadth and depth of knowledge search possibilities, thus increasing the enterprise's access to more external and complementary diverse and heterogeneous knowledge (Laurson & Salter, 2006). Knowledge search is the process of establishing connections to external knowledge sources. From a purely statistical point of view, since the benefits of any given enterprise's external innovation connection are unknown, the chances of gaining benefits from any connection in a given distribution of benefits increase with the number of connections. Establishing more external connections increases the likelihood of acquiring practical external knowledge that can be combined with the enterprise's internal knowledge to innovate (Leiponen & Helfat, 2010), and the knowledge gained from multiple external connections creates complementarities between external connections and between internal R&D and external connections (Roper et al., 2008). Thus, having several different types of external connections increases the likelihood of innovation by directly increasing the flow of practical external knowledge and increasing the opportunities for effective complementarity between external and internal knowledge.

In general, enterprises tend to search for knowledge more in terms of breadth rather than depth (Chiang & Hung, 2010; Chen et al., 2011; Keupp & Gassmann, 2009), and search is mainly focused on local rather than long-distance search mainly on the use of related domain knowledge (Belderbos et al., 2010). Thus, external search breadth is closer to exploiting current knowledge or exploring related knowledge areas. In the collaborative technology activities of enterprises, the relationship between the enterprise and the external collaborator is deepened by the sharing of jointly owned patents (Belderbos et al., 2010). In some exploratory development projects, the project's success is facilitated by enhanced interaction with external collaborators and inter-firm knowledge-sharing mechanisms (Hsieh & Tidd, 2012). Once an enterprise has completed its external search and identified a partner, it will adopt an acquisition strategy (e.g. purchase) to deepen its collaboration with the target enterprise. Laursen & Salter (2006) argue that less search width and more search depth will affect their innovation performance. However, some scholars argue that search width positively affects breakthrough innovation performance but not incremental innovation performance, while some argue that search depth has no effect on breakthrough innovation performance but positively affects incremental innovation performance (Chiang & Hung, 2010).

As enterprises continue to search for knowledge, resulting in more connections to external knowledge sources, the need to establish appropriate contractual agreements for many formal connections and the time spent maintaining these connections makes the knowledge search costly (Love et al., 2014). At the same time, due to the limitations of the manager's attention span, the manager's knowledge of external knowledge sources is limited, so an initial increase in external connections will positively impact innovation gains. However, additional external connections will reduce innovation gains beyond a certain point. Laursen and Salter (2006), examining data from 2700 manufacturing enterprises in the UK, find that the breadth of information

sources enhances innovation. However, search expansion hurts innovation beyond certain limits; the same result is found in Finnish manufacturing (Leiponen & Helfat, 2010).

Because of their small size, SMEs need to join external corporate networks through strategic alliances when innovating, and they need to form personal networks by linking up with external sources of innovation through entrepreneurs' personal social relationships. In addition, SMEs must frequently participate in more informal knowledge networks (Büchel & Raub, 2002). These networks are often regional and aim to share knowledge and facilitate linkages between different groups such as start-ups, incubators, venture capitalists, technologists, etc. (Collinson & Gregson, 2003). SMEs' limited financial, human resource and technological power forces enterprises to look for external sources of knowledge and build their knowledge networks to access external knowledge.

International IT enterprises derive patents not only from internal R&D but also from outside-in open innovation models. These enterprises obtain patents mainly from internal R&D, university-enterprise partnerships and purchases, contributing to sales, profits and market value creation. Acquiring ideas, technology and human resources from external sources for internal R&D is the most effective way for enterprises to develop outside-in open innovation models. Purchasing patents can contribute to short-term growth, and university-enterprise partnerships are necessary for medium- to long-term growth (Lee et al., 2015).

To sum up, technology-based SMEs need to adopt an outside-in open innovation model to obtain knowledge resources from the outside world for innovation and establish links with more external knowledge sources. The current development status of technology-based SMEs in China shows that

the proportion of technology imported from outside is low, the number of collaborative R&D targets is low, and the number of connections with external knowledge sources is far from the inflexion point that reduces innovation performance. There is a need to expand the number of external knowledge sources continuously. At the same time, technology-based SMEs select more external knowledge sources by expanding the breadth of knowledge search, identifying cooperation partners and adopting knowledge acquisition strategies to establish deep cooperation with them. Adopting the outside-in open innovation model by technology-based SMEs helps improve enterprises' innovation performance, regardless of whether the external knowledge is acquired through the breadth or depth of knowledge search. Therefore, based on the above literature on outside-in open innovation and innovation performance, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1a: Adopting an outside-in open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs.

3.1.2 Inside-out Open Innovation Model – Innovation Performance

The main objective of adopting an Inside-out open innovation model is to transfer unused and underused ideas and assets from the enterprise to outside the enterprise, pursuing external commercialisation of technological knowledge (Chesbrough & Crowther, 2006). The open innovation model includes multiple internal and external sources of technology and multiple internal and external channels of technology commercialisation (West & Gallagher, 2006), so technology commercialisation will be an essential part of the implementation process of the Inside-out open innovation model. With the globalisation of the economy, technology commercialisation has become an essential competitive strategy for enterprises to adapt to the highly competitive environment (Chen et al., 2011). Technology commercialisation enables technology to add value at every step of the business process (Cooper & Kleinschmidt, 1990); therefore, innovation is worthless if it is not commercialised.

When adopting an inside-out open innovation model, enterprises must strategically decide to 'hold or sell' (Dittrich & Duysters, 2007). Although inside-out open innovation is not a major strategic decision for most companies, its importance is beginning to be seen in large companies such as IBM (Chesbrough, 2006). However, the main risk associated with this model is that the technology transferred may weaken the enterprise's competitive position (Arora et al., 2001), so many enterprises are reluctant to transfer technology for fear of strengthening the competitiveness of their competitors through the sale of their key technologies (Rivette & Kline, 2000). As a result, industrial enterprises are more focused on product sales than technology transfer (Davis & Harrison, 2001), in contrast to the success of some start-up companies (Rivette & Kline, 2000). Different innovation strategies must be developed under different environmental conditions regarding the potential adverse effects of transferring competitively relevant technologies. Thus, the inside-out open innovation model reflects the degree of restriction on technology transfer to enterprises, i.e. the degree of external technology commercialisation (Rivette & Kline, 2000).

Enterprises can reap additional economic and strategic benefits by adopting an inside-out open innovation model to commercialise the technology. Regarding economic gains, some start-ups, such as Texas-based securities agencies, generate hundreds of millions of dollars in licensing revenue each year (Rivette & Kline, 2000). Inside-out open innovation allows enterprises to commercialise unused or inconsistent technologies with their existing business model outside the enterprise or to co-develop them with external partners, contributing to their innovation performance (Anokhin et al., 2011). Regarding strategic gains, enterprises can develop their technologies into industry standards or gain access to external technologies (Grindley & Teece, 1997; Gassmann & Reepmeyer, 2005). When enterprises lack the practical resources or market knowledge to undertake technological innovation activities internally, enterprises that adopt inside-out open innovation can

benefit from external collaborators using the technology (Chiaroni et al., 2011; Chesbrough & Garman, 2009). Therefore, adopting an inside-out open innovation model is often a requirement rather than an option for enterprises (Rivette & Kline, 2000).

Although the economic and strategic benefits of adopting an inside-out open innovation model do not necessarily compensate for the adverse effects of over-selling technology that leads to a weakened competitive position (Fosfuri, 2006), the diffusion of technology and the export of industry standards can lead to an increase in corporate reputation (Rigby & Zook, 2002). Through an inside-out open innovation model, enterprises can explore new market segments and gain access to multiple resources, thereby gaining a competitive advantage (Lichtenthaler, 2009), while industry leadership and competitive advantage can help enterprises create long-term sustainable innovation performance. In the current development of technology-based SMEs in China, the sale and transfer of technology has not yet become an excessive behaviour of enterprises and has become an inevitable requirement for the commercialisation of technology to offset the costs of R&D, thus bringing economic and strategic benefits to the enterprise. Therefore, based on the above literature on inside-out open innovation and innovation performance, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1b: Adopting an inside-out open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs.

3.1.3 Coupled Open Innovation Model – Innovation Performance

The technological innovation process is divided into R&D and commercialisation processes, and the openness of innovation includes the openness of the R&D and commercialisation processes. Adopting an outside-in open innovation model can lead companies to search for innovation knowledge externally, and the knowledge search increases the openness of

innovation. Once an enterprise has searched for the required innovation knowledge, it will adopt an acquisition strategy to achieve deeper cooperation with the innovation source. Therefore, the outside-in open innovation model primarily influences the degree of openness of an enterprise's R&D process. Adopting an inside-out open innovation model is to commercialise technology externally through technology trading, outsourcing, and transfer of intellectual property. However, not all enterprises are willing to transfer their technology externally, and different 'sell or keep' strategic decisions will affect the extent to which the technology is commercialised externally, i.e. how much of the enterprise's technology is sold externally. Thus, the inside-out open innovation model will affect the openness of the enterprise's commercialisation process.

Establishing a wide range of links with external sources of innovative knowledge in the R&D process will increase the possibility of acquiring helpful knowledge complementary to the company's internal knowledge to a greater extent. As the number of links with external sources of innovative knowledge increases, it will distract managers' attention and the emergence of cognitive limits, reducing the efficiency of the enterprise in integrating external knowledge and thus negatively affecting the innovation performance of the enterprise. Collaboration with external organisations in commercialisation and technology transfer will help enterprises capture more of innovation's economic and strategic benefits. However, excessive sales of technology may lead to a loss of competitive advantage and harm the enterprise's innovation performance. Given the reality of innovation in China's technology-based SMEs, the proportion of R&D conducted in collaboration with external parties is low, and the proportion of technology transfer is also low, and the overall innovation openness is not high; therefore, outside-in and inside-out open innovation models primarily have a positive impact on innovation performance.

The adoption of a coupled open innovation paradigm may, in principle, require a combination of outside-in and inside-out open innovation mechanisms in

order to carry out R&D and commercialisation activities with external partners (Bogers, 2011), thus affecting the degree of openness of the R&D and commercialisation process and consequently innovation performance. The inflow and outflow of knowledge in the open innovation paradigm are complementary, with enterprises making purchases and sales of knowledge, enabling them to increase their innovation outcomes. At the same time, for some enterprise-related costs, such as cognitive, transaction and organisational costs, enterprises can reduce these costs by combining knowledge inflows and outflows through a coupled open innovation paradigm. Through empirical testing, enterprises that simultaneously purchase and sell knowledge increase their sales revenue of new products (Cassiman & Valentini, 2016). Therefore, based on the above literature on coupled open innovation and innovation performance, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H1c: Adopting a coupled open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs.

3.2 The Impact of Open Innovation Models on Absorptive Capability

3.2.1 Outside-in Open Innovation Model – Absorptive Capability

In the process of outside-in open innovation, on the one hand, enterprises establish open innovation networks with various external innovation organisations to access external creative information, knowledge and technology, which bring beneficial supplements to the internal R&D innovation of enterprises. Aitamurto (2013) takes Procter & Gamble as the subject of his study, concluding that more than one-third of the enterprise's new products come from external sources, and outside-in open innovation can increase R&D efficiency by 60%. On the other hand, through outside-in open innovation, enterprises can learn, understand and capture the needs and changes of customers and markets promptly, enhance the scientific and rational selection of innovation paths and resource allocation, and thus reduce costs and risks. Zhao & Zhang (2016) argue that it is essential for enterprises

to establish the concept of outside-in open innovation and to continuously improve their ability to utilise and absorb external technology and knowledge as a way to obtain a higher level of innovation performance. Gao & Zhang (2017) and Yao (2017) all argue that through outside-in open innovation, enterprises can fully capture the changes in external domestic and international market demand, thus improving their innovation science and innovation performance.

In addition, the complex external environment is also influential in open innovation activities and can make a slight difference in innovation performance. Mi & Lin (2015) argue that more and more enterprises are aware of the role of outside-in open innovation and that enterprises choose to proactively consider collaborative organisations when seeking external knowledge resources to capture innovation and development in a long evolutionary process. Similarly, Li & Guo (2016) argue that enterprises should fully consider the changing nature of their environment when developing their outside-in open innovation strategies. Therefore, based on the above literature on outside-in open innovation and absorptive capability, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2a: Adopting an outside-in open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs.

3.2.2 Inside-out Open Innovation Model – Absorptive Capability

Chesbrough argues that when enterprises engage in inside-out open innovation, they can expand their business channels through internal knowledge transfer, cooperation with external organisations and co-business, and continuously export resources outside the organisation to develop new markets. Peng (2015) argues that when enterprises practise inside-out open innovation, they can expand their markets, which in turn enhances the ability to transform innovation results and improves innovation efficiency. Similarly,

Chen et al. (2016) argue that inside-out open innovation can bring development resources to the enterprise and enhance its capabilities. Gu et al. (2017) argue that enterprises can make merit-based choices when engaging in inside-out open innovation and acquire exclusive rights to specific knowledge resources, thus helping them occupy an advantageous position in the fierce market competition and gain development sources. In summary, inside-out open innovation can help enterprises export valuable internal information, knowledge technology, etc., to the external market by transferring intellectual property rights, secondary research and development and disseminating innovative ideas. Therefore, based on the above literature on inside-out open innovation and absorptive capability, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2b: Adopting an inside-out open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs.

3.2.3 Coupled Open Innovation Model – Absorptive Capability

Coupled open innovation requires the purposeful management of a two-way flow of knowledge across organisational boundaries to collaborate in developing and commercialising the innovation (Borgers, 2011).

Chesbroughers (2014) similarly argues that coupled open innovation is a form of combined outside-in and inside-out open innovation, where there is an inflow and outflow of knowledge between participants in the innovation process, collaborating on developing and commercialising the innovation. Regarding coupled open innovation, enterprises need to implement specific mechanisms involving complementary partners, usually including strategic alliances, joint ventures, joint R&D, networks, ecosystems, platforms, etc. From the perspective of knowledge management theory, coupled open innovation requires complementary partners, with more emphasis on the matching and complementarity of knowledge between the collaborating parties. Enterprises systematically develop and exploit internal and external knowledge through the innovation process. Numerous studies have shown

that the effectiveness of open innovation depends on the ability to acquire and share knowledge. In the case of outside-in open innovation, the efficiency of the enterprise in conducting innovation activities depends more on the ability to share knowledge. Correspondingly, for inside-out open innovation, the efficiency of the enterprise's innovation activities depends more on the ability to acquire knowledge (Colin et al., 2016). For coupled open innovation, on the other hand, knowledge sharing facilitates mutual learning across organisations, stimulating existing knowledge stocks and new knowledge thinking. In practice, enterprises such as P&G and InnoCentive have demonstrated that intellectual property licensing can be used to collaborate on R&D with external business partners to achieve technological innovation. Therefore, based on the above literature on coupled open innovation and absorptive capability, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H2c: Adopting a coupled open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs.

3.3 The Impact of Absorptive Capability on Innovation Performance

Lane (2006) argues that enterprises find it difficult to fully integrate the new external knowledge they want to acquire and use when it is logically structured differently from the relevant knowledge and technology they have internally. For this reason, enterprises must adopt a change process to integrate these two types of knowledge effectively. Enterprises in the knowledge economy need to transform the wealth of external R&D knowledge into their competitive advantage, and the efficiency with which they can absorb and transform external knowledge and apply new knowledge is closely related to their absorptive capability endowment. An enterprise with a high level of absorptive capability will generally achieve higher economic returns during its production and operation. Absorptive capability determines whether an enterprise can effectively apply this new knowledge to cultivate a competitive advantage, promoting enterprise performance and enabling the

enterprise to gain a first-mover advantage. Wu et al. (2008) argue that R&D pursues creation and innovation, and based on the context of open innovation, external R&D knowledge acquisition is considered an essential creation and innovation management task. A higher level of absorptive capability can help enterprises break the confinement of limited internal resources, observe the industry's technological development from the acquired external knowledge, and gain timely insight into cutting-edge science and technology. A high level of absorptive capability enables enterprises to efficiently search, analyse and acquire valuable knowledge from the external environment, to quickly respond to changes in the external environment, to predict the direction of market changes and to identify development opportunities accurately, thus enabling them to capture market development opportunities and improve enterprise performance. The absorptive capability enables enterprises to avoid "path lock" in innovation, enhance the production capacity of heterogeneous products, and exploit comparative advantages. Acquiring external R&D knowledge strengthens the linkage between knowledge elements, which provides enterprises with a wealth of heterogeneous knowledge for innovation (Rothaermel & Alexandre, 2009; Yu, 2013; Fan & Li, 2019). Feng & Chen (2015) argue that organisational access to obtained external knowledge resources is positively correlated with the enterprise's absorptive capability, enabling sharper utilisation of new knowledge, new ideas and new business opportunities in resource-limited and context-specific situations, thus enhancing the enterprise's intrinsic creativity and viability. Fan et al. (2015) argue that for SMEs engaging in open innovation, especially start-up small enterprises, the only way to overcome the drawbacks of limited internal knowledge resources and capabilities is to strengthen their absorptive capability continuously. Guo (2016), in his study, argues that if enterprises want to maximise the value of knowledge and further develop new products and services, the only way to lay the foundation for this is by continuously enhancing their absorptive capability. Therefore, based on the above literature on absorptive capability and innovation performance, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3: The absorptive capability positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs.

3.4 The Mediating Role of Absorptive Capability in the Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

The outside-in open innovation helps enterprises to continuously access and utilise the resources in the open innovation network. With improved absorptive capability, enterprises can continuously adapt to and strengthen their ability to digest the external environment and transform more of the external knowledge, technology and other innovation resources into the enterprise's innovative performance. The inside-out open innovation helps enterprises to integrate internal knowledge and transfer it to the outside for application and commercialisation. By increasing absorptive capability, enterprises can more effectively access and utilise corporate information from the external environment, further shaping innovation performance. Coupled open innovation, on the other hand, encompasses the characteristics of both outside-in and inside-out open innovation.

Zahra & George (2002) suggest that potential absorptive capability is positively related to an enterprise's resource allocation flexibility. The stronger the potential absorptive capability, the stronger the enterprise's ability to connect to the external environment and improve its internal R&D team, and thus, the more flexible it can be in using internal and external resources. Spithoven et al. (2011) found that enterprises can enhance their potential absorptive capability through collective central learning in an intermediary platform such as an industry association, which helps them to acquire more external knowledge. When enterprises have higher levels of potential absorptive capability, they can explore and transform learning about information, knowledge, technology and opportunities more effectively,

stimulating innovative outcomes and increasing business value. Wang et al. (2016) argue that enterprises that want to use existing knowledge to identify, digest, and integrate new knowledge must improve their processing power in the resource acquisition process, and with increased processing power comes improved absorptive capability. Maintaining a positive communication and interaction pattern with each external channel helps enterprises to accurately understand the heterogeneous knowledge from external sources, thus helping to maximise the value of knowledge. Focusing on the automotive industry, Li et al. (2018) argue that in the process of open innovation practices, enterprises will increase their interactions with external resources, and such interactions can both increase their internal knowledge and resources and further strengthen their absorptive capability, which in turn can effectively improve innovation performance. Therefore, based on the above literature, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H4a: Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between outside-in open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H4b: Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between inside-out open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H4c: Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between coupled open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

3.5 The Impact of Open Innovation Models on Dynamic Capabilities

Implementing an open innovation model has a catalytic effect on the construction of dynamic capabilities in enterprises. Dynamic capabilities evolve with knowledge (Nielsen, 2006), and knowledge innovation can facilitate the construction and development of dynamic capabilities, which in turn must have a continuous drive for renewal, including organisational innovation (He et al., 2006). Based on a technological innovation perspective, Teece argues that the dynamic capabilities framework targets the environment

not as an industry but as a business system comprising organisations and individuals such as customers, suppliers, government agencies, etc., which is consistent with the breadth of open innovation (Teece, 2007). It needs to be context-dependent for dynamic capabilities, and it is the context of the environment that open innovation emphasises (Chesbrough, 2007). Open innovation is a dynamic process that requires different dynamic capabilities at each stage, and the dynamics of the open innovation process lead to the evolution of dynamic capabilities in enterprises (Ma, 2014). Eisenhardt and Martin (2000) argue that mergers and acquisitions, alliances and product innovation are all activities that firms undertake to renew and reallocate resources. They argue that product development is an enterprise's dynamic capability because it can change the firm's resource allocation and that product development is a mechanism for firms to create, integrate, reorganise, and decentralise resources. Open innovation means enterprises have decentralised innovation agents, which can help them overcome organisational inertia by developing different technological levels, thus facilitating the construction of dynamic organisational capabilities (Ma & Song, 2014). This means that open innovation, especially product innovation, positively impacts the construction of dynamic capabilities.

In a rapidly changing environment, innovation significantly impacts the construction and development of dynamic capabilities (Lawson & Samson, 2001). Research has found that sustained product and market innovation can improve dynamic capabilities and give enterprises a competitive advantage (Danneels, 2002). Some enterprises will use continuous product and market innovation to gain a competitive advantage, others will pursue additional benefits by adopting managerial innovation, and others will sense change faster to gain first-mover benefits (Jiao et al., 2013). Open innovation models are implemented to enable enterprises to innovate more effectively. The modern evolutionary view of innovation is that it is an organisational behaviour of enterprises that creates internal variation to compensate for the risks associated with the external variation and is an internal driver of dynamic

capability formation. Therefore, the adoption of open innovation models by enterprises has a significant impact on the development of dynamic capabilities.

3.5.1 Outside-in Open Innovation Model – Dynamic Capabilities

External Knowledge Acquisition

External acquisition of technology is essential to an enterprise's adoption of an open innovation model for acquiring external knowledge (Dahlander & Gann, 2010; Rubera et al., 2016). Acquiring technology from outside the enterprise speeds up the acquisition of new technologies and reduces operational costs and technological innovation risks, as in the case of Procter & Gamble (Rubera et al., 2016). Once an enterprise has acquired external technologies, it needs to integrate them into its activities, so it must develop an integration mechanism to enable the shared exchange of technologies (West & Bogers, 2014). In particular, some external technologies will be less similar to those within the enterprise, and integration will be more difficult (Dahlander & Gann, 2010). In order to benefit from external technologies, enterprises must develop more complex and costly integration mechanisms, even if they need to draw on prior knowledge and capabilities to identify, access, absorb and implement this technological knowledge (Chen et al., 2011; Hung & Chou, 2013) into something that the organisation can understand (Todorova & Durisin, 2007).

The technological innovation process is a combinatorial search and problem-solving activity related to the "creation and reorganisation of technological ideas" (Katila & Ahuja, 2002). Technological innovation is uncertain, leading to learning traps and over-reliance on familiar, proven and close solutions (Ahuja & Lampert, 2001). External knowledge allows enterprises to inject the necessary diversity combined with internal knowledge to stimulate the innovation engine (Mihalache et al., 2012). External sources of technology

influence entrepreneurial innovation through the complementarity of internal and external knowledge, where internal technological capabilities determine the effectiveness of technology investments and complement internal capabilities through external networks, thus creating synergies (Voudouris et al., 2012).

Acquiring external technologies through contracts, alliances, joint ventures or informal models can reduce technology risk, improve R&D capabilities and increase the likelihood of R&D success (Giarratana & Mariani, 2014; Oxley & Sampson, 2004). First, enterprises that acquire and integrate external technologies will likely try new alternatives and adopt multiple problem-solving approaches. External technologies increase the number and diversity of knowledge elements in a technology portfolio, creating potentially new technology combinations (Fleming, 2001). This may reduce learning traps and make technology exploration possible (Ahuja & Lampert, 2001; Katila & Ahuja, 2002). Secondly, external R&D can increase the pool of problem-solvers available to enterprises and help solve problems that require combining knowledge from multiple fields (Boudreau et al., 2011). Thus, the acquisition of new technologies from outside is a primary characteristic of an enterprise's R&D capability, which is dynamic capabilities (Danneels, 2008).

Therefore, acquiring external technologies will bring new technologies and technological solutions to the enterprise's R&D, complementing internal and external knowledge, thus generating new technological combinations and enhancing the enterprise's R&D capabilities.

External Knowledge Sourcing

The exploratory orientation of cross-border sourcing is at the heart of an enterprise's adaptive capabilities, as it generates the necessary internal changes that allow the enterprise to adapt to the market, technological and

competitive changes through innovation (Sidhu et al., 2007). Cross-border search is consequently the engine of dynamic capabilities, a management and organisational process that consolidates and enables the successful deployment of dynamic capabilities (Ambrosini & Bowman, 2009). Non-local search can bring new and differentiated knowledge elements to the enterprise, update the existing knowledge base on time, and enhance the dynamic capabilities of the enterprise to adapt to changes in the environment (Zhao et al., 2014). The external knowledge source strategy of an enterprise can improve the exploratory innovation performance of an enterprise through the mediation of dynamic capabilities (Jin & Chen, 2015). Therefore, cross-border knowledge search significantly impacts dynamic capabilities (Liu & Meng, 2016).

External search for knowledge is the ability of organisations to penetrate organisational boundaries to acquire new ideas and knowledge from outside (von Hippel, 2010). External search allows for diversification by identifying and acquiring new external knowledge and ideas that can be combined with an organisation's internal knowledge base, leading to solutions to current problems and new business opportunities (Laursen, 2012; Voudouris et al., 2012). Enterprises can access various external knowledge sources through external search, providing them with complementary knowledge. Broader and more diverse searches, which enable access to more comprehensive knowledge sources, provide opportunities to develop new organisational capabilities and successful innovations (Leiponen & Helfat, 2010; Vega-Jurado et al., 2009). Different external sources of knowledge require different management approaches and organisational practices to make the search effective (Laursen & Salter, 2006). Therefore, the more diverse the external knowledge sources, the more different management skills are needed to match them (Faems et al., 2010).

Search breadth and depth extend the concepts of exploratory and developmental learning (March, 1991), with search depth being aligned with the developmental learning concept of how enterprises reuse existing knowledge and search breadth being how enterprises explore new knowledge more broadly, closer to exploratory learning (Katila & Ahuja, 2002). In absorptive capability theory, external knowledge search allows enterprises to identify and acquire new and valuable knowledge from a broader range of external sources and gradually change their existing knowledge base through absorption and application (Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). However, there is a domain distance between new knowledge and existing knowledge that is difficult to understand and accept. When enterprises collaborate deeply with external organisations, they can more easily understand and derive value from this distant knowledge, which cannot be obtained through simple searches (Hsieh & Tidd, 2012).

In summary, the main task of implementing the outside-in open innovation model is sourcing and acquiring external knowledge. Sourcing and acquiring external knowledge can help enterprises obtain complementary knowledge resources, promote the effective integration of internal and external knowledge, update the enterprise's knowledge base on time, and form or update the dynamic capabilities of enterprises to adapt to the environment. Therefore, based on the above literature on outside-in open innovation model and dynamic capabilities, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5a: Adopting an outside-in open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs.

3.5.2 Inside-out Open Innovation Model – Dynamic Capabilities

Internal Knowledge Sale

In the inside-out open innovation model, inside-out technological activities stimulate enterprises to open their organisational boundaries to the

technological products of other enterprises, which helps to enhance their perception and sensitivity to external knowledge and thus stimulate their technological inspiration (Lichtenthaler, 2009). Furthermore, selling intangible assets such as intellectual property and know-how can facilitate reorganising and utilising internal knowledge (Mol & Birkinshaw, 2009). Meanwhile, in exporting knowledge externally, enterprises can observe environmental changes, explore market opportunities, identify changes in customer demand, and adjust their resource allocation or organisational structure to enhance knowledge reconfiguration (Yao et al., 2017).

Technology outsourcing remains a challenge for most enterprises in the process of inside-out open innovation. A European survey of innovators showed a 40% difference between the decision to outsource and the actual deal (Gambardella et al., 2007) and the high complexity of outsourcing. No technology outsourcing enterprise is aware of all technology opportunities, let alone processing all the information about new technology opportunities. Even when a technology licensing enterprise is aware of a technology opportunity, it faces a great deal of uncertainty about the value and applicability of the technology (Arora & Gambardella, 2010; Jensen & Thursby, 2001; Kani & Motohashi, 2012).

In technology licensing transactions, the selection of potential licensees can be complicated by limited information (Jensen & Roy, 2008). There is a general information asymmetry in the technology market, with licensees lacking knowledge of the details of the technology and licensors lacking knowledge of the market potential of the technology. In inside-out open innovation, desorption capabilities are used as a dynamic capability to create, extend and modify the firm's resource base (Helfat & Peteraf, 2015). The mainstream view is that those dynamic capabilities can be classified as sensing, capturing and resetting (Teece, 2007). Identifying new opportunities for technology out-licensing is associated with perception capabilities during

technology out-licensing transactions. Identifying market opportunities in technology out-licensing requires enterprises to have strong opportunity perception capabilities and to capture the opportunity and reset the enterprise process to transform the technology out-licensing business opportunity into a real deal (Hu et al., 2015). Desorption capabilities can be built up through exploratory and exploitative learning, with exploratory learning overcoming cognitive barriers about technology and product domains and helping enterprises broaden their horizons of technology commercialisation opportunities (Eggers & Kaplan, 2009). Start-ups can build desorption capabilities through technology alliances and learning from their technology tracks (Bianchi et al., 2011).

The sale of internal knowledge is primarily about outsourcing the enterprise's technology, sensing changes in the technology market environment, understanding changes in customer needs and identifying business opportunities. In order to identify business opportunities, enterprises must be able to perceive them and seize them, reallocate their resources and turn them into real deals. Implementing a sales strategy helps enterprises explore, learn, and thus build their desorption capabilities, enabling them to identify and seize more business opportunities and realise technology deals.

Internal Knowledge Disclosure

Openness emphasises reducing or eliminating access restrictions, including relinquishing control over an enterprise's resources, such as intellectual property rights, which means that other enterprises can access one or more parts of the enterprise's resources. Such openness is more common in the case of knowledge and information products and intangible resources, as they can be easily relocated by enterprises seeking competitive advantage (Miller & Shamsie, 1996). Of course, this openness has also been observed in other industries, such as blast furnaces, furniture and construction (Dodgson et al., 2007; Fuller, 2010). Common to all forms of open strategy is relinquishing at

least some control over an enterprise's current or future asset base (Boudreau, 2010). Openness implies the purposeful reduction or even elimination of the inimitability of an enterprise's resources, which seems to lead to a dissipation of the enterprise's competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). However, enterprises can still maintain an advantage by controlling the further exploitation of open resources (West & O'Mahony, 2008), i.e. by reconfiguring the enterprise's open resources.

Free disclosure means enterprises give up the proprietary nature of their product or process know-how and the protection of their intellectual property rights, releasing these intellectual assets to the outside environment. Free disclosure of product and process designs is a defining characteristic of the open innovation model. Free disclosure is a collaborative product design feature that allows everyone to participate, which is prevalent in open-source software projects (Alexy et al., 2013). However, empirical studies have shown that free disclosure of product and service design extends well beyond software projects, such as IBM's disclosure to outsiders of a semiconductor manufacturing process it invented. In practice, most innovators find it difficult to protect their innovations from direct or close imitation, and innovators are faced with deciding whether to voluntarily disclose or protect their innovations (Harhoff et al., 2003). If technology spillovers enable the recipient to obtain the technology for free, technology protection is no longer relevant and voluntary free disclosure is the best practice.

Increases in computing and communication technology capabilities tend to reduce the ability of innovators to control the knowledge they create, and the most practical knowledge management strategies and practices will be biased towards knowledge sharing (Calvert, 2004). Free disclosure of new product designs and their performance can significantly increase the collective learning rate, leading to faster development of better designs (Nuvolari, 2004) and allowing innovators to perceive business opportunities within the

innovation community (Baldwin & Clark, 2006). Free disclosure of innovations can increase the reach and speed of innovation diffusion, gaining a network effect in the process. Suppose an innovation that is freely disclosed and adopted by others rapidly becomes the 'dominant design' of a product or even an 'open standard'. In that case, it may provide a commercial opportunity for innovators to pre-empt the development or commercialisation of other versions of the innovation (Allen, 1983). By disclosing information about an innovative product or process for free, the innovator enables the manufacturer to learn about the innovation. The manufacturer can then build on this and offer the product at a price below the innovator's internal production costs (Kotha, 1995).

Thus, disclosing internal knowledge opens up an enterprise's product and process innovations to all outside organisations and individuals, creating collective learning within the innovation community, accelerating learning, allowing product and process performance to evolve faster and enabling the enterprise to identify business opportunities. When the disclosed technology has become the dominant design or open standard for a product, the enterprise can pre-empt the development of other versions of the new technology and maintain control over further development by reallocating available technology resources, thereby gaining competitive advantages.

In summary, the sale or free disclosure of internal knowledge creates the opportunity for enterprises to be exposed to changes in the external market environment, enabling them to be one step ahead of the market opportunity so that they can reset their resources and use that opportunity to develop new products or technologies and achieve innovative performance. Therefore, based on the above literature on inside-out open innovation model and dynamic capabilities, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5b: Adopting an inside-out open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs.

3.5.3 Coupled Open Innovation Model – Dynamic Capabilities

The adoption of open innovation models by enterprises can help entrepreneurs perceive changes in the external environment, grasp business opportunities, bring in external resources, reorganise with internal resources, and develop dynamic capabilities to adapt to changes in the external environment so that they can produce new products or technologies that meet market needs and improve innovation performance. However, the impact of different open innovation models on dynamic capabilities varies. Acquiring and sourcing for external knowledge is primarily used in the outside-in open innovation model to help enterprises obtain external knowledge and technology, increase the diversity of internal knowledge, enhance the possibility of generating new combinations of technologies, and help improve the R&D capability of enterprises. In contrast, the sale and disclosure of internal knowledge are mainly used in the inside-out open innovation model to help enterprises discover and identify business opportunities for technology trading and enhance their ability to commercialise technology externally. Theoretically, depending on the context, implementing outside-in and inside-out open innovation can be crossed and combined to form a coupled open innovation model with different impacts on dynamic capabilities (Gassmann & Enkel, 2004). Therefore, based on the above literature on coupled open innovation model and dynamic capabilities, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H5c: Adopting a coupled open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs.

3.6 The Impact of Dynamic Capabilities on Innovation Performance

The openness of an enterprise's dynamic capabilities enables it to continuously absorb information from its environment, create and develop

new knowledge, and thus make itself flexible in a rapidly changing market (Zahra & George, 2002). The openness of dynamic capabilities allows enterprises to actively absorb external knowledge and disseminate, replicate and internalise it within the enterprise so internal resources and the external environment can interact positively. Because dynamic capabilities enable the interaction between internal resources and the external environment, they potentially impact an enterprise's competitive advantage, which is a critical finding in dynamic capabilities theory (Teece et al., 1997). An enterprise has a competitive advantage when it is more successful in its industry than its current or potential competitors (Peteraf & Barney, 2003). A concept consistent with a competitive advantage in enterprise performance and superior enterprise innovation performance relative to competitors is often an empirical indicator of competitive advantage (Schilke, 2014).

Dynamic capabilities are the ability of an enterprise to integrate, build and reorganise its resources and internal and external competencies to meet the requirements of a changing environment (Teece, 2007), emphasising the ability to perceive and capture opportunities and reallocate resources. Wu (2015) subdivided dynamic capabilities into opportunity recognition and opportunity exploitation capabilities based on the integration capability perspective from the perspective of the internal strategic characteristics of the enterprise and empirically tested the impact of dynamic capabilities on innovation performance and the moderating effect of strategic orientation. The study found that opportunity recognition capability and opportunity exploitation capability can enhance the innovation performance of enterprises. Du & Xiong et al. (2017) found empirically that both the opportunity perception ability and resource reconfiguration ability dimensions of dynamic capabilities of SMEs have a significant positive effect on innovation performance. Yang et al. (2018) proposed that the dynamic capabilities of enterprises mediated the impact of customer engagement on the technological innovation performance of enterprises and tested that perceived capability and resource reconfiguration capability had a significant positive effect on innovation performance.

Thus, dynamic capabilities help enterprises to perceive market opportunities in the external environment and to exploit them through the reallocation of internal and external resources, thus improving their innovation performance. Therefore, based on the above literature on dynamic capabilities and innovation performance, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H6: The dynamic capabilities positively impact innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs.

3.7 The Mediating Role of Dynamic Capabilities in the Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

When an enterprise adopts an open innovation model, it needs to integrate internal and external knowledge processes to obtain innovation performance from it. In an open innovation model, an enterprise's knowledge processes can be divided into knowledge exploration, retention, and development. In the knowledge discovery process, enterprises decide whether to make or buy knowledge (Cassiman & Veugelers, 2006). In the knowledge retention process, enterprises decide whether to integrate knowledge into the internal or retain it in the external knowledge base by relying on inter-enterprise relationships (Integrate or Relate). In knowledge development, companies are also faced with deciding whether to keep or sell knowledge (Lichtenthaler, 2007). For the knowledge management process in an open innovation model, six knowledge capabilities are needed to support the process: knowledge invention, absorption, transformation, linking, innovation and desorption. These six knowledge capabilities can bring temporary innovation performance but not sustained innovation performance, which can only be achieved by adapting and reconfiguring them to the changing environment to form dynamic capabilities (Lichtenthaler & Lichtenthaler, 2009).

In order to adapt to a changing environment, an enterprise's knowledge capabilities need to be reconfigured through proactive management because adaptation is not only a state but also a process (Floyd & Lane, 2000; Miles & Snow, 1994). The reconfiguration of knowledge capabilities requires changes to the enterprise's existing knowledge base in response to changes in markets and technology (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). The enterprise can identify new knowledge and markets on the evolutionary path of its current knowledge base and market position, thus revealing gaps between market opportunities and its current position. It is consequently necessary for enterprises to recognise, behind the management of knowledge exploration, retention and development processes, that knowledge capabilities must be adaptive (Helfat et al., 2007) to sustain superior innovation performance. Thus, for knowledge capabilities to be adaptable to changes in the external environment, they need to be reorganised by higher-level corporate capabilities.

In summary, open innovation aims to integrate internal and external knowledge of the enterprise and accelerate the flow of innovative knowledge into and out of the enterprise. When knowledge flows into an enterprise from outside, it needs to be absorbed and reorganised through its knowledge exploration and retention capabilities and integrated into its original knowledge base to enhance the knowledge base for enterprise innovation. The outflow of knowledge from the enterprise requires the enterprise to release its knowledge through its knowledge exploitation capability to achieve the commercial application of knowledge. In order to realise the management process of knowledge exploration, retention and utilisation, enterprises need different knowledge capabilities to support them and to realise the internalisation of external knowledge and the externalisation of internal knowledge; they need the support of the six knowledge capabilities of enterprises. In order to adapt to the changes in the external environment of the enterprise, higher-order dynamic capabilities are required to reconfigure the existing knowledge capabilities to adapt to the changes in the environment

and continuously transform the internal and external knowledge of the enterprise into innovative performance.

3.7.1 Outside-in Open Innovation Model

Open innovation integrates an enterprise's pursuit of new product development goals and external inputs. Based on theoretical analysis of resources and capabilities, the realisation of outside-in open innovation is dependent on external resources, and the establishment of dependency links with external enterprises and institutions helps the enterprise to gain access to resources so that the enterprise's relational capabilities - i.e. its ability to establish and manage knowledge connections with other enterprises - can enhance the impact of the outside-in open innovation model on the enterprise's performance (Sisodiya et al., 2013). Once an enterprise has established links with external knowledge sources, the critical issue is how to translate the acquired external knowledge into its internal knowledge, in which absorptive capability plays an essential role.

In an outside-in open innovation model, the enterprise's ability to absorb external knowledge has become a primary driver of competitive advantage. In large, R&D-intensive enterprises, the implementation of open innovation is often linked to the ability to absorb knowledge, while small enterprises and enterprises in traditional industries often have no or low levels of absorptive capability. In an outside-in open innovation model, enterprises need to scan their surroundings for the knowledge and technology they need rather than relying solely on internal R&D.. Absorptive capability is a critical prerequisite for adopting an outside-in open innovation model (Spithoven et al., 2011). The use of social media in outside-in open innovation models increases transparent, moderate and multi-directional interaction with the outside of the enterprise, which in turn affects the four absorptive capacities of the enterprise, namely connectivity, social strategy, cross-functionality and receptivity (Ooms et al., 2015).

If SMEs are to implement outside-in open innovation successfully, they need to inject complementary external resources. When SMEs implement open external innovation, technological complementarity is the most critical factor influencing resource complementarity, with transformational capabilities mediating the relationship between resource complementarity and innovation performance (Huang et al., 2015). Many enterprises connect their internal R&D functions to external players to enhance innovation capabilities. Enterprises' activities in accessing external knowledge resources will affect their innovation allocation and performance, with technology scouting capabilities playing an essential antecedent role in their access to external knowledge resources (Wang et al., 2015). Thus, establishing an enterprise's ability to connect external knowledge sources improves the efficiency of the outside-in open innovation model in achieving superior performance, and the acquired external knowledge can only be transformed into enterprise innovation performance through knowledge absorption and transformation capabilities. Therefore, based on the above literature, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7a: Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between outside-in open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

3.7.2 Inside-out Open Innovation Model

While technology out-licensing activities provide essential economic and strategic benefits for many enterprises, enabling them to profit from technology out-licensing outside their traditional scope of business, most enterprises encounter management difficulties in implementing an aggressive out-licensing strategy (Lichtenthaler, 2011). Technology out-licensing is a technology development option that can generate corporate revenues without investing in downstream complementary assets, but the complexity of technology licensing out-licensing activities determines the ability of enterprises to derive monetary benefits from them (Bianchi et al., 2011).

Based on the potential benefits and risks of out-licensing, the adoption of an inside-out open innovation model may have a positive or negative impact on enterprise performance, which may depend on both internal factors (e.g. desorption) and external factors (e.g. appropriateness) (Lichtenthaler, 2015). An empirical analysis of pharmaceutical enterprises shows that the state of technological development, reputation and desorption have some influence on the number of external technology licenses. Over the past two decades, drug development costs for pharmaceutical enterprises have risen rapidly, but the number of approved new drug products has not increased, and these increased costs are mainly attributed to abandoned new drug development. A broader external licensing of intellectual property associated with abandoned new drug development could lead to the recovery and/or redeployment of new drugs to meet some unmet medical needs (Chesbrough & Chen, 2013). Learning from external alliances has a power-change effect as enterprises build their desorption capabilities (Hu et al., 2015). Thus, desorption capabilities are essential to the relationship between enterprises' inside-out open innovation models and innovation performance. Therefore, based on the above literature, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7b: Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between inside-out open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

3.7.3 Coupled Open Innovation Model

The coupled open innovation model is about co-creation with complementary partner enterprises through alliances, collaborations and joint ventures. This model is used by enterprises to combine outside-in and inside-out innovation processes and to develop and commercialise innovations with complementary partner enterprises jointly. Co-creation has been widely studied in the context of open innovation, for example, in open-source project development (Von Hippel & von Krogh, 2006). Co-creation focuses mainly on innovation through communities (Lakhani et al., 2008; Reichwald & Piller, 2009), consumers

(Hienerth, 2006; Lettl et al., 2006), leading users (Franke et al., 2006), universities or research institutions (Perkmann & Walsh, 2007), and partners from other industries (Enkel & Gassmann, 2009) for mass production. Enterprises that adopt this innovation model do so mainly to set product standards, increase revenues, and establish strategic alliances with complementary partner enterprises (Enkel & Gassmann, 2009). Once a strategic alliance has been established, combining heterogeneous knowledge from complementary organisations to achieve co-creation is critical to achieving innovation performance using a coupled open innovation model. However, due to their lack of absorptive capability or low absorptive capability, SMEs need to use innovation intermediaries to establish strategic alliances with external complementary enterprises to compensate for their lack of absorptive capability to achieve innovation performance (Spithoven et al., 2011). Thus, absorptive capability plays a crucial intermediate role in the relationship between the impact of coupled open innovation models on innovation performance. Therefore, based on the above literature, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H7c: Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between coupled open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

3.8 The Impact of Cognitive Inertia on Innovation Performance

Enterprises oriented towards learning new knowledge value breaking away from their original knowledge base and hope to search for new knowledge, skills and methods through external social networks to make up for the inadequacy of their existing knowledge resources and improve their innovation capabilities. The stronger the learning inertia, the more enterprises use the new knowledge learned and change their usual problem-solving mindset by transforming old ideas and innovating work methods to improve their innovation performance. Yang & Fei (2018) point out that with higher learning inertia, enterprises are more inclined to track and learn cutting-edge

knowledge in the existing knowledge structure and improve incremental innovation capabilities by learning and combining existing and new knowledge. More substantial learning inertia also enhances organisational adaptability and the ability to promptly respond to the rapidly changing external environment, facilitating timely and good innovation and change (Bakker & Knobon, 2015). The strengthening of learning inertia is conducive to breaking knowledge path dependency, helping enterprises to break the shackles of over-reliance on obsolete knowledge, continuously acquiring favourable advanced knowledge, and resolving the problem of information mismatch under the difference between internal and external knowledge scenarios through recombination with external differentiated knowledge, in order to better achieve technological paradigm shift and enterprise product innovation (Nerkar & Roberts, 2004; Xie et al., 2016). At the same time, knowledge complementation will also enable the potential value of the original knowledge to be exploited and improve the utility of knowledge through the leverage effect, which will lead to more innovations and achieve the purpose of knowledge-driven innovation.

Based on the knowledge base view, enterprises have learnt and accumulated a large number of successful experiences and high-quality knowledge in the process of innovation and creation in the past, which will be integrated and internalised into the existing knowledge system of enterprises and become the basis for enterprises to obtain competitive advantages and carry out innovation activities in the future (Zhou & Wu, 2010). At the same time, the enhancement of experience inertia will strengthen an enterprise's original knowledge advantage, which is conducive to the development of new technologies and products, and the continuous improvement and value-added optimisation and upgrading of existing R&D paths, which can effectively avoid the uncertain risks associated with the development of new technologies, thus contributing to the improvement of innovation performance (Yang et al., 2014). Xie et al. (2016) argue that path dependence on learning is a core component of enterprise innovation activities and that experience inertia can lead to

higher learning efficiency, relying on existing experience and knowledge, which can eliminate uncertainty and complexity in the innovation process, avoid multiple trials of different innovation routes, and effectively reduce innovation costs to increase the level of enterprise innovation output rapidly. The existence of experience inertia is closely related to the accumulation of corporate knowledge, and the path dependence brought about by experience inertia makes enterprises, when planning their future development, more inclined to choose innovation projects that are in line with their existing strengths and possess previously accumulated experience knowledge (Arend et al., 2014), in order to increase the success rate of innovation. Prior experiential knowledge is unique knowledge that has been used and filtered over time and is not easily copied by other enterprises. When an enterprise faces a new dilemma, it will either look for solutions in its specific existing knowledge base or use prior experiential knowledge as a guide to create targeted solutions using heuristic thinking (Islam & Zein, 2020), depending on the specific situation. This analogy-like heuristic thinking helps enterprises solve existing dilemmas, creatively leading to more innovative outcomes.

A procedural problem-solving process can save costs and time and achieve the purpose of risk avoidance, but at the same time, it can also cause a lack of creative thinking and limited innovative behaviour, which seriously affects the learning and growth of enterprises. The existence of procedural inertia will cause inertia in the flow of knowledge in enterprises, making it difficult for knowledge to flow within the enterprise, which is directly manifested by the fact that enterprises do not attach importance to the creation of new knowledge internally and the research and development of new technologies, and also resist acquiring, absorbing and using new knowledge from outside (Zhou & Chen, 2014), which is not conducive to the innovative development of enterprises. The stronger the procedural inertia, the more enterprises tend to use conservative and fixed organisational processes and will be obsessed with pursuing the stability of the enterprise, neglecting the combination and application of internal and external elements of the enterprise, and will not

make efforts to transform and update existing knowledge, which is not conducive to the generation of innovative behaviour in enterprises. Procedural inertia will cause path dependence to become locked, and enterprises will cling to their past modes of thinking and behaviour, immersing themselves in a set of processes and practices for a long time, which hinders the learning of new knowledge and new technologies. Over time, they will lose the awareness and ability to explore beyond their existing thinking patterns and technology trajectories, which will not be conducive to various R&D activities, thus reducing their innovation performance. The learning inertia brought about by procedural inertia makes enterprises comfortable with maintaining the status quo and reluctant to change easily, preferring to remain consistent with the past in the choice of products, markets, upstream and downstream partners and development strategies and not paying much attention to potential opportunities in other areas. This limits the possibility of innovation through the acquisition of cutting-edge external knowledge. When the external environment is in turbulence, these conventional and institutionalised structural processes lose their original value and become an opposing force that hinders change and innovation, resulting in the inability of the enterprise to make flexible and timely responses to changes in the external environment (Karim & Kaul, 2015), thus reducing the enterprise's innovation efficiency. Therefore, based on the above literature on cognitive inertia and innovation performance, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H8a: The learning inertia positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs

H8b: The experience inertia positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs

H8c: The procedural inertia negatively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs

3.9 The Moderating Role of Cognitive Inertia in the Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

Innovation is utilising known information to break through conventions and produce unique and valuable objects and ideas for enterprise growth and personal development. In a knowledge-based economy, the sustainable development of an enterprise depends on constantly updated knowledge and technology, and organisational innovation is the fundamental driving force that keeps the knowledge and technology of an enterprise up-to-date. Therefore, the open innovation model is essentially a form of organisational innovation.

3.9.1 Learning Inertia

The source and origin of organisational innovation are employees' innovative capability and innovative behaviour (Hou, 2012). The results of organisational innovation are the accumulation and extension of individual innovative behaviour (Amabile, 1988; Woodman et al., 1993; Shalley, 1995). When individual innovative behaviour reflects employees' creativity, i.e. when employees are innovative, it becomes the basis for organisational innovation capability. Deci et al. (1985) argue that team leaders can impact team members' ability to innovate and that leaders who support their members to innovate will contribute to their ability to innovate. Studies by Skyrme (2000) and many others have also shown that knowledge leadership significantly promotes individual skills and knowledge creation. Therefore, when an enterprise's executives implement knowledge leadership for researchers, the researchers will be more inclined to enhance the exchange of knowledge and experience among themselves, thus rapidly improving their innovation capabilities. In contrast, when executives implement knowledge leadership, there will be cognitive inertia, which hinders the flow of knowledge and inhibits the enhancement of researchers' innovation capabilities by rejecting new methods, ideas and thoughts (Yuan et al., 2005). Executives with high cognitive inertia tend to lack risk-taking and curiosity and not try to learn new ideas and solutions, relying on past routines and experiences (Liao, 2002). Therefore, although knowledge leadership is effective in enhancing individual innovation, executives with high cognitive inertia rely too much on past problem-solving methods and experience, and their cognitive inertia can,

therefore, have a deterrent effect on the enhancement of researchers' innovation capabilities, impacting on their innovative behaviour and, consequently, on the development of organisational innovation and its capabilities. Therefore, based on the above literature, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H9a: Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H9b: Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H9c: Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

3.9.2 Experience Inertia

The formation of experience inertia has defined a learning development path along which enterprises will consciously search for the knowledge they need to supplement their existing knowledge base. Searching for prior knowledge often saves time, reduces costs and leads to quick solutions to problems (Subramaniam & Youndt, 2005). Conversely, enterprises trying to break out of previously formed knowledge path dependencies are bound to be time-consuming and costly, incurring greater opportunity and sunk costs, bearing greater market risk, and challenging to ensure profit growth (Murmann, 2013). Cognitive theory suggests that when analysing and predicting new problems and situations, enterprises are more likely to base their search for new knowledge on what they already know. Therefore, only new knowledge that is local and similar to the existing knowledge will be searched for instead of searching for new sources of knowledge and choosing to search for new knowledge that is more different from the existing knowledge resources of the

enterprise (Argote & Mironspektor, 2011). The existence of experience inertia makes enterprises rely more on the current development track. It will search for domain-specific knowledge related to current advantageous experience and knowledge as much as possible in the process of organisational learning and improve the utility of knowledge by integrating, refining and optimising it to consolidate further and expand existing advantages while also further strengthening experience inertia (Zhou & Chen, 2011), forming a dynamic, positive feedback causal loop. Therefore, based on the above literature, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H9d: Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H9e: Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H9f: Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

3.9.3 Procedural Inertia

Procedural inertia can obstruct this process when an enterprise searches for new external knowledge. Firstly, enterprises believe that the current procedurally structured processes are the best application of their prior experiential knowledge in their production and business activities, are trusted and familiar to all employees consistently, and ensure the smooth running of the enterprise. It also saves time and effort, brings efficiency and avoids the risks that change can bring. Therefore, the stronger the procedural inertia, the less an enterprise sees the need to spend time and effort acquiring new knowledge and changing existing conditions. Secondly, heterogeneous knowledge acquired by enterprises through external knowledge search is

often difficult to fit into the existing procedural practices of enterprises and needs to be filtered, filtered and integrated before it can be internalised into enterprise knowledge (Tsai, 2001; Mehrabani & Shajari; Piezunka & Dahlander, 2015). When enterprises integrate internal and external knowledge, the procedural inertia within the organisation can have a disruptive hindering effect, thus negatively affecting the knowledge search process (Obeso & Sarabia, 2018). Finally, the existence of procedural inertia can restrict the interflow of internal knowledge resources and the updating and optimisation of the knowledge base, making enterprises less enthusiastic about exploring and assimilating new knowledge (Lu et al., 2015) while forming a solid procedural dependency, which can inhibit the knowledge search activities of enterprises and easily lead to the rejection of knowledge search behaviour. This inertia will be strengthened as time goes on. If enterprises try to break this inertia, they will inevitably incur substantial path-switching costs, which will seriously discourage them from conducting new knowledge searches (Andrew & Frank, 2011), thus making it even more detrimental to the development of knowledge search activities. Therefore, based on the above literature, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H9g: Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H9h: Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

H9i: Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs.

3.10 Summary of Research Hypothesis Development

The low openness of innovation in China's technology-based SMEs, which mainly utilise their technology for R&D, has led to a "familiarity trap" in which enterprises rely heavily on their technology for innovation, falling into the path of "not-invented-here" and making it difficult for their products to meet the changes in market demand. At the same time, enterprises face the problem of commercialisation of external technologies, such as low technology patent conversion rate and low industrialisation rate, making it challenging to develop new technology application markets and falling into the path dependence of "not-sold-here", which ultimately leads to low innovation performance. By adopting the open innovation model, technology-based SMEs construct or renew their dynamic capabilities, reconfigure their knowledge absorption capability, effectively utilise external knowledge sources and new product markets, and break the path dependency in the R&D and commercialisation stages of technology innovation, thus achieving improved innovation performance. The adoption of the open innovation model by technology-based SMEs to enhance innovation performance will be constrained by cognitive inertia, which will impact the effectiveness of enterprises in creating or obtaining innovation performance. Therefore, based on the literature on open innovation models, innovation performance, absorptive capability, dynamic capability and cognitive inertia, 29 research hypotheses were developed in Table 3-1, and the mechanistic research model shown in Figure 3-1 below was constructed for empirical analysis.

Table 3-1, Research Hypotheses List

H1a	Adopting an outside-in open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs
H1b	Adopting an inside-out open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs
H1c	Adopting a coupled open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs
H2a	Adopting an outside-in open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs

- H2b Adopting an inside-out open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs
- H2c Adopting a coupled open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs
-
- H3 The absorptive capability positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs
-
- H4a Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between outside-in open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H4b Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between inside-out open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H4c Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between coupled open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
-
- H5a Adopting an outside-in open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs
- H5b Adopting an inside-out open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs
- H5c Adopting a coupled open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs
-
- H6 The dynamic capabilities positively impact innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs
-
- H7a Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between outside-in open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H7b Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between inside-out open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H7c Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between coupled open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
-
- H8a The learning inertia positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs
- H8b The experience inertia positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs

- H8c The procedural inertia negatively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs
-
- H9a Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9b Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9c Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9d Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9e Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9f Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9g Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9h Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
- H9i Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs
-

Figure 3-1, The research model for the impact of open innovation models on enterprise innovation performance under the perspectives of absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and cognitive inertia

Chapter 4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This chapter will describe the methodology used in this study, including a pilot survey based on grounded theory, operational measurement of variables in the empirical model, questionnaire design, questionnaire measurement filtering, and survey data pre-processing.

4.1 Pilot Survey

At the beginning of this study, the authors focused on the impact of open innovation models on innovation performance, in addition to seeking possible intermediate and moderating variables in this impact. However, as different scholars have different starting points for their research on open innovation theory, this has led to numerous theoretical models and findings. In the interest of rigorous consideration of the timeliness and locality of the study, the authors decided to conduct a pilot study based on the grounded theory with 100 SMEs from various industries in Shandong Province before developing a questionnaire to find out what factors are most likely to influence innovation performance in the perceptions of SME entrepreneurs.

4.1.1 Grounded Theory

First coined by American sociologists Glaser & Strauss, grounded theory is an inductive approach to exploring phenomena and refers broadly to all methods of constructing theoretical perspectives based on data (Chen, 1999).

Grounded theory works to uncover new understandings and insights into phenomena and to build and develop innovative theories (Goulding, 2002). As a qualitative research method, grounded theory has recently been applied to various research areas, including management, sociology, psychology, and social networks (Coleman & Connor, 2007). This pilot survey is an exploratory study based on a procedural grounded theory research approach. Its research

process has six major parts: data collection, coding, and analysis are the key steps.

4.1.2 Work Preparation and Data Collection

The pre-preparation for this pilot study was primarily a combination of open-ended questionnaires and random personal in-depth interviews. The review of specific literature was avoided as far as possible to avoid the authors' research ideas being bound by previous research and the interviewees' responses being guided by the findings of previous studies. A total of 72 valid questionnaires were collected, plus 14 interview transcripts. The content covered the industry in which the SME operates, the geographical location, attitudes towards innovation, whether it has an internal R&D team, whether it has experience with open innovation, expectations of open innovation, concerns about open innovation and possible reasons for refusing to engage in it.

4.1.3 Coding and Analysis

The questionnaire provides less raw information than the in-depth interview transcripts. Therefore, this grounded theory analysis will be based on in-depth interview transcripts supplemented by questionnaires. The content of the interview transcripts will first be coded and analysed, followed by a search for the amount of support for their views in the questionnaire. The actual analysis was conducted with the help of the qualitative analysis software Nvivo 9.0 to ground the interview data analysis programmatically.

Open Coding

The coding was first labelled, and specific coding rules were developed. As there were 15 primary materials for this study, they were coded in the order of the interviews, denoted by the Arabic numerals 1, 2, 3, and 15. The specific

cases were then subjected to a reverse labelling operation, with the variation numbers denoted by 1A1, 1A2, 1A3, for the first original material as an example, where the Arabic numbers before A represent the order of the source material, A represents the element we want to study - the factor impacts innovation performance - and the Arabic numbers after A represent the number of labelling numbers. Secondly, the conceptualisation of each source material was manipulated. The process of categorising and integrating the labels was carried out by using the free coding function of Nvivo 9.0 software to free code the interview transcripts, decompose the source material, analyse and repeatedly compare the fragmented data word by word and sentence by sentence, and extract the phrases needed for this study until the source material became saturated (i.e. the concept became saturated), at which point the conceptualisation process was completed. Then, classed operations are performed. That is, the classification and integration of labelling, using the software's genus coding function, effectively suggests the types that recur in the above phrases, integrates similar or identical types, and uses the original text to name them as much as possible during the operation, thus making the results more consistent with the original material. Some of the open codes are shown in Table 4-1 for length constraints.

Table 4-1, Example of Open Coding

Primary Material	Open Coding
Open innovation demands a higher quality of R&D personnel. Internal R&D staff need a more vital ability to find, screen, implement and manage external innovations and collaborate with external resources.	R&D staff quality
Technological innovation, like research and development, is a 'double-edged sword'. The chemical industry has a natural talent and technical advantage in terms of technological innovation, but at the same time, there are huge safety risks. Closed innovation allows for effective control of personnel and processes.	Insist on close innovation.
As a traditional food production and management	Insist on close

enterprise, we are still, to a large extent, limited to the closed innovation stage, without the support of high value-added products, no monopoly, and no product sharps to influence the market, open innovation for the traditional industry, it still needs a relatively long process.	innovation.
When the external environment in which a company operates is characterised by intense change, complexity and uncertainty, it is difficult for the company to cope with its resources alone, or the risk of acting independently is too high.	Environmental Dynamics
The technical capacity of the partner cannot meet the needs of innovation. Furthermore, the innovation capacity of the company's existing technical team meets the needs of the company's products and technological innovation.	External Knowledge Sourcing
The enterprise's closed innovation benefits from special research funding from the local government and has good conditions for innovation, sufficient to meet our needs and can lead the development direction of the local industry without the need for open innovation for the time being.	Insist on close innovation.
The lack of high-tech talent is the main reason limiting open innovation in our company.	R&D staff quality
The core competencies of the company's main business are currently at the absolute leading position in the industry. Furthermore, the company's business objectives do not need to broaden new areas for now; the goal is to build a well-known brand.	Insist on close innovation.
The company's innovation capacity does not meet the industry's needs and cannot effectively transform external knowledge into products.	Cannot transfer knowledge
With many industry-leading professionals in-house, no external skills are required.	Self-confidence
...	

Axial Coding

The free nodes obtained from the open coding are further analysed, and the free nodes with high similarity are merged to categorise them into higher-level tree nodes in the process. By exploring the connections between the different nodes, the potential connections between the free nodes at the conceptual level are grasped, and potential threats are discovered. For example, "insistence on closed innovation", "lack of understanding of open innovation", and "confidence in corporate innovation" were merged into "cognitive inertia". The questions "the company wants to be more involved in professional meetings" and "the company updates its products in response to customer demand" were merged into "the company's ability to perceive external knowledge". By doing so, the many free nodes were further grouped into eight nodes (i.e. sub-categories). The eight sub-categories were eventually grouped into three categories based on the literature. It can be seen that the most frequent variables that impact the open innovation model on innovation performance among the SME executives who participated in the pilot survey were absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and cognitive inertia. However, some scholars have identified absorptive capability as part of dynamic capability; more than half of the entrepreneurs mentioned absorptive capability as a concern. The absorptive capability was, therefore, singled out for focus. In summary, absorptive capability contains two sub-categories, dynamic capability contains three sub-categories, and cognitive inertia also contains three sub-categories. The specific hierarchy of factors analysed by Nvivo 9.0 is shown in Table 4.2.

Table 4-2, The Hierarchy of Relevant Factors

Ax	ax	aax
The intermediate and moderating variables in the impact of open innovation models on innovation performance	Absorptive Capability	Potential absorptive capability Realised absorptive capability
	Dynamic Capabilities	Ability to sense

	opportunities
	Ability to capture opportunities
	Ability to transform opportunities
Cognitive inertia	Learning inertia
	Experience inertia
	Procedural inertia

Selective Coding

The final step of the analysis process in the procedural grounded theory approach is the selection of the core categories that systematically summarise all the conceptual categories that have been found. The main categories, categories and sub-categories, which are coded in the main axes, are associated with each other according to the research needs and are extracted, reorganised, integrated and compared with the original data several times so that the concepts are sublimated. It is then compared with existing theories and research results to ensure that the main categories, categories and sub-categories are close to the source material and, simultaneously, in line with the reality of open innovation in SMEs. The results of the grounded theory analysis, which categorised the impact variables as absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and cognitive inertia, further suggest that the delineation of possible impact factors in the open innovation model on innovation performance in the research design section of this thesis is theoretically sound.

Theoretical Saturation Testing

Theoretical saturation testing is also a crucial part of the procedural grounded theory research methodology and is the process of testing the final results of the groundedness. To further confirm the completeness and feasibility of the

coding in this study, the final 13 questionnaires collected were analysed for theoretical saturation at the end of the coding analysis process. This was done by following the steps of open coding, axial coding and selective coding to code the newly collected questionnaire level by level. The final theoretical saturation test revealed that no new categories outside of the three categories mentioned above were found, and no new categories were found within the three categories, indicating that the theoretical categories subject to construction in this study were well developed, suggesting that the theoretical constructs achieved through the grounded analysis have reached a state of saturation.

4.2 Operational Variables Measurement Scales

4.2.1 Measurement Scales for Open Innovation Models Variables

There is no classical and unified measurement scale for measuring open innovation activities carried out by enterprises. According to the previous theoretical analysis, open innovation activities of enterprises take various forms, but from the perspective of knowledge flow, they can undoubtedly be classified into three types, namely outside-in, coupled and inside-out open innovation. However, no scale measures the three types of open innovation. Therefore, this paper will measure the open innovation activities of enterprises in terms of four open innovation models: acquiring, sourcing, selling and revealing (Dahlander & Gann, 2010), and then identify items to measure outside-in, coupled and inside-out open innovation by extracting principal components from the survey data. The items in the acquiring and sourcing model mainly reflect outside-in open innovation activities, the items in the selling and disclosing model reflect inside-out open innovation activities, and some combination of items in the acquiring, sourcing, selling and revealing model reflects coupled open innovation activities. Open innovation is measured on a five-point Likert scale, with SME executives scoring the extent to which they agree with each item, with 1 representing strong disagreement and 5 representing strong agreement.

Table 4-3, Open Innovation Model Measurement Scales

Measurement Dimensions	Measurement Items	Literature Sources
Acquiring	Ac ₁ : Enterprises often purchase and utilise new technologies or intellectual property from other enterprises and institutions.	Parida et al. (2012)
	Ac ₂ : Enterprises outsource a high proportion of R&D.	Berchicci (2013)
Sourcing	So ₁ : Enterprises regularly source external ideas that have the potential to create value for the enterprise.	Chesbrough (2003)
	So ₂ : Enterprises have a robust system for sourcing external technology and intellectual property.	Chesbrough & Crowther (2006)
	So ₃ : Enterprises proactively engage with external participants for better technological knowledge or products.	Lichtenthaler (2008)
	So ₄ : Enterprises build closer relationships with external participants and rely on their innovations.	Hung & Chou (2013)
Selling	Se ₁ : Enterprises proactively manage the outflow of knowledge.	Chesbrough (2003)
	Se ₂ : Enterprises sell technical knowledge and intellectual property in the marketplace formally.	Chesbrough & Crowther (2006)
	Se ₃ : Enterprises have a dedicated department for the commercialisation of intellectual assets.	Lichtenthaler (2008)
	Se ₄ : Enterprise welcomes other organisations and individuals to purchase and utilise the enterprise's technological knowledge or intellectual property.	Lichtenthaler (2009)

	Se5: Enterprises rarely share their technology with external organisations.	Hung & Chou (2013)
Revealing	Re1: Enterprises may selectively reveal some intellectual property for further gains.	von Hippel & von Krogh (2006)
	Re2: Enterprises often reveal proprietary information and knowledge about the products they develop for free.	Henkel et al. (2014)

4.2.2 Measurement Scales for Absorptive Capability

Two dimensions of absorptive capability are used as the focus of the study: potential absorptive capability and realised absorptive capability. The potential absorptive capability measures focus on five topics, including the ability of enterprises to acquire and absorb external knowledge, based on Zahra & George (2002). The realised absorptive capability measures focus on five topics, including the ability of enterprises to transform and utilise external knowledge, based on Flatten et al. (2011). Absorptive capability is measured using a five-point Likert scale, which allows SME executives to rate each item's occurrence frequency, with one being almost none and five being very frequent.

Table 4-4, Absorptive Capability Measurement Scales

Measurement Dimensions	Measurement Items	Literature Sources
Potential Absorptive Capability	PAC ₁ : Finding relevant industry information is a daily task for enterprises.	Zahra & George (2002)
	PAC ₂ : Enterprises obtain industry information through various channels.	
	PAC ₃ : External knowledge is gained through contact with customers, suppliers, and other enterprises or organisations.	
	PAC ₄ : Ideas are exchanged, problems are	

solved across departments Ideas are exchanged, and problems are solved across departments.

PAC₅: Regular meetings are held to share achievements and problems arising during the enterprise's development.

Realised Absorptive Capability	RAC ₁ : The enterprise can quickly identify opportunities from external knowledge.	
	RAC ₂ : Employees can apply external knowledge in their daily work.	
	RAC ₃ : Employees can link existing knowledge with new external knowledge.	Flatten et al. (2011)
	RAC ₄ : The enterprise supports the development of new products and services.	
	RAC ₅ : The enterprise regularly considers technical issues and adapts to new knowledge.	

4.2.3 Measurement Scales for Dynamic Capabilities

According to Teece's (2007) definition of dynamic capabilities, dynamic capabilities are measured in three dimensions: the ability to sense, capture and transform opportunities. The dynamic capabilities of the enterprise were measured using a five-point Likert scale, which allowed SME exclusives to rate the frequency of occurrence of each measured item, with 1 representing almost none and five representing very frequent.

Table 4-5, Dynamic Capabilities Measurement Scales

Measurement Dimensions	Measurement Items	Literature Sources
Ability to Sense	ASO ₁ : Enterprise participates in the activities of professional associations	Teece (2007)

Opportunities	<p>/scientific or professional conferences.</p> <p>ASO₂: Enterprise uses established processes to identify target markets, changes in customer needs and user innovations.</p> <p>ASO₃: Enterprise observes best practices in the sectors.</p> <p>ASO₄: Economic information is gathered about the enterprise's operations and the operational environment relevant to it.</p>	
<p>Ability to Capture Opportunities</p>	<p>ACO₁: The enterprise is willing to invest in helping customers find solutions.</p> <p>ACO₂: The enterprise adopts best practices in the sector.</p> <p>ACO₃: The enterprise responds to deficiencies identified by employees.</p> <p>ACO₄: The enterprise changes its current practices when customer feedback gives it a reason to change.</p>	<p>Wilden et al. (2013)</p>
<p>Ability to Transform Opportunities</p>	<p>The frequency of the following activities in the enterprise in the last five years:</p> <p>ARO₁: Implement new or substantially changed corporate strategies.</p> <p>ARO₂: Implement new management methods.</p> <p>ARO₃: Implement new or substantially changed marketing methods or strategies.</p> <p>ARO₄: Substantial renewal of business processes.</p> <p>ARO₅: Substantial change in the way the business objectives are met.</p>	<p>Wilden & Gudergan (2015)</p>

4.2.4 Measurement Scales for Cognitive Inertia

In this paper, a three-dimensional division of cognitive inertia into learning inertia, experience inertia and procedural inertia was conducted, and the scale of relevant variables in this paper was designed based on Liao's (2002) research, combined with the well-established scales adopted by Zhao (2012), Xie (2016) and Fan (2016), with moderate adjustments. Cognitive inertia was measured using a five-point Likert scale, which allowed SME executives to rate the frequency of occurrence of each measure, with one representing almost none and five representing very frequent.

Table 4-6, Cognitive Inertia Measurement Scales

Measurement Dimensions	Measurement Items	Literature Sources
Learning Inertia	LI1: Enterprises will provide opportunities to learn new ideas or new approaches.	Zhao (2012)
	LI2: When new problems are encountered, enterprises will try to solve them in new ways.	
	LI3: Enterprises try to learn new ideas to change how they think and act.	
	LI4: Enterprises often use different approaches to solve problems.	
	LI5: Enterprises actively seek out new sources of knowledge.	
Experience Inertia	EI1: Enterprises are used to obtaining knowledge from the same sources or channels.	Xie (2016)
	EI2: Enterprises rely heavily on previous knowledge or experience.	
	EI3: Past knowledge and experience increase the efficiency of the department's work.	
	EI4: Enterprises use previous experience to solve new problems.	
	EI5: Enterprises often learn from previous experience.	

El₆: Past knowledge and experience affect how much an enterprise accepts new knowledge.

Procedural Inertia	PI ₁ : Enterprises use the same procedures and approaches to solve practical problems as in the past.	
	PI ₂ : Enterprises are not good at using insightful methods to solve problems.	
	PI ₃ : Enterprises are not flexible and innovative in their strict procedures.	Fan (2016)
	PI ₄ : Enterprises are not keen to learn new ideas to change their thinking and behaviour.	
	PI ₅ : Enterprise problem-solving strategies are predictable.	

4.2.5 Measurement Scales for Innovation Performance

There is no uniform measurement of enterprise innovation performance as its connotation has not been standardised. Since innovation performance is a comprehensive measure of an enterprise's innovation outcomes, it can be measured employing the innovation performance of new products and new technologies, the two main output categories of enterprise innovation. Considering the innovation scenario of Chinese enterprises, the measurement scale of Chen et al. (2011) adopted this as the basis for constructing the measurement items for technology-based SMEs. The five-point Likert scale method was adopted to allow the senior managers of the enterprises to score the degree of agreement with each measurement item.

Table 4-7, Innovation Performance Measurement Scales

Variable	Measurement Items	Literature Sources
Innovation Performance	IP ₁ : Enterprise new product quality (1=very poor, 5=very good) IP ₂ : Enterprise new product quantity	Atuahene Gima et al. (2005);

(1=very low, 5=very high)	Knudsen & Mortensen (2011);
IP ₃ : Enterprise new product sales as a proportion of total sales	
(1=very low, 5=very high)	
IP ₄ : Enterprise's speed of new product development	Chen et al. (2011);
(1=very slow, 5=very fast)	
IP ₅ : Enterprise cost of new product development	Pullen et al. (2012);
(1=very low, 5=very high)	
IP ₆ : Enterprise success rate of new product development	Yue et al. (2018)
(1=very low, 5=very high)	
IP ₇ : Number of patents applied for or registered by the enterprise	
(1=very low, 5=very high)	
IP ₈ : Number of industry standards the enterprise has led in developing	
(1=very low, 5=very high)	

4.3 Questionnaire Design and Sample Acquisition

4.3.1 Questionnaire Design

Following the principle of concise and easy-to-answer, the questionnaire length was appropriate, with a response time of 20 minutes or less. Only the question directly related to the purpose of this study was included in this questionnaire. The vocabulary and sentences for each question were simple, easy to understand, and accurately reflected the variables being measured in Chinese. All vocabulary and sentences for describing each question were kept neutral and subject. Moreover, any sensitive questions, such as those related to privacy or confidentiality, were avoided as far as possible so that the SME exclusives could answer the questions truthfully. The questionnaire included six parts based on the measurement scales for each operational variable. The

first part of the questionnaire focuses on basic information about the participant's enterprise, including the size of the enterprise, how long it has been in operation, and the percentage of employees engaged in the R&D department. The second to sixth parts are the measurement scales for open innovation models, the absorptive capability, the dynamic capabilities, the cognitive inertia and the innovation performance. The original questionnaire and its English translation are in the Appendix chapter.

Table 4-8, Questionnaire Design

Questionnaire Parts	Measurement Purpose	Numbers of Question	Details
Part 1	Enterprises basic information	No. 1 ~ 4	The size of the enterprise, how long it has been in operation, and the percentage of employees engaged in the R&D department.
Part 2	Open Innovation Models	Acquiring: Ac ₁ , Ac ₂ ; Sourcing: So ₁ ~So ₄ ; Selling: Se ₁ ~Se ₅ ; Revealing: Re ₁ , Re ₂	The four main dimensions of acquiring, sourcing, selling and revealing are measured on a five-point Likert scale, from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'.
Part 3	Absorptive Capability	Potential absorptive capability: PAC ₁ ~PAC ₅ ; Realised	The two dimensions of enterprises' potential and realised absorptive capability are measured on a five-point Likert scale, from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'.

		absorptive capability: RAC ₁ ~RAC ₅	
Part 4	Dynamic Capabilities	Ability to sense opportunities: ASO ₁ ~ASO ₄ ; Ability to capture opportunities: ACO ₁ ~ACO ₄ ; Ability to transform opportunities: ATO ₁ -ATO ₅	The three main dimensions of the ability to sense, capture and transform opportunities are measured on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 'almost none' to 'very frequent'.
Part 5	Cognitive Inertia	Learning inertia: LI ₁ ~LI ₅ ; Experience inertia: EI ₁ ~EI ₆ ; Procedural inertia: PI ₁ ~PI ₅	The three main dimensions of learning, experience and procedural inertia are measured on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'.
Part 6	Innovation Performance	IP ₁ -IP ₈	Measured on the five-point Likert scale.

4.3.2 Sample Acquisition

In order to improve the speed and quality of questionnaire collection, this study relies on the help of a third-party questionnaire agency to administer the online questionnaire and collect the sample data via the Internet. Five hundred questionnaires were distributed to 250 executives of technology-based SMEs in several provinces and cities across China through a third-party survey agency. Among them, 349 questionnaires were valid, with a valid return rate of 69.80%. Valid samples were selected based on the following: 1) Questionnaires with a total response time of fewer than 10 minutes were considered invalid; questionnaires with questions that were not wholly completed were also counted as invalid.

4.3.3 Data Analysis Methods

This study relied on the data analysis software SPSS, AMOS and SmartPLS to analyse the data samples and research hypotheses at various levels and perspectives, including the following data analysis methods.

(1) Descriptive statistical data analysis was first performed relying on SPSS. The main focus was on descriptive analysis of the questions in the first part of the questionnaire involving basic information about the enterprise, including enterprise size, operating time, percentage of R&D employees within the enterprise and description of enterprise innovation. Secondly, the distribution of each measure's mean and standard deviation of the required variables in the model was described.

(2) The homogeneous bias tests. Homogeneous bias was tested by SPSS for each measured item of the variables. Homoscedasticity refers to artificial covariation between predictor variables and validated variables caused by the same data source or rater, measurement context, item context, and the items' characteristics. In this study, the problem of homophily was tested using Harmam single-factor analysis: all questionnaire items were included in factor

analysis and judged based on the first principal component when unrotated. If only one factor was analysed or if one factor had the majority of explanatory power, it was judged that there was severe homoscedasticity bias (Zhang, 2016).

3) Reliability analysis. A Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.6 was used as the minimum criterion for the reliability analysis of the variables of open innovation, dynamic capabilities, innovation performance, environmental dynamics and knowledge inertia.

4) Validity analysis via AMOS. In this study, the scale's validity was analysed using factor analysis, which consisted of two main methods: exploratory and validation factor analysis. Exploratory and validation factor analyses were used to examine the structural validity of the variables of open innovation, dynamic capabilities, innovation performance, environmental dynamics and knowledge inertia.

5) Correlation analysis. Person correlation analysis was used to analyse the research data, specifically to explore the correlation coefficients between the critical variables of open innovation, dynamic capabilities, innovation performance, environmental dynamics and knowledge inertia, to examine the interrelationships between the variables and lay the foundation for further analysis.

6) Regression analysis via SmartPLS. Due to the small sample size, it was not possible to ascertain whether the survey data satisfied a multivariate normal distribution, so the PLS method was used to analyse the causal relationship between the model hypotheses in order to determine the causal

relationship between the variables affecting each other, to verify the model hypotheses.

4.4 Summary of Research Methodology

In this part, data analysis methods were introduced. The pilot survey based on grounded theory sorted and identified the variables required in this research, including independent, dependent, mediating and moderating variables. Then, measurement scales for each variable in the questionnaire were developed based on the previous research findings and paper. After that, a questionnaire was developed following the research logic based on the pilot survey results and the measurement scales mentioned above. Finally, the comprehensive data analysis methods were presented, which will be used to comprehensively and systematically analyse the data from the questionnaire and ultimately test the research hypotheses in this thesis.

Chapter 5. Data Analysis

In this chapter, the data analysis process will be presented. This analysis process only addresses the relationship between the variables and their constituent measures, including descriptive statistics, homogeneous bias tests, and reliability and validity tests for the measures. The various relationships between variables are described in the next chapter.

5.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis

5.1.1 Descriptive Statistical Analysis for Basic Information

The technology-based SMEs in this survey are of different sizes, ages, R&D capabilities and open innovation models. The distribution of these SMEs is shown in Table 5-1 – Table 5-4.

Table 5-1, Amount of Current Employees in Enterprises

(people)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 100	51	14.6	14.6	14.6
101-200	108	30.9	30.9	45.6
201-300	131	37.5	37.5	83.1
301-400	31	8.9	8.9	92.0
401-500	19	5.4	5.4	97.4
More than 500	9	2.6	2.6	100.0
Total	349	100.0	100.0	

Table 5-2, Operating Time of Enterprises

(year)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 1	35	10.0	10.0	10.0
1-3	127	36.4	36.4	46.4
4-6	149	42.7	42.7	89.1

7-9	27	7.7	7.7	96.8
More than 10	11	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	349	100.0	100.0	

Table 5-3, % R&D Personnel to Total

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Less than 10%	17	4.9	4.9	4.9
11%-15%	206	59.0	59.0	63.9
16%-20%	29	8.3	8.3	72.2
21%-25%	25	7.2	7.2	79.4
26%-30%	65	18.6	18.6	98.0
More than 30%	7	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	349	100.0	100.0	

Table 5-4, Describe The Enterprises' Innovation

(Option)	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
A	80	22.9	22.9	22.9
B	78	22.3	22.3	45.3
C	81	23.2	23.2	68.5
D	67	19.2	19.2	87.7
E	43	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	349	100.0	100.0	

As seen from the above tables, the size of technology-based SMEs is mainly concentrated in those with less than 300 employees, accounting for over 80% of the total number of enterprises in the sample. Enterprises with less than seven years of operation account for nearly 90% of the total number of enterprises in the sample, which are relatively young and have a strong drive for innovation. The number of enterprises with more than 25% of R&D personnel has exceeded nearly 80% of the sample enterprises, reflecting the strong R&D capability of technology-based SMEs. All enterprises have

adopted various open innovation models and can actively seek cooperation from external organisations and purchase intellectual property from the technology market to supplement their R&D deficiencies. Overall, the valid sample represents enterprise size, age, R&D capability and open innovation models and can meet the analytical requirements of open innovation performance studies of technology-based SMEs.

5.1.2 Descriptive Statistical Analysis for Open Innovation Model

The descriptive statistics for the open innovation models (OIM) measures are shown in Table 5-5. As can be seen, the mean values for all the measures are more significant than 2.5, indicating that the surveyed technology-based SMEs have implemented open innovation activities to varying degrees and have adopted a combination of models simultaneously. In addition, the mean value of 3.48 for the open innovation measure is more significant than 2.5, indicating that open innovation is now commonly practised by the surveyed technology-based SMEs.

Table 5-5, Descriptive Statistics for OIM

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Ac1	349	1	5	3.69	0.817
Ac2	349	1	5	3.59	0.810
So2	349	1	5	3.35	1.121
So3	349	1	5	3.43	1.179
So4	349	1	5	3.46	0.849
Se1	349	1	5	3.40	1.152
Se2	349	1	5	3.46	1.165
Se4	349	1	5	3.40	0.854
Se5	349	1	5	3.43	1.116
Re1	349	1	5	3.64	0.884
OIM	349	1.50	4.60	3.486	0.624
Valid N (listwise)	349				

5.1.3 Descriptive Statistical Analysis for Absorptive Capability

The descriptive statistics for the absorptive capability (AC) measures are shown in Table 5-6. As can be seen, the mean values of all the measures are more significant than 2.5, indicating that both potential (PAC) and realised absorptive capability (RAC) exist among the surveyed technology-based SMEs. At the same time, the mean value of 3.708 for the absorptive capability measure is more significant than 2.5, indicating that the sample enterprises as a whole have a high absorptive capability.

Table 5-6, Descriptive Statistics for AC

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
PAC1	349	1	5	3.90	0.920
PAC2	349	1	5	3.78	1.099
PAC4	349	2	5	3.77	0.786
PAC5	349	1	5	3.68	0.870
RAC1	349	2	5	3.40	0.691
RAC2	349	1	5	3.72	0.955
RAC3	349	1	5	3.72	1.015
RAC4	349	1	5	3.68	1.031
AC	349	1.63	4.88	3.708	0.610
Valid N (listwise)	349				

5.1.4 Descriptive Statistical Analysis for Dynamic Capabilities

The descriptive statistics for dynamic capabilities (DC) are shown in Table 5-7. As can be seen, the mean values of all the measures are more significant than 2.5, indicating that the ability to sense (ASO), ability to capture (ACO), and ability to transform opportunities (ARO) are all present in the surveyed technology-based SMEs. Meanwhile, the mean value of the dynamic capabilities measurement scale is 3.384, more significant than 2.5, indicating that the sample enterprises have high dynamic capabilities.

Table 5-7, Descriptive Statistics for DC

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
ASO1	349	1	5	3.42	1.116
ASO2	349	1	5	3.55	1.037
ASO3	349	1	5	3.62	0.917
ASO4	349	1	5	3.50	0.918
ACO1	349	1	5	3.79	1.024
ACO2	349	1	5	3.53	1.068
ACO3	349	1	5	3.68	1.120
ACO4	349	1	5	3.64	0.872
ATO1	349	1	5	3.07	1.215
ATO2	349	1	5	3.15	1.180
ATO3	349	1	5	3.10	0.926
ATO4	349	1	5	2.99	1.368
ATO5	349	1	5	2.97	1.278
DC	349	1.38	4.85	3.384	0.626
Valid N (listwise)	349				

5.1.5 Descriptive Statistical Analysis for Cognitive Inertia

The descriptive statistics of cognitive inertia (CI) are shown in Table 5-8. The mean values of all learning inertia (LI) measures were more significant than 2.5, indicating that the executives in the surveyed technology-based SMEs had a high level of learning inertia and were not better able to learn and absorb new knowledge. The mean value of all measures of experience inertia (EI) was more significant than 2.5, indicating that executives in the sample enterprises had a high level of experience inertia and relied more on previous experience and knowledge when decision-making. Procedural inertia (PI) was also greater than 2.5 for all measures, indicating a high level of procedural inertia among executives in the sample enterprises, indicating that they refer to strict procedures in their entrepreneurial activities. The mean value of the cognitive inertia measure was 3.528, indicating a high level of cognitive inertia among executives in the sample enterprises.

Table 5-8, Descriptive Statistics for CI

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
LI1	349	2	5	3.44	0.944
LI2	349	2	5	3.44	0.937
LI4	349	1	5	3.37	1.013
LI	349	1.67	5.00	3.415	0.797
EI3	349	1	5	3.68	1.020
EI5	349	1	5	3.59	0.796
EI6	349	1	5	3.66	0.814
EI	349	1.00	5.00	3.641	0.722
PI1	349	1	5	3.61	1.148
PI3	349	1	5	3.60	0.893
PI5	349	1	5	3.36	0.720
PI	349	1.33	5.00	3.526	0.772
CI	349	1.67	4.56	3.528	0.556
Valid N (listwise)	349				

5.1.6 Descriptive Statistical Analysis for Innovation Performance

The descriptive statistics for innovation performance (IP) are shown in Table 5-9. The mean values of all the measures are more significant than 2.5, indicating the presence of innovation performance among the surveyed technology-based SMEs. Meanwhile, the mean value of the innovation performance measurement scale is 3.494, which is greater than 2.5, indicating that the sample enterprises have a high level of innovation performance.

Table 5-9, Descriptive Statistics for IP

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
IP1	349	1	5	3.62	1.150
IP2	349	1	5	3.44	1.077
IP3	349	1	5	3.51	1.169
IP4	349	1	5	3.52	0.859
IP6	349	1	5	3.56	0.894
IP7	349	2	5	3.31	0.732

IP	349	1.33	5.00	3.494	0.800
Valid N (listwise)	349				

5.2 Homogeneous Bia Test

As the data for this questionnaire were obtained from executives, it was necessary to test the questionnaire data for homoscedasticity. The Harman one-way analysis of variance test found that the first principal component at unrotated explained 25.002% of the total variance, which was less than 50% and did not account for the majority of the total variance, so it was concluded that there was no severe homophily bias in this survey (see Table 5-10).

Table 5-10, Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	11.502	25.005	25.005	11.502	25.005	25.005	4.223	9.181	9.181
2	3.633	7.898	32.903	3.633	7.898	32.903	3.803	8.267	17.448
3	2.645	5.751	38.654	2.645	5.751	38.654	3.370	7.326	24.774
4	2.466	5.360	44.014	2.466	5.360	44.014	3.139	6.825	31.599
5	2.434	5.292	49.306	2.434	5.292	49.306	3.073	6.681	38.280
6	2.165	4.707	54.012	2.165	4.707	54.012	3.020	6.565	44.844
7	1.987	4.321	58.333	1.987	4.321	58.333	2.566	5.579	50.423
8	1.804	3.923	62.256	1.804	3.923	62.256	2.176	4.731	55.154
9	1.476	3.208	65.463	1.476	3.208	65.463	2.155	4.684	59.838
10	1.435	3.120	68.584	1.435	3.120	68.584	2.112	4.591	64.428
11	1.148	2.495	71.079	1.148	2.495	71.079	2.074	4.510	68.938
12	1.009	2.193	73.272	1.009	2.193	73.272	1.994	4.334	73.272
13	0.841	1.829	75.101						
14	0.699	1.519	76.620						
15	0.675	1.467	78.087						
16	0.639	1.388	79.475						
17	0.585	1.272	80.747						
18	0.577	1.255	82.002						
19	0.555	1.207	83.209						

20	0.502	1.091	84.300
21	0.471	1.024	85.324
22	0.431	0.938	86.262
23	0.424	0.922	87.184
24	0.413	0.897	88.081
25	0.402	0.875	88.956
26	0.391	0.850	89.805
27	0.368	0.800	90.605
28	0.346	0.752	91.357
29	0.325	0.707	92.065
30	0.312	0.677	92.742
31	0.289	0.627	93.369
32	0.268	0.583	93.952
33	0.263	0.572	94.524
34	0.252	0.547	95.071
35	0.245	0.533	95.604
36	0.235	0.510	96.114
37	0.224	0.486	96.601
38	0.216	0.469	97.069
39	0.202	0.439	97.508
40	0.188	0.408	97.917
41	0.181	0.393	98.310
42	0.174	0.379	98.689
43	0.166	0.361	99.049

44	0.160	0.348	99.397
45	0.144	0.314	99.712
46	0.133	0.288	100.000

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

5.3 Reliability Tests

This study tested reliability using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, with a reliability coefficient of 0.5 being the minimum acceptable standard (Nunnally, 1978), 0.7-0.8 being reasonably good, and 0.8 or more being very good (De Vellis, 1991). In addition, the data were filtered using a Corrected Item-Total Correlation (CITC) for each item score of the measure. The process was to remove items with a CITC of less than 0.3 and to check whether Cronbach's alpha coefficient had improved after removing the item. If there was an increase, the items were removed until Cronbach's alpha coefficients were less than the current ones, and then the filtering process was stopped. SPSS 27.0 was used to analyse the data for reliability.

5.3.1 Reliability Test for Open Innovation Models

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the open innovation models variable measures was $0.753 > 0.6$, indicating acceptable internal consistency and reliability of the open innovation models variable measures (see Tables 5-11 and 5-12).

Table 5-11, Reliability Statistics for Open Innovation

Models		
Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.753	0.768	13

Table 5-12, Item-Total Statistics for Open Innovation Models

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Ac1	42.03	40.798	0.438	0.597	0.734
Ac2	42.13	41.268	0.396	0.554	0.737

So1	42.16	42.700	0.132	0.141	0.767
So2	42.37	38.314	0.466	0.474	0.727
So3	42.30	37.668	0.483	0.601	0.725
So4	42.26	39.991	0.496	0.648	0.728
Se1	42.32	37.183	0.536	0.530	0.718
Se2	42.27	37.276	0.520	0.537	0.720
Se3	42.15	41.943	0.158	0.207	0.766
Se4	42.32	39.559	0.536	0.572	0.724
Se5	42.30	39.933	0.345	0.186	0.742
Re1	42.08	39.453	0.522	0.514	0.725
Re2	41.99	44.385	0.049	0.123	0.771

However, the CITC of the So1 Se3 Re2 measures were 0.132, 0.158 and 0.049, respectively, all of which were less than 0.3, so the measures were removed, as shown in Tables 5-13 and 5-14.

Table 5-13, Reliability Statistics for Open Innovation

Models 2		
Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.822	0.828	10

Table 5-14, Item-Total Statistics for Open Innovation Models 2

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Ac1	31.16	33.580	0.494	0.595	0.808
Ac2	31.26	34.034	0.448	0.553	0.812
So2	31.50	31.073	0.527	0.470	0.804
So3	31.43	30.694	0.524	0.600	0.805
So4	31.39	33.038	0.529	0.646	0.805
Se1	31.45	30.507	0.557	0.522	0.800
Se2	31.40	30.477	0.551	0.528	0.801
Se4	31.46	32.525	0.582	0.568	0.800

Se5	31.43	32.981	0.366	0.183	0.822
Re1	31.21	32.600	0.548	0.509	0.802

After removing the three measures, Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the open innovation models variable measures was $0.822 > 0.7$, indicating that the open innovation models variable measures have good internal consistency and reliability. The CITC values for each open innovation models variable measure ranged from 0.336-0.582, all more significant than 0.3, and the “Cronbach's alpha coefficients if item deleted” were all less than 0.822, and the scale stopped being purified. Thus, the open innovation models variable included ten measures, namely, Ac12, So2-4, Se1245 and Re1.

5.3.2 Reliability Test for Absorptive Capability

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the absorptive capability variable measures was $0.728 > 0.6$, indicating acceptable internal consistency and reliability of the absorptive capability variable measures (see Tables 5-15 and 5-16).

Table 5-15, Reliability Statistics for Absorptive Capability

Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.728	0.731	10

Table 5-16, Item-Total Statistics for Absorptive Capability

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
PAC1	33.11	20.528	0.455	0.513	0.696
PAC2	33.23	19.110	0.506	0.604	0.685
PAC3	33.32	24.214	-0.019	0.032	0.776
PAC4	33.24	20.682	0.542	0.646	0.686

PAC5	33.33	20.296	0.525	0.586	0.686
RAC1	33.61	21.998	0.416	0.414	0.705
RAC2	33.29	20.130	0.482	0.501	0.691
RAC3	33.29	19.121	0.566	0.663	0.675
RAC4	33.33	19.125	0.553	0.549	0.677
RAC5	33.35	24.855	-0.037	0.015	0.759

However, the CITC of the PAC3 and RAC5 measures were -0.019 and -0.037, respectively, all of which were less than 0.3, so the measures were removed, as shown in Tables 5-17 and 5-18.

Table 5-17, Reliability Statistics for Absorptive Capability

2

Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.811	0.813	8

Table 5-18, Item-Total Statistics for Absorptive Capability 2

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
PAC1	25.76	19.113	0.478	0.512	0.796
PAC2	25.89	17.797	0.518	0.603	0.793
PAC4	25.89	19.333	0.557	0.645	0.787
PAC5	25.98	18.764	0.568	0.581	0.784
RAC1	26.26	20.642	0.428	0.412	0.803
RAC2	25.94	18.568	0.525	0.496	0.790
RAC3	25.95	17.759	0.586	0.659	0.780
RAC4	25.99	17.761	0.573	0.548	0.782

After removing two measures, Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the absorptive capability variable measures was 0.811 > 0.7, indicating that the absorptive capability variable measures have good internal consistency and reliability.

The CITC values for each absorptive capability variable measure ranged from 0.428 – 0.586, all of which were more significant than 0.3, and the “Cronbach's alpha coefficients if item deleted” were all less than 0.811, and the scale stopped being purified. Thus, the absorptive capability variable included eight measures, namely, PAC1245 and RAC1-4.

5.3.3 Reliability Test for Dynamic Capabilities

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the dynamic capabilities variable measures was 0.831 > 0.6, indicating acceptable internal consistency and reliability of the dynamic capabilities variable measures (see Tables 5-19 and 5-20).

Table 5-19, Reliability Statistics for Dynamic Capabilities

Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.831	0.833	13

Table 5-20, Item-Total Statistics Reliability Statistics for Dynamic Capabilities

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
ASO1	40.57	56.475	0.506	0.636	0.817
ASO2	40.45	57.708	0.471	0.697	0.819
ASO3	40.38	57.777	0.544	0.716	0.815
ASO4	40.50	58.825	0.464	0.691	0.820
ACO1	40.21	59.191	0.379	0.588	0.826
ACO2	40.47	59.094	0.364	0.584	0.827
ACO3	40.32	58.207	0.395	0.510	0.825
ACO4	40.36	58.846	0.493	0.607	0.819
ATO1	40.92	55.238	0.525	0.645	0.815
ATO2	40.85	56.476	0.470	0.597	0.820

ATO3	40.90	58.510	0.482	0.538	0.819
ATO4	41.01	52.937	0.573	0.650	0.811
ATO5	41.02	54.402	0.539	0.643	0.814

The CITC values for each dynamic capabilities variable measure ranged from 0.364 – 0.573, all greater than 0.3, and the “Cronbach's alpha coefficients if item deleted” were less than 0.831. Thus, the dynamic capabilities variable included 13 measures, namely, ASO1-4, ACO 1-4 and ATO 1-5.

5.3.4 Reliability Test for Cognitive Inertia

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the cognitive inertia variable measures was $0.589 < 0.6$, indicating no acceptable internal consistency and reliability of the cognitive inertia variable measures (see Tables 5-21 and 5-22).

Table 5-21, Reliability Statistics for Cognitive Inertia

Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.589	0.584	16

Table 5-22, Item-Total Statistics for Cognitive Inertia

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
LI1	52.31	26.123	0.346	0.376	0.551
LI2	52.32	25.477	0.422	0.456	0.537
LI3	52.43	29.614	-0.019	0.052	0.614
LI4	52.39	24.727	0.456	0.398	0.527
LI5	52.52	29.687	-0.019	0.018	0.612
EI1	52.27	29.363	0.018	0.037	0.606
EI2	52.21	29.485	-0.019	0.047	0.617
EI3	52.08	24.654	0.459	0.435	0.526
EI4	52.32	29.475	0.016	0.033	0.604

EI5	52.17	25.854	0.477	0.414	0.535
EI6	52.10	26.232	0.415	0.350	0.544
PI1	52.14	24.163	0.431	0.443	0.528
PI2	52.15	30.012	-0.050	0.059	0.617
PI3	52.15	25.681	0.428	0.512	0.538
PI4	52.38	30.197	-0.049	0.048	0.609
PI5	52.40	27.757	0.274	0.380	0.567

The CITC of the LI3 (-0.019), LI5 (-0.019), EI2 (-0.019), EI4 (-0.016) and PI2 (-0.050) were less than 0.3, so the measures were removed. Though the CITC of the PI5 is 0.274 (near 0.3), the “Cronbach’s alpha if item deleted” was less than 0.589, so PI5 was kept to see what happened later. The progress is shown in Tables 5-23 and 5-24.

Table 5-23, Reliability Statistics for Cognitive Inertia 2

Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.776	0.778	9

Table 5-24, Item-Total Statistics for Cognitive Inertia 2

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
LI1	28.30	20.597	0.410	0.361	0.761
LI2	28.31	20.560	0.420	0.439	0.760
LI4	28.38	19.714	0.474	0.389	0.752
EI3	28.07	19.072	0.549	0.432	0.740
EI5	28.16	20.376	0.556	0.412	0.743
EI6	28.09	20.633	0.502	0.339	0.749
PI1	28.13	19.140	0.453	0.435	0.758
PI3	28.14	20.543	0.453	0.506	0.755
PI5	28.39	22.169	0.342	0.350	0.769

After removing those measures, Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the cognitive inertia variable measures was $0.776 > 0.7$, indicating that the cognitive inertia variable measures have good internal consistency and reliability. The CITC values for each cognitive inertia variable measure ranged from $0.342 - 0.556$, all of which were more significant than 0.3 , and the “Cronbach's alpha coefficients if item deleted” were all less than 0.776 , and the scale stopped being purified. Thus, the cognitive inertia variable included nine measures, namely, LI124, EI356 and PI135.

5.3.5 Reliability Test for Innovation Performance

The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the innovation performance variable measures was $0.795 > 0.6$, indicating acceptable internal consistency and reliability of the innovation performance variable measures (see Tables 5-25 and 5-26).

Table 5-25, Reliability Statistics for Innovation Performance

Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.795	0.765	8

Table 5-26, Item-Total Statistics for Innovation Performance

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
IP1	24.13	15.088	0.743	0.581	0.726
IP2	24.32	16.337	0.637	0.490	0.748
IP3	24.24	15.247	0.705	0.627	0.734
IP4	24.23	16.936	0.760	0.663	0.734
IP5	24.31	23.059	-0.085	0.024	0.844
IP6	24.19	16.535	0.786	0.675	0.728

IP7	24.44	19.133	0.528	0.394	0.771
IP8	24.41	22.978	-0.060	0.024	0.834

However, the CITC of the IP5 and IP8 measures were -0.085 and -0.060, respectively, all of which were less than 0.3, so the measures were removed, as shown in Tables 5-27 and 5-28.

Table 5-27, Reliability Statistics for Innovation

Performance 2		
Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.891	0.896	6

Table 5-28, Item-Total Statistics for Innovation Performance 2

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
IP1	17.35	14.992	0.752	0.577	0.866
IP2	17.53	16.141	0.660	0.490	0.881
IP3	17.45	14.950	0.742	0.625	0.869
IP4	17.44	16.707	0.793	0.663	0.862
IP6	17.40	16.339	0.814	0.672	0.858
IP7	17.66	18.858	0.569	0.383	0.891

After removing two measures, Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the innovation performance variable measures was $0.891 > 0.7$, indicating that the innovation performance variable measures have good internal consistency and reliability. The CITC values for each innovation performance variable measure ranged from 0.569 – 0.793, all of which were greater than 0.3, and the “Cronbach's alpha coefficients if item deleted” were all less than 0.891, and the scale stopped being purified. Thus, the cognitive inertia variable included eight measures, namely, IP1-4 and IP6-7.

5.4 Exploratory Factor Analysis

After completing the CITC and reliability analysis of the research measures, exploratory factor analysis was used to purify the measures further. The sample was first subjected to a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) adequacy measure to determine whether factor analysis could be performed. Samples were suitable for factor analysis when $KMO > 0.5$ and Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant at less than 0.001. The factors were then refined using principal component analysis and orthogonal rotation of the factors using the maximum variance method. After the rotation, the factor loadings obtained from the factor matrix were used as the purification criteria, and those with factor loadings above 0.5 were retained. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted primarily to identify factor structure and purification scales. To ensure the validity of the EFA analysis, a sample size of at least five times the number of questionnaire items is generally required, following Gorsuch's (1983) recommendation of an average of five observations per measured variable and a total sample size of at least 100. The valid sample obtained for this study was 349, and the sample size ratio to the number of items measured in the open innovation model variable was 26.846, which is greater than the minimum requirement of 5. Therefore, the sample size meets the requirements for EFA analysis and can be used for EFA analysis.

The Open Innovation Model measurement scale does not fully cite other researchers' formally published scales, so it is constructed based on theory. At the same time, there are only two measures for acquiring and revealing strategies, which do not guarantee the reliability of the measurement of the variables. Therefore, exploratory factor analysis used principal component analysis to ensure good measurement validity. The method was as follows: a principal component analysis was first conducted on 349 samples, the items that did not contribute significantly to the principal component were removed, then factor analysis was conducted again, and the process was repeated until

the factor structure was stable. Finally, the principal components were named according to the content of the items constituting the principal components to form a new construct, and then validity analysis was conducted.

5.4.1 Factor Analysis Possibility Verification

The KMO and Bartlett tests were conducted on the Open Innovation Measure scale, and as seen in Table 5-29, the KMO = 0.783, which is greater than 0.4, and the Bartlett test of sphericity is significant at less than 0.001, and the scale is suitable for factor analysis.

Table 5-29, KMO and Bartlett's Test

KME Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.783
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1576.399
	df	45
	Sig.	0.000

5.4.2 Exploratory Factor Analysis Progress

Qiu (2010) states that regardless of the factor analysis model, at least three measured variables for each factor are the minimum criterion to obtain stable results. By extracting factors with eigenvalues greater than 1 through principal component analysis, three common factors were extracted from the ten measured items using the maximum variance method, which explained 71.638% of the total variance variation, greater than 50% (refer to Table 5-31). Moreover, the scree plot (Figure 1) also shows that the slope of the curve starts to become flat when the number of factors exceeds three. Thus, the three principal component factors have at least three measures, no cross-loading of the measures, and the factor structure is stable (See Table-30).

Figure 5-1, EFA Scree Plot

Table 5-30, Rotated Component Matrix^a

Variable	Component		
	1	2	3
Se4	0.846		
Se1	0.833		
Se2	0.829		
Se5			
So4		0.900	
So3		0.847	
So2		0.793	
Ac1			0.879
Ac2			0.878
Re1			0.744

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 5 iterations.

Table 5-31, Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.955	39.547	39.547	3.955	39.547	39.547	2.571	25.713	25.713
2	1.696	16.964	56.512	1.696	16.964	56.512	2.352	23.522	49.235
3	1.513	15.126	71.638	1.513	15.126	71.638	2.240	22.403	71.638
4	0.784	7.842	79.479						
5	0.495	4.950	84.429						
6	0.381	3.805	88.234						
7	0.368	3.683	91.917						
8	0.333	3.327	95.244						
9	0.269	2.689	97.933						
10	0.207	2.067	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

5.4.3 New Concepts Development

In the social sciences, the best results are achieved when the cumulative explained variance of the extracted public factor is at least 70% of the total variance. A public factor is considered reliable when it reaches 60% or more. A minimum of 50% or more is required (Wu, 2010). In factor analysis, the selection criterion for factor loadings should ideally be above 0.4, at which point the public factor can explain 16% of the measured variance (Wu, 2010). Following these two guidelines, three principal components could be explored for the open innovation measure, but the measure Se5 did not meet the criterion of a factor loading of more than 0.5, so the construction of a new concept was started after deleting the measure Se5 to ensure a stable factor structure. Based on the content of each component, component 1 was named “inside-out open innovation”, component 2 was named “outside-in open innovation”, and component 3 was named “coupled open innovation”. Thus, the open innovation models variable consists of three new concepts, and their measures are shown in Table 5-32.

Table 5-32, Measures for the New Concepts of Open Innovation Models

New Concepts	Measures	Details
Outside-in Open Innovation (OIOI)	So2	Enterprises have a robust system for sourcing external technology and intellectual property.
	So3	Enterprises proactively engage with external participants for better technological knowledge or products.
	So4	Enterprises build closer relationships with external participants and rely on their innovations.
Coupled Open Innovation (COI)	Ac1	Enterprises often purchase and utilise new technologies or intellectual property from other enterprises and institutions.
	Ac2	Enterprises outsource a high proportion of

		R&D.
	Re1	Enterprises may selectively reveal some intellectual property for further gains.
	Se1	Enterprises proactively manage the outflow of knowledge.
Inside-out Open Innovation (IOOI)	Se2	Enterprises sell technical knowledge and intellectual property in the marketplace formally.
	Se4	Enterprise welcomes other organisations and individuals to purchase and utilise the enterprise's technological knowledge or intellectual property.

5.4.4 Reliability Tests after Exploratory Factor Analysis

After EFA, while the Se5 measure needed to be removed, the open innovation models variable retained nine measures, consisting of three dimensions. At this point, Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the new open innovation models variable was $0.822 > 0.6$ (see Table 5-33). The CITC values for each new open innovation models variable measure ranged from 0.466 – 0.566, all greater than 0.3, and the “Cronbach's alpha coefficients if item deleted” were less than 0.811, less than 0.822 (see Table 5-34), indicating that the internal consistency and reliability of the new open innovation models variable measures were acceptable.

Table 5-33, Reliability Statistics for New OIM

Cronbach's Alpha		
Cronbach's Alpha	Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.822	0.828	9

Table 5-34, Item-Total Statistics for New OIM

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
So2	28.08	25.888	0.511	0.451	0.806
So3	28.00	25.376	0.523	0.599	0.805
So4	27.97	27.499	0.535	0.646	0.803
Ac1	27.74	27.810	0.523	0.591	0.805
Ac2	27.84	28.309	0.466	0.552	0.811
Re1	27.79	27.035	0.561	0.508	0.800
Se1	28.03	25.353	0.543	0.520	0.802
Se2	27.97	25.272	0.542	0.528	0.802
Se4	28.03	27.215	0.566	0.558	0.800

The reliability test results for all measures in this questionnaire are shown in Table 5-35.

Table 5-35, Reliability Statistics for All Variables

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Open Innovation Mode	0.822	9
Absorptive Capability	0.811	8
Dynamic Capabilities	0.831	13
Cognitive Inertia	0.776	9
Innovation Performance	0.891	6
Total	0.922	45

The reliability coefficient of the total scale is 0.87, which is greater than the recommended value of 0.7. The reliability coefficients of the remaining variables were all greater than 0.7, and the reliability coefficients of all variables met the standard, indicating that the questionnaire measurements had good internal consistency, were reliable and could be subjected to the next step of validity analysis.

5.5 Construct Validity Analysis

Construct validity is examined in terms of convergent and discriminant validity, and this paper will use AMOS 23.0 to achieve construct validity. Convergent validity is tested by using the fit of each construct in the latent variable to the measurement model alone. The C.R. value of the λ value of the constructs' measurement indicators should be greater than 1.96, the chi-squared freedom ratio less than 3, the RMSEA less than 0.08, the AGFI greater than 0.9, and the GFI greater than 0.9. If the above model fit criteria are met, the measurement model of a single construct can fit the sample data, and the convergent validity of the constructs is good (Wu, 2016). The AVE reflects the ratio of the amount of variance in the measure that the latent constructs can explain. A higher value indicates that the measure is a more valid reflection of the latent constructs. The construct has good convergent validity when the AVE value exceeds 0.5. Discriminant validity was measured using the Fronell-Larcker Criterion. The Fronell-Larcker criterion is considered one of the most common techniques used to examine the discriminant validity of the measurement model. Based on this standard, the square root of the mean variance extracted in one construct must be greater than the correlation between this and any other construct. Once this condition is satisfied, discriminant validity is established (Fronell & Larcker, 1981).

5.5.1 Construct Validity Test for Open Innovation Models

Open innovation models are classified as outside-in, coupled and inside-out open innovation models. The outside-in open innovation model includes the sourcing model, the inside-out open innovation model includes the selling model, and the coupled open innovation model includes a combination of acquiring and revealing models. The following validated factor analysis will be used to test the construct validity of the open innovation model variables. The model for testing the construct validity of the distinction between outside-in OI - coupled OI- inside-out OI is shown in Figure 5-2.

Figure 5-2, Construct Validity Analysis Model for OIM

As shown in Table 5-36, the SRMR is 0.097 larger than 0.05, CMIN/df is 4.252 larger than 3, RMSEA is 0.097 less than 0.08, and P is 0.000 less than 0.005, which is not a good fit. The GFI was 0.941 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.889 less than 0.9, the IFI was 0.948 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.948 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is more significant than 1.96. Overall, the OIM model does not fit well and needs further modification.

Table 5-36, Model Fit Summary for OIM

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
OIM	0.064	102.051	24	4.252	0.000	0.097
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.941	0.889	0.933	0.900	0.948	0.921	0.948
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
OIOI	0.615	0.087	7.086	***		
COI	0.501	0.055	9.133	***		
IOOI	0.822	0.101	8.133	***		
e1	0.639	0.056	11.307	***		
e2	0.444	0.054	8.181	***		

e3	0.131	0.028	4.649	***
e4	0.165	0.028	5.928	***
e5	0.225	0.027	8.18	***
e6	0.396	0.036	10.934	***
e7	0.502	0.055	9.103	***
e8	0.495	0.056	8.837	***
e9	0.227	0.03	7.708	***

As can be seen from Table 5-37, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-37, Factor Loadings for OIM

	Path		Estimate	AVE	C.R.
So2	<---	OIOI	0.700		
So3	<---	OIOI	0.824	0.662	0.853
So4	<---	OIOI	0.904		
Ac1	<---	COI	0.867		
Ac2	<---	COI	0.810	0.633	0.837
Re1	<---	COI	0.701		
Se1	<---	IOOI	0.788		
Se2	<---	IOOI	0.797	0.648	0.847
Se4	<---	IOOI	0.829		

As can be seen from Table 5-38, the absolute values of correlation coefficients of Outside-in OI, Coupled OI and Inside-out were 0.203, 0.048 and 0.044, less than 0.5 and less than the square root of the corresponding AVE, which means that the latent variables are correlated and have a certain degree of differentiation, indicating that the scale's validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-38, Discriminant Validity for OIM

	OIOI	COI	IOOI
OIOI	0.662		
COI	0.203***	0.633	

IOOI	0.048***	0.044***	0.648
AVE SQRT	0.814	0.796	0.805

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.001

level

Note. The element on the diagonal represents S.E.

In the OIM model, it is assumed that the error terms are not independent and that there may be some degree of relationship between the error terms of multiple measurement indicators. Based on the correction indicators (Table 5-39), the covariance relationships between the error terms of the measurement indicators are added one by one until the final model presented has no correction indicator value greater than 4.00. The final OIM correction model is shown in Figure 5-3.

Table 5-39, Modification Indices for OIM

	Path	M.I.
e6	<--> IOOI	52.928
e6	<--> OIOI	5.727
e6	<--> e8	9.363
e6	<--> e7	5.406
e5	<--> IOOI	6.691
e4	<--> IOOI	7.302
e4	<--> e8	4.533
e3	<--> e9	7.942
e3	<--> e6	5.842
e2	<--> e9	9.796
e2	<--> e5	5.242

Figure 5-3, Construct Validity Analysis Model for OIM after Modification

As shown in Table 5-40, the SRMR is 0.031 larger than 0.05, CMIN/df is 1.882 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.050 less than 0.08, and P is 0.006 larger than 0.005, which is a good fit. The GFI was 0.974 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.949 over 0.9, the IFI was 0.986 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.979 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is more significant than 1.96. Overall, the OIM model fits well.

Table 5-40, Model Fit Summary for OIM after Modification

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
OIM	0.031	43.297	23	1.882	0.006	0.050
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.974	0.949	0.972	0.956	0.986	0.979	0.986
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
OIOI	0.614	0.087	7.083	***		
COI	0.515	0.056	9.226	***		
IOOI	0.838	0.101	8.307	***		
e1	0.640	0.056	11.326	***		
e2	0.445	0.054	8.23	***		
e3	0.131	0.028	4.672	***		
e4	0.150	0.029	5.184	***		

e5	0.221	0.028	7.888	***
e6	0.422	0.038	11.247	***
e7	0.493	0.053	9.223	***
e8	0.478	0.054	8.871	***
e9	0.241	0.029	8.443	***

As can be seen from Table 5-41, the factor loadings for each path are all nearly greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-41, Factor Loadings for OIM after Modification

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
So2	<--- OIOI	0.700		
So3	<--- OIOI	0.824	0.663	0.854
So4	<--- OIOI	0.905		
Ac1	<--- COI	0.880		
Ac2	<--- COI	0.814	0.632	0.836
Re1	<--- COI	0.678		
Se1	<--- IOOI	0.794		
Se2	<--- IOOI	0.805	0.649	0.847
Se4	<--- IOOI	0.818		

As can be seen from Table 5-42, the absolute values of correlation coefficients of Outside-in OI, Coupled OI and Inside-out were 0.044, 0.047 and 0.039 than 0.5 and less than the square root of the corresponding AVE, which means that the latent variables are correlated and have a certain degree of differentiation, indicating that the scale's validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-42, Discriminant Validity for OIM after Modification

	OIOI	COI	IOOI
OIOI	0.663		
COI	0.044***	0.632	
IOOI	0.047***	0.039***	0.649

AVE SQRT	0.814	0.795	0.806
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***. Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level

Note. The element on the diagonal represents S.E.

5.5.2 Construct Validity Test for Absorptive Capability

Absorptive capability is classified as potential and realised absorptive capability models. The following validated factor analysis will be used to test the construct validity of the absorptive capability variables. The model for testing the construct validity of the distinction between potential and realised absorptive capability is shown in Figure 5-4.

Figure 5-3, Construct Validity Analysis Model for AC

As shown in Table 5-43, the SRMR is 0.232 larger than 0.05, CMIN/df is 24.950 larger than 3, RMSEA is 0.262 less than 0.08, and P is 0.000 less than 0.005, which is not a good fit. The GFI was 0.798 less than 0.9, the AGFI was 0.616 less than 0.9, the IFI was 0.685 less than 0.9, and the TLI was 0.533 less than 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the OIM model does not fit well and needs further modification.

Table 5-43, Model Fit Summary for AC

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
AC	0.232	474.055	19	24.950	0.000	0.262
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.798	0.616	0.676	0.523	0.685	0.533	0.683
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
PAC	0.495	0.495	0.495	***		
RAC	0.013	0.013	0.013	***		
e1	0.349	0.349	0.349	***		
e2	0.305	0.305	0.305	***		
e3	0.177	0.177	0.177	***		
e4	0.724	0.724	0.724	***		
e5	0.463	0.463	0.463	***		
e6	0.388	0.388	0.388	***		
e7	0.271	0.271	0.271	***		
e8	0.375	0.375	0.375	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-44, the factor loadings for each path are all nearly greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-44, Factor Loadings for AC

Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
PAC1 <--- PAC	0.766	0.522	0.790
PAC2 <--- PAC	0.864		
PAC4 <--- PAC	0.844		
PAC5 <--- PAC	0.206		
RAC1 <--- RAC	0.167	0.496	0.769
RAC2 <--- RAC	0.758		
RAC3 <--- RAC	0.858		
RAC4 <--- RAC	0.804		

Table 5-45 shows that the absolute value of correlation coefficients of potential and realised absorptive capability was 0.009, less than the square

root of the corresponding AVE, which means that the latent variables are correlated and have a certain degree of differentiation, indicating that the scale's validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-45, Discriminant Validity for AC

	PAC	RAC
PAC	0.522	
RAC	0.009	0.496
AVE SQRT	0.722	0.704

Note. The element on the diagonal represents S.E.

Based on the analysis results, the construct validity analysis model for AC after modification is shown in Figure 5-5.

Figure 5-4, Construct Validity Analysis Model for AC after Modification

As shown in Table 5-46, the SRMR is 0.017 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 0.936 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.000 less than 0.08, and P is 0.485 larger than 0.005, which is a good fit. The GFI was 0.992 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.981 over 0.9, the IFI was 1.001 over 0.9, and the TLI was 1.001 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is more significant than 1.96. Overall, the AC model fits well.

Table 5-46, Model Fit Summary for AC after Modification

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
OIM	0.017	7.486	8	0.936	0.485	0.000
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.992	0.981	0.992	0.986	1.001	1.001	1
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
PAC	0.496	0.062	7.989	***		
RAC	0.525	0.068	7.763	***		
e1	0.348	0.034	10.265	***		
e2	0.301	0.045	6.738	***		
e3	0.177	0.023	7.662	***		
e4	0.385	0.039	9.888	***		
e5	0.269	0.042	6.373	***		
e6	0.375	0.044	8.525	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-47, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-47, Factor Loadings for AC after Modification

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
PAC1	<--- PAC	0.766		
PAC2	<--- PAC	0.866	0.684	0.866
PAC4	<--- PAC	0.845		
RAC2	<--- RAC	0.759		
RAC3	<--- RAC	0.859	0.654	0.850
RAC4	<--- RAC	0.804		

Table 5-48 shows that the absolute values of correlation coefficients of potential and realised absorptive capability were 0.033, less than 0.5 and less than the square root of the corresponding AVE, which means that the latent variables are correlated and have a certain degree of differentiation, indicating that the scale's validity is satisfactory.

**Table 5-48, Discriminant
Validity for AC after
Modification**

	PAC	RAC
PAC	0.654	
RAC	0.033***	0.684
AVE SQRT	0.808	0.827

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level

Note. The element on the diagonal represents S.E.

5.5.3 Construct Validity Test for Dynamic Capabilities

The dynamic capabilities variable consists of three constructs: the ability to sense, capture and transform opportunities. The following hypothetical model of differential validity between the constructs was developed (as shown in Figure 5-6).

Figure 5-5, Construct Validity Analysis Model for DC

As shown in Table 5-49, the SRMR is 0.046 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 3.186 larger than 3, RMSEA is 0.079 less than 0.08, and P is 0.000 less than 0.005, which is not a good fit. The GFI was 0.924 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.888 less than 0.9, the IFI was 0.958 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.939 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the OIM model does not fit well and needs further modification.

Table 5-49, Model Fit Summary for DC

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
DC	0.046	197.562	62	3.186	0.000	0.079
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.924	0.888	0.932	0.914	0.952	0.939	0.952
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
ASO	0.846	0.092	9.214	***		
ACO	0.698	0.080	8.770	***		

ATO	0.988	0.110	9.020	***
e1	0.395	0.037	10.686	***
e2	0.267	0.028	9.612	***
e3	0.188	0.021	9.070	***
e4	0.213	0.022	9.693	***
e5	0.348	0.038	9.159	***
e6	0.413	0.043	9.682	***
e7	0.559	0.052	10.742	***
e8	0.268	0.028	9.525	***
e9	0.485	0.047	10.278	***
e10	0.546	0.050	11.000	***
e11	0.426	0.036	11.774	***
e12	0.502	0.054	9.296	***
e13	0.510	0.051	10.042	***

As can be seen from Table 5-50, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-50, Factor Loadings for DC

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
ASO1	<--- ASO	0.825		
ASO2	<--- ASO	0.867	0.7387	0.9187
ASO3	<--- ASO	0.881		
ASO4	<--- ASO	0.864		
ACO1	<--- ACO	0.817		
ACO2	<--- ACO	0.798	0.6261	0.8699
ACO3	<--- ACO	0.744		
ACO4	<--- ACO	0.804		
ATO1	<--- ATO	0.819		
ATO2	<--- ATO	0.779	0.6394	0.8983
ATO3	<--- ATO	0.708		
ATO4	<--- ATO	0.855		
ATO5	<--- ATO	0.829		

As seen from Table 5-51, the absolute values of correlation coefficients of ASO, ACO and ATO were 0.049, 0.055 and 0.051, less than 0.5 and less than the square root of the corresponding AVE, which means that the latent variables are correlated and have a certain degree of differentiation, indicating that the scale's validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-51, Discriminant Validity

	ASO	ACO	ATO
ASO	0.739		
ACO	0.049***	0.626	
ATO	0.055**	0.051	0.6394
AVE SQRT	0.859	0.791	0.800

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.005 level

*** . Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level

Note. The element on the diagonal represents S.E.

In the DC model, it is assumed that the error terms are not independent and that there may be some degree of relationship between the error terms of multiple measurement indicators. Based on the correction indicators (Table 5-52), the covariance relationships between the error terms of the measurement indicators are added one by one until the final model presented has no correction indicator value greater than 4.00. The final DC correction model is shown in Figure 5-7.

Table 5-52, Modification Indices for DC

	Path	M.I.
e11	<--> e13	16.992
e10	<--> e11	27.763
e9	<--> e13	8.520
e9	<--> e11	4.238
e9	<--> e10	4.120
e8	<--> ATO	18.438
e8	<--> e11	4.992
e8	<--> e9	10.997
e7	<--> e8	5.931

e6	<-->	ATO	10.956
e6	<-->	ASO	4.066
e6	<-->	e9	5.948
e6	<-->	e7	12.192
e5	<-->	ATO	4.745
e5	<-->	e8	7.545
e5	<-->	e6	4.248
e4	<-->	e13	4.013
e4	<-->	e11	5.445
e4	<-->	e7	4.851
e3	<-->	ATO	7.237
e3	<-->	e9	5.930
e3	<-->	e5	7.063
e2	<-->	ATO	4.086
e2	<-->	e9	4.141

Figure 5-6, Construct Validity Analysis Model for DC after Modification

As shown in Table 5-53, the SRMR is 0.035 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 1.895 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.051 less than 0.08, and P is 0.000 less than 0.005, which is a good fit considering the complexity of this model. The GFI was 0.956 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.930 over 0.9, the IFI was 0.982 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.975 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is more significant than 1.96. Overall, the DC model fits well.

Table 5-53, Model Fit Summary for DC after Modification

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
DC	0.035	109.909	58	1.895	0.000	0.051
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.956	0.930	0.962	0.949	0.982	0.975	0.982
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
ASO	0.846	0.092	9.218	***		
ACO	0.658	0.078	8.490	***		
ATO	1.018	0.110	9.241	***		
e1	0.395	0.037	10.683	***		
e2	0.267	0.028	9.609	***		
e3	0.187	0.021	9.057	***		
e4	0.214	0.022	9.720	***		
e5	0.387	0.038	10.157	***		
e6	0.304	0.045	6.735	***		
e7	0.462	0.055	8.384	***		
e8	0.297	0.028	10.454	***		
e9	0.456	0.045	10.049	***		
e10	0.478	0.047	10.139	***		
e11	0.427	0.040	10.809	***		
e12	0.524	0.055	9.534	***		
e13	0.584	0.057	10.331	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-54, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-54, Factor Loadings for DC after Modification

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
ASO1	<--- ASO	0.826		
ASO2	<--- ASO	0.867	0.739	0.919
ASO3	<--- ASO	0.881		
ASO4	<--- ASO	0.863		
ACO1	<--- ACO	0.794		
ACO2	<--- ACO	0.856	0.651	0.881
ACO3	<--- ACO	0.794		
ACO4	<--- ACO	0.780		
ATO1	<--- ATO	0.831		
ATO2	<--- ATO	0.810		
ATO3	<--- ATO	0.708	0.642	0.899
ATO4	<--- ATO	0.848		
ATO5	<--- ATO	0.801		

Table 5-55 shows that the absolute values of correlation coefficients of ASO, ACO and ATO were 0.46, 0.055 and 0.48, less than 0.5 and less than the square root of the corresponding AVE, which means that the latent variables are correlated and have a certain degree of differentiation, indicating that the scale's validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-55, Discriminant Validity for DC after Modification

	ASO	ACO	ATO
ASO	0.739		
ACO	0.46***	0.651	
ATO	0.055**	0.48	0.642
AVE SQRT	0.859	0.807	0.801

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

*** . Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level

Note. The element on the diagonal represents S.E.

Construct Validity Test for ASO

As each of the three latent constructs of the dynamic capabilities variable has greater than three measures, construct validity tests will be conducted for each of the three constructs individually, starting with a single construct measurement model for the ASO construct (as shown in Figure 5-8).

Figure 5-8, Construct Validity Analysis Model for ASO

As shown in Table 5-56, the SRMR is 0.013 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 2.700 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.070 less than 0.08, and P is 0.067 larger than 0.005, which is a good fit considering the complexity of this model. The GFI was 0.992 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.962 over 0.9, the IFI was 0.997 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.990 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is more significant than 1.96. Overall, the ASO model fits well.

Table 5-56, Model Fit Summary for ASO

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
ASO	0.013	5.400	2	2.700	0.067	0.070
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.992	0.962	0.995	0.984	0.997	0.990	0.997
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
ASO	0.841	0.092	9.170	***		
e1	0.400	0.037	10.710	***		
e2	0.265	0.028	9.542	***		
e3	0.190	0.021	9.096	***		
e4	0.209	0.022	9.570	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-57, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-57, Factor Loadings for ASO

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
ASO1	<--- ASO	0.823		
ASO2	<--- ASO	0.868	0.739	0.919
ASO3	<--- ASO	0.879		
ASO4	<--- ASO	0.867		

In the case of a single construct variable, traditional discriminant validity testing, which compares correlation coefficients between different constructs, cannot be conducted. However, there are alternative ways to assess the validity of a single construct variable. One method is to evaluate the construct's validity through internal consistency. Composite Reliability can be used to assess the internal consistency of the variable. Table 5-57 shows that the C.R. was 0.919, more significant than 0.7, and considered good discriminant validity in the ASO model.

Construct Validity Test for ACO

The single construct measurement for the ACO construct is shown in Figure 5-9.

Figure 5-9, Construct Validity Analysis Model for ACO

As shown in Table 5-58, the SRMR is 0.030 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 11.574 larger than 3, RMSEA is 0.174 larger than 0.08, and P is 0.000 less than 0.005, which is not a good fit. The GFI was 0.971 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.854 less than 0.9, the IFI was 0.969 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.907 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the ACO model does not fit well and needs further modification.

Table 5-58, Model Fit Summary for ACO

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
ACO	0.030	23.147	2	11.574	0.000	0.174
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.971	0.854	0.966	0.899	0.969	0.907	0.969
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
ACO	0.702	0.080	8.793	***		
e1	0.344	0.038	9.031	***		
e2	0.416	0.043	9.673	***		
e3	0.556	0.052	10.691	***		
e4	0.270	0.028	9.521	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-59, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-59, Factor Loadings for ASO

Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
ASO1 <--- ASO	0.823		
ASO2 <--- ASO	0.868	0.7388	0.9187
ASO3 <--- ASO	0.879		
ASO4 <--- ASO	0.867		

The ACO model assumes that the error terms are not independent and that there may be some degree of relationship between the error terms of multiple

measurement indicators. Based on the correction indicators (Table 5-60), the covariance relationships between the error terms of the measurement indicators are added one by one until the final model presented has no correction indicator value greater than 4.00. The final ACO correction model is shown in Figure 5-10.

Table 5-60, Modification Indices for ACO

	Path	M.I.
e3	<--> e4	6.031
e2	<--> e3	12.075
e1	<--> e4	7.761
e1	<--> e2	4.14

Figure 5-10, Construct Validity Analysis Model for ASO after Modification

As shown in Table 5-61, the SRMR is 0.007 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 0.999 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.000 less than 0.08, and P is 0.317 larger than 0.005, which is a good fit. The GFI was 0.999 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.986 less than 0.9, the IFI was 1.000 over 0.9, and the TLI was 1.000 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the ACO model fits well.

Table 5-61, Model Fit Summary for ACO after Modification

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
ACO	0.007	0.999	1	0.999	0.317	0.000
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.999	0.986	0.999	0.991	1.000	1.000	1.000
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
ACO	0.655	0.078	8.413	***		

e1	0.391	0.039	10.002	***
e2	0.316	0.047	6.661	***
e3	0.438	0.056	7.864	***
e4	0.298	0.029	10.325	***

As can be seen from Table 5-62, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-62, Factor Loadings for ACO after Modification

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
ACO1	<--- ACO	0.791		
ACO2	<--- ACO	0.850	0.651	0.882
ACO3	<--- ACO	0.806		
ACO4	<--- ACO	0.779		

In the case of a single construct variable, traditional discriminant validity testing, which compares correlation coefficients between different constructs, cannot be conducted. However, there are alternative ways to assess the validity of a single construct variable. One method is to evaluate the construct's validity through internal consistency. Composite Reliability can be used to assess the internal consistency of the variable. Table 5-62 shows that the C.R. was 0.882, more significant than 0.7, and considered good discriminant validity in the ACO model.

Construct Validity Test for ATO

The single construct measurement for the ATO construct is shown in Figure 5-11.

Figure 5-11, Construct Validity Analysis Model for ATO

As shown in Table 5-63, the SRMR is 0.039 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 11.283 larger than 3, RMSEA is 0.172 larger than 0.08, and P is 0.000 less than 0.005, which is not a good fit. The GFI was 0.946 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.838 less than 0.9, the IFI was 0.951 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.901 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the ATO model does not fit well and needs further modification.

Table 5-63, Model Fit Summary for ATO

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
ATO	0.039	56.416	5	11.283	0.000	0.172
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.946	0.838	0.946	0.893	0.951	0.901	0.951
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
ATO	0.989	0.110	9.027	***		
e1	0.484	0.047	10.248	***		
e2	0.544	0.050	10.970	***		
e3	0.426	0.036	11.767	***		
e4	0.506	0.054	9.319	***		
e5	0.510	0.051	10.024	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-64, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is

more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-64, Factor Loadings for ATO

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
ATO1	<--- ATO	0.819		
ATO2	<--- ATO	0.780		
ATO3	<--- ATO	0.708	0.639	0.898
ATO4	<--- ATO	0.854		
ATO5	<--- ATO	0.829		

The ATO model assumes that the error terms are not independent and that there may be some degree of relationship between the error terms of multiple measurement indicators. Based on the correction indicators (Table 5-65), the covariance relationships between the error terms of the measurement indicators are added one by one until the final model presented has no correction indicator value greater than 4.00. The final ATO correction model is shown in Figure 5-12.

Table 5-65, Modification Indices for ATO

	Path	M.I.
e3	<--> e5	17.05
e2	<--> e3	28.327
e1	<--> e5	8.783
e1	<--> e3	4.189

Figure 5-12, Construct Validity Analysis Model for ATO after Modification

As shown in Table 5-66, the SRMR is 0.009 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 1.658 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.043 less than 0.08, and P is 0.191 larger than 0.005, which is a good fit. The GFI was 0.996 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.971 less than 0.9, the IFI was 0.999 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.994 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the ATO model fits well.

Table 5-66, Factor Loadings for ATO after Modification

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
ATO	0.009	3.316	2	1.658	0.191	0.043
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.996	0.971	0.997	0.984	0.999	0.994	0.999
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
ATO	1.045	0.112	9.324	***		
e1	0.428	0.047	9.146	***		
e2	0.501	0.048	10.485	***		
e3	0.416	0.039	10.691	***		
e4	0.547	0.055	9.891	***		
e5	0.515	0.061	8.469	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-67, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-67, Factor Loadings for ATP after Modification

Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
ATO1 <--- ATO	0.842		
ATO2 <--- ATO	0.799		
ATO3 <--- ATO	0.716	0.650	0.903
ATO4 <--- ATO	0.841		
ATO5 <--- ATO	0.827		

In the case of a single construct variable, traditional discriminant validity testing, which compares correlation coefficients between different constructs,

cannot be conducted. However, there are alternative ways to assess the validity of a single construct variable. One method is to evaluate the construct's validity through internal consistency. Composite Reliability can be used to assess the internal consistency of the variable. Table 5-67 shows that the C.R. was 0.903, more significant than 0.7, and considered good discriminant validity in the ATO model.

5.5.4 Construct Validity Test for Cognitive Inertia

The cognitive inertia variable consists of three constructs: learning, experience and procedural inertia. The following hypothetical model of differential validity between the constructs was developed (as shown in Figure 5-13).

Figure 5-13, Construct Validity Analysis Model for CI

Table 5-68 shows that the SRMR is 0.039 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 1.560 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.050 less than 0.08, and P is 0.040 larger than 0.005, which is a good fit. The GFI was 0.977 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.957 less than

0.9, the IFI was 0.986 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.979 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the CI model fits well.

Table 5-68, Model Fit Summary for CI

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
CI	0.039	37.441	24	1.560	0.040	0.040
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.977	0.957	0.962	0.943	0.986	0.979	0.986
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
LI	0.421	0.066	6.397	***		
EI	0.633	0.085	7.446	***		
PI	0.668	0.099	6.773	***		
e1	0.468	0.048	9.739	***		
e2	0.330	0.047	6.956	***		
e3	0.515	0.055	9.368	***		
e4	0.406	0.054	7.517	***		
e5	0.281	0.033	8.550	***		
e6	0.402	0.037	10.924	***		
e7	0.646	0.068	9.525	***		
e8	0.194	0.044	4.440	***		
e9	0.300	0.028	10.854	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-69, the factor loadings for each path are nearly all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is reasonably representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is approaching 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is fair.

Table 5-69, Factor Loadings for CI

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
LI1	<--- LI	0.688		
LI2	<--- LI	0.789	0.531	0.772
LI4	<--- LI	0.705		
EI3	<--- EI	0.781		
EI5	<--- EI	0.745	0.519	0.762
EI6	<--- EI	0.626		
PI1	<--- PI	0.713	0.562	0.791

PI3	<---	PI	0.870
PI5	<---	PI	0.648

As seen from Table 5-70, the absolute values of correlation coefficients of LI, EI and PI were 0.043, 0.036 and 0.051, less than 0.5 and less than the square root of the corresponding AVE, which means that the latent variables are correlated and have a certain degree of differentiation, indicating that the scale's validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-70, Discriminant Validity for CI

	LI	EI	PI
LI	0.531		
EI	0.043***	0.519	
PI	0.036	0.051***	0.562
AVE SQRT	0.729	0.720	0.749

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level

Note. The element on the diagonal represents S.E.

5.5.5 Construct Validity Test for Innovation Performance

The single construct measurement for the innovation performance variable construct is shown in Figure 5-14.

Figure 5-14, Construct Validity Analysis Model for IP

As shown in Table 5-71, the SRMR is 0.035 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 7.085 larger than 3, RMSEA is 0.132 larger than 0.08, and P is 0.000 less than 0.005, which is not a good fit. The GFI was 0.945 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.872 less than 0.9, the IFI was 0.913 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.955 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the IP model does not fit well and needs further modification.

Table 5-71, Model Fit Summary for IP

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
IP	0.035	63.767	9	7.085	0.000	0.132
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.945	0.872	0.948	0.913	0.955	0.925	0.955
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
IP	0.833	0.096	8.66	***		
e1	0.486	0.044	10.946	***		
e2	0.573	0.048	11.87	***		
e3	0.475	0.044	10.74	***		
e4	0.218	0.022	10.065	***		
e6	0.213	0.022	9.589	***		
e7	0.332	0.027	12.405	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-72, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-72, Factor Loadings for IP

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
IP1	<--- IP	0.795		
IP2	<--- IP	0.710		
IP3	<--- IP	0.807	0.600	0.899
IP4	<--- IP	0.839		
IP6	<--- IP	0.856		
IP7	<--- IP	0.615		

The IP model assumes that the error terms are not independent and that there may be some degree of relationship between the error terms of multiple measurement indicators. Based on the correction indicators (Table 5-73), the covariance relationships between the error terms of the measurement indicators are added one by one until the final model presented has no correction indicator value greater than 4.00. The final CI correction model is shown in Figure 5-15.

Table 5-73, Modification Indices for CI

	Path	M.I.
e5	<--> e6	18.741
e4	<--> e5	5.416
e3	<--> e4	22.039
e2	<--> e3	11.147
e1	<--> e4	6.046

Figure 5-15, Construct Validity Analysis Model for IP after Modification

As shown in Table 5-74, the SRMR is 0.014 less than 0.05, CMIN/df is 1.392 less than 3, RMSEA is 0.034 less than 0.08, and P is 0.213 larger than 0.005, which is a good fit. The GFI was 0.992 over 0.9, the AGFI was 0.973 larger than 0.9, the IFI was 0.998 over 0.9, and the TLI was 0.995 over 0.9. The C.R. of all measures is not greater than 1.96. Overall, the IP model fits well.

Table 5-74, Model Fit Summary for IP after Modification

Model	SRMR	CMIN	df	CMIN/df	P	RMSEA
IP	0.014	8.351	6	1.392	0.213	0.034
GFI	AGFI	NFI	RFI	IFI	TLI	CFI
0.992	0.973	0.993	0.983	0.998	0.995	0.998
	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P		
IP	0.856	0.098	8.76	***		
e1	0.463	0.045	10.329	***		
e2	0.516	0.047	10.964	***		
e3	0.505	0.054	9.264	***		
e4	0.252	0.026	9.688	***		
e6	0.224	0.025	9.033	***		
e7	0.358	0.029	12.225	***		

As can be seen from Table 5-75, the factor loadings for each path are all greater than 0.7, indicating that each latent variable is highly representative of the topic to which it belongs. In addition, the AVE of each latent variable is

more significant than 0.5, and the C.R. is more significant than 0.8, indicating that the convergent validity is satisfactory.

Table 5-75, Factor Loadings for IP after Modification

	Path	Estimate	AVE	C.R.
IP1	<--- IP	0.805		
IP2	<--- IP	0.745		
IP3	<--- IP	0.794	0.590	0.895
IP4	<--- IP	0.811		
IP6	<--- IP	0.848		
IP7	<--- IP	0.575		

In the case of a single construct variable, traditional discriminant validity testing, which compares correlation coefficients between different constructs, cannot be conducted. However, there are alternative ways to assess the validity of a single construct variable. One method is to evaluate the construct's validity through internal consistency. Composite Reliability can be used to assess the internal consistency of the variable. Table 5-66 shows that the C.R. was 0.895, more significant than 0.7, and considered good discriminant validity in the IP model.

5.6 Summary of Data Analysis

This chapter presents the data analysis for each measure inside the variables of open innovation models, absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities, cognitive inertia and innovation performance, including the descriptive statistics analysis, homogeneous bias tests, reliability and validity test. Furthermore, the above data analysis results laid the foundation for the next chapter, which analyses the relationship between each variable.

Chapter 6. Research Hypotheses Tests

This chapter empirically tests the mechanism by which various hypotheses of open innovation models of technology-based SMEs impact innovation performance developed in Chapter Three, based on the pre-processing questionnaire data from 349 technology-based SMEs in Chapter Five. Firstly, the direct impact of outside-in, coupled and inside-out open innovation models on innovation performance will be examined. Secondly, the mediating impact of absorptive and dynamic capabilities in the relationship between open innovation and innovation performance is examined. Thirdly, the moderating effect of three types of cognitive inertia on the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance is examined. Finally, the results of the hypotheses tests are summarised and analysed.

6.1 The Direct Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

This study constructed a PLS structural equation model of "Open Innovation Models - Innovation Performance" to verify the direct impact between the two via SmartPLS 4. The independent variables are outside-in OI, coupled OI and inside-out OI, and the dependent variable is innovation performance, which is used to test the availability of each reflective indicator for each latent variable.

6.1.1 Outside-in Open Innovation Model – Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H1a (Adopting an outside-in open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs), the construction of the Outside-in OI and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-1.

Figure 6-1, Path Model of the Impact of OIOI on IP (Model 1)

Table 6-1 shows that the SRMR (standardised root mean residual) measures the fit between the observed data and the model, with lower values indicating a better fit. In this path model, the SRMR value of 0.061 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} (degree of freedom for the unweighted least squares estimator) measures model degrees of freedom, representing the number of parameters freely estimated in the model. Here, 0.166 indicates a moderate degree of freedom in this path model. Similarly, the d_G (degree of freedom for the generalised least squares estimator) is another measure of model degrees of freedom. The value of 0.086 indicates a moderate degree of freedom in the path model. The Chi-square statistic evaluates the fit between the model and the observed data. In this path model, the Chi-square value is 178.718, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI (normal fit index) is used to evaluate the model fit, with values closer to one indicating a better fit. Here, the NFI value of 0.9 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-1, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.183, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on IP is 18.3%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-1, Model Fit for Model 1

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.061	0.061
d_ULS	0.166	0.166
d_G	0.086	0.086
Chi-square	178.718	178.718
NFI	0.9	0.9

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-2, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all more significant than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-2, Convergent Validity for Model 1

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.806			
So3	0.895			
So4	0.918			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.846			
IP2	0.759			
IP3	0.831			
IP4	0.851			
IP6	0.888			
IP7	0.688			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-3 shows that the path correlation coefficient between the two latent variables was 0.428, less than the SQRT (AVE) of the two latent variables (0.814 and 0.874), indicating good discriminant validity in model 1, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-3, Discriminant Validity for Model 1

	IP	OIOI
IP	0.814	
OIOI	0.428	0.874

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-4 shows that the path coefficient 0.428 indicates a positive relationship between the OIOI and IP. The T statistic of 8.645, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of OIOI on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that adopting an outside-in open innovation model directly and significantly positively impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Hypothesis H1a is fully supported by model 1.

Table 6-4, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 1

Path	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	
OIOI -> IP	0.428	0.432	0.05	8.645	0.000

6.1.2 Inside-out Open Innovation Model - Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H1b (Adopting an inside-out open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs), the

construction of the Inside-out OI and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-2.

Figure 6-2, Path Model of the Impact of IOOI on IP (Model 2)

Table 6-5 shows that the SRMR value of 0.059 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.154 and 0.090, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 188.058, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.891 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-2, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.094, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on IP is 9.4%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-5, Model Fit for Model 2

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.059	0.059
d_{ULS}	0.154	0.154
d_G	0.090	0.090
Chi-square	188.058	188.058
NFI	0.891	0.891

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-6, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-6, Convergent Validity for Model 2

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.764
Se1	0.867			
Se2	0.863			
Se4	0.893			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.661
IP1	0.852			
IP2	0.752			
IP3	0.839			
IP4	0.854			
IP6	0.891			
IP7	0.668			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-7 shows that the path correlation coefficient between the two latent variables was 0.306, less than the SQRT (AVE) of the two latent variables (0.874 and 0.813), indicating good discriminant validity in model 2, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-7, Discriminant Validity for Model 2

	IOOI	IP
IOOI	0.874	
IP	0.306	0.813

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-8 shows that the path coefficient 0.306 indicates a positive relationship between the IOOI and IP. The T statistic of 4.451, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of IOOI on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that adopting an inside-out open innovation model directly and significantly positively impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Hypothesis H1b is fully supported by model 2.

Table 6-8, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 2

Path	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	
IOOI -> IP	0.306	0.312	0.069	4.451	0.000

6.1.3 Coupled Open Innovation Model – Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H1c (Adopting a coupled open innovation model directly impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs), the construction of the Coupled OI and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-3.

Figure 6-3, Path Model of the Impact of COI on IP (Model 3)

Table 6-9 shows that the SRMR value of 0.062 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.173 and 0.088, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 184.261, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.894 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-3, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.187, indicating the explanatory power of COI on IP is 18.7%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-9, Model Fit for Model 3

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.062	0.062
d_{ULS}	0.173	0.173
d_G	0.088	0.088
Chi-square	184.261	184.261
NFI	0.894	0.894

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-10, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-10, Convergent Validity for Model 3

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
COI		0.832	0.898	0.747
Ac1	0.908			
Ac2	0.898			
Re1	0.780			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.840			
IP2	0.771			
IP3	0.837			
IP4	0.864			
IP6	0.881			
IP7	0.670			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-11 shows that the path correlation coefficient between the two latent variables was 0.433, less than the SQRT (AVE) of the two latent variables (0.864 and 0.814), indicating good discriminant validity in model 3, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-11, Discriminant Validity for Model 3

COI	IP

COI	0.864	
IP	0.433	0.814

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-12 shows that the path coefficient 0.433 indicates a positive relationship between the IOOI and IP. The T statistic of 9.183, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of COI on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that adopting a coupled open innovation model directly and significantly positively impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Hypothesis H1c is fully supported by model 3.

Table 6-12, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 3

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
COI -> IP	0.433	0.437	0.047	9.183	0.000

6.1.4 Three Open Innovation Models – Innovation Performance

Models 1, 2 and 3 were combined to test the combined effect of the three open innovation models on innovation performance, as shown in Figure 6-4.

Figure 6-4, Path Model of the Impact of Three OIM on IP (Model 4)

Table 6-13 shows that the SRMR value of 0.063 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.470 and 0.215, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 454.950, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.845 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-4, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.288, indicating the explanatory power of OIM on IP is 28.8%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-13, Model Fit for Model 4

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.063	0.063
d_{ULS}	0.47	0.47
d_G	0.215	0.215

Chi-square	454.95	454.95
NFI	0.845	0.845

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-14, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the four latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-14, Convergent Validity for Model 4

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.806			
So3	0.896			
So4	0.918			
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.764
Se1	0.867			
Se2	0.863			
Se4	0.893			
COI		0.832	0.898	0.747
Ac1	0.908			
Ac2	0.897			
Re1	0.781			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.844			
IP2	0.764			
IP3	0.835			
IP4	0.858			
IP6	0.885			
IP7	0.678			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-15 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the four latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 4, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-15, Discriminant Validity for Model 4

	COI	IOOI	IP	OIOI
COI	0.864			
IOOI	0.349	0.874		
IP	0.432	0.302	0.814	
OIOI	0.329	0.291	0.427	0.874

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-16 shows that the path coefficient 0.297 indicates a positive relationship between the OIOI and IP, 0.112 indicates a positive relationship between the IOOI and IP, and 0.295 indicates a positive relationship between the COI and IP. The T statistic of 6.000, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of OIOI on IP is statistically significant. The T statistic of 5.642, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of COI on IP is statistically significant. The T statistic of 1.652, with a corresponding p-value of 0.099, suggests that the impact of IOOI on IP is not statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that the outside-in and coupled open innovation models can positively and significantly impact innovation performance when considering the three open innovation models. In contrast, the inside-out open innovation model can positively but not significantly impact innovation performance.

Table 6-16, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 4

Path Coefficient	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values

		(M)	(STDEV)		
OIOI ->	0.297	0.299	0.050	6.000	0.000
IP					
IOOI ->	0.112	0.114	0.068	1.652	0.099
IP					
COI ->	0.295	0.296	0.052	5.642	0.000
IP					

6.2 The Mediating Role of Absorptive Capability in the Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

6.2.1 Approach for Mediating Impact Tests

Baron & Kenny (1986) proposed the classical method of testing for mediating effects of variables, but this test is subject to measurement error in regression testing (Bollen, 1989). Furthermore, it is not a necessary condition for the existence of a mediating effect that X significantly affects Y (Shrout & Bolger, 2002). The key to testing for mediating effects is to test for the significance of indirect effects, and most studies have relied on the indirect effects test proposed by Sobel (1982) to test for significance. However, the Sobel Test requires that the product of the mediating and independent variables meet a normal distribution, so it does not apply to the PLS method. If the sample is small, the Sobel Z-Test lacks statistical power (Jr, 2013). In this paper, the PLS method is used to test the mediating effect of absorptive and dynamic capabilities, and the mediating effect test procedure proposed by (Zhao et al., 2010) is used, as shown in Figures 6-5 below.

Figure 6-5 Process for Testing the Mediating Effect of Latent Variables

1) Test whether the mediating effect $a \times b$ is significant. If significant, it means there is a mediating effect. If not, it means there is no mediating effect.

2) Provided the $a \times b$ test is significant, test whether the direct effect c is significant. If not significant, this indicates a fully mediated effect and the mediating variable is confirmed to be consistent with the assumptions of the theoretical model. If significant, check whether $a \times b \times c$ is positive. If $a \times b \times c$ is positive, then there is a complementary mediating effect. Otherwise, there is a competitive mediating effect, indicating an incomplete theoretical model with the mediating variable confirmed as hypothesised and a partial mediating effect.

3) Given that the $a \times b$ test is insignificant, whether the direct effect c is significant. If significant, it means that there is only a direct effect between the independent and dependent variables, there is no mediating effect, and the theoretical model is faulty. If not, it means there is no effect between the

independent and dependent variables, no mediating effect, and the theoretical model is incorrect.

6.2.2 Open Innovation Models - Absorptive Capability

Based on hypotheses H2a (Adopting an outside-in open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs), H2b (Adopting an inside-out open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs) and H2c (Adopting a coupled open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs), the construction of the open innovation models and innovation performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-6.

Figure 6-6, Path Model of the Impact of OIM on AC (Model 5)

Table 6-17 shows that the SRMR value of 0.110 suggests a relatively poorer fit for the model. The d_ULS and d_G are 1.451 and 0.425, indicating a higher degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 941.428, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.649 suggests a relatively poorer fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-6, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.303, indicating the explanatory power of OIM on AC is 30.3%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial absorptive capability. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-17, Model Fit for Model 5

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.110	0.110
d_ULS	1.451	1.451
d_G	0.425	0.425
Chi-square	941.428	941.428
NFI	0.649	0.649

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-18, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the four latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were not all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was not more than 50%.

Table 6-18, Convergent Validity for Model 5

Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
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OIOI		0.846	0.847	0.765
So2	0.831			
So3	0.879			
So4	0.912			
COI		0.832	0.872	0.747
Ac1	0.916			
Ac2	0.880			
Re1	0.792			
IOOI		0.846	0.849	0.764
Se1	0.866			
Se2	0.881			
Se4	0.876			
AC		0.770	0.774	0.466
PAC1	0.681			
PAC2	0.733			
PAC4	0.731			
RAC2	0.622			
RAC3	0.647			
RAC4	0.675			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-19 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the four latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 5, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-19, Discriminant Validity for Model 5

	AC	COI	IOOI	OIOI
AC	0.683			
COI	0.432	0.864		
IOOI	0.391	0.356	0.874	
OIOI	0.401	0.331	0.294	0.875

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-20 shows that the path coefficient 0.246 indicates a positive relationship between the OIOI and AC, 0.222 indicates a positive relationship between the IOOI and AC, and 0.271 indicates a positive relationship between the COI and AC. The T statistic of 5.253, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of OIOI on AC is statistically significant. The T statistic of 3.552, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of IOOI on AC is statistically significant. The T statistic of 5.236, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of COI on AC is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that the three open innovation models can positively and significantly impact absorptive capability. However, due to the model's poor fit, model 5 needs modification, and the new model is shown in Figure 6-7.

Table 6-20, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 5

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
OIOI -> AC	0.246	0.248	0.047	5.253	0.000
COI -> AC	0.271	0.274	0.052	5.236	0.000
IOOI -> AC	0.222	0.226	0.063	3.552	0.000

Figure 6-7, Path Model of the Impact of OIM on AC (Model 5) after Modification

Table 6-21 shows that the SRMR value of 0.079 suggests a relatively good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.564 and 0.197, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 406.793, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.815 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-7, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.267, indicating the explanatory power of OIM on AC is 26.7%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-21, Model Fit for Model 5 after Modification

Saturated Model	Estimated Model
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SRMR	0.079	0.079
d_ULS	0.564	0.564
d_G	0.197	0.197
Chi-square	406.793	406.793
NFI	0.815	0.815

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-22, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the four latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-22, Convergent Validity for Model 5 after Modification

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.827			
So3	0.883			
So4	0.913			
COI		0.832	0.899	0.748
Ac1	0.913			
Ac2	0.881			
Re1	0.796			
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.764
Se1	0.867			
Se2	0.882			
Se4	0.873			
AC		0.752	0.85	0.595
PAC1	0.818			

PAC2	0.851
PAC4	0.859
RAC4	0.501

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-23 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the four latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 5, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

**Table 6-23, Discriminant Validity for Model 5
after Modification**

	AC	COI	IOOI	OIOI
AC	0.772			
COI	0.405	0.865		
IOOI	0.363	0.357	0.874	
OIOI	0.381	0.331	0.294	0.875

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-24 shows that the path coefficient 0.238 indicates a positive relationship between the OIOI and AC, 0.202 indicates a positive relationship between the IOOI and AC, and 0.254 indicates a positive relationship between the COI and AC. The T statistic of 5.178, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of OIOI on AC is statistically significant. The T statistic of 3.037, with a corresponding p-value of 0.002, suggests that the impact of IOOI on AC is statistically significant. The T statistic of 4.949, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of COI on AC is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that adopting each outside-in, inside-out and coupled open innovation model can positively and significantly impact the construction or renewal of absorptive capability in technology-based SMEs based on Model 5.

Table 6-24, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 5

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
OIOI -> AC	0.238	0.239	0.046	5.178	0.000
COI -> AC	0.254	0.257	0.051	4.949	0.000
IOOI -> AC	0.202	0.205	0.066	3.037	0.002

6.2.3 Absorptive Capability - Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H3 (The absorptive capability positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs), the construction of the Absorptive Capability and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-8.

Figure 6-8, Path Model of the Impact of AC on IP (Model 6)

Table 6-25 shows that the SRMR value of 0.071 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.281 and 0.089, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 178.130, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.903 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-8, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.167, indicating the explanatory power of AC on IP is 16.7%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial

innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-25, Model Fit for Model 6

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.071	0.071
d_ULS	0.281	0.281
d_G	0.089	0.089
Chi-square	178.13	178.13
NFI	0.903	0.903

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-26, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-26, Convergent Validity for Model 6

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
AC		0.752	0.851	0.604
PAC1	0.828			
PAC2	0.876			
PAC4	0.883			
RAC4	0.527			
IP		0.896	0.920	0.659
IP1	0.856			
IP2	0.774			

IP3	0.843
IP4	0.866
IP6	0.872
IP7	0.632

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-27 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the two latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 6, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-27, Discriminant Validity for Model 6

	AC	IP
AC	0.777	
IP	0.408	0.812

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-28 shows that the path coefficient 0.408 indicates a positive relationship between the AC and IP. The T statistic of 6.646, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of AC on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that the absorptive capability significantly positively impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Hypothesis H3 is fully supported by model 6.

Table 6-28, Construct Reliability and Validity for Model 6

Path	Sample Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
AC -> IP	0.408	0.418	0.061	6.646	0.000

6.2.4 Absorptive Capability - Outside-in Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H4a (Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between outside-in open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the mediating variable, absorptive capability, is added to the relationship between outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-9 was constructed to test the absorptive capability mediating impact.

Figure 6-9, Path Model of the Mediating Impact of AC on OIOI and IP (Model 7)

Table 6-29 shows that the SRMR value of 0.068 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.421 and 0.139, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 282.887, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.884 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-9, the R-square for OIOI to IP is 0.249, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on IP is 24.9%; the R-square

for OIOI to AC is 0.141, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on AC is 14.1%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-29, Model Fit for Model 7

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.068	0.068
d_ULS	0.421	0.421
d_G	0.139	0.139
Chi- square	282.887	282.887
NFI	0.884	0.884

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-30, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-30, Convergent Validity for Model 7

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.815			
So3	0.891			
So4	0.916			
AC		0.752	0.851	0.602
PAC1	0.831			

PAC2	0.866			
PAC4	0.871			
RAC4	0.455			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.661
IP1	0.852			
IP2	0.766			
IP3	0.837			
IP4	0.859			
IP6	0.882			
IP7	0.663			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-31 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 7, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-31, Discriminant Validity for Model 7

	AC	IP	OIOI
AC	0.776		
IP	0.401	0.813	
OIOI	0.376	0.426	0.875

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-32 shows the path coefficient of 0.376 and the T statistic of 7.550, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact AC directly. The path coefficient of 0.281 and the T statistic of 3.916, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggest that the AC can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.321 and the T statistic of 5.854, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-32, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 7

		Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Direct Effects	OIOI -> AC	0.376	0.379	0.050	7.550	0.000
	AC -> IP	0.281	0.286	0.072	3.916	0.000
	OIOI -> IP	0.321	0.320	0.055	5.854	0.000
Indirect Effects	OIOI -> AC	0.106	0.109	0.032	3.320	0.001
	-> IP					
Total Effects	OIOI -> IP	0.426	0.429	0.051	8.430	0.000

Mediation Impact Tests

The indirect effect of OIOI on IP is equal to the path coefficient of OIOI on AC (a) multiplied by the path coefficient of AC on IP (b), which is $a \times b = 0.376 \times 0.281 = 0.106$ ($t = 3.320, p < 0.001, significant$). The path coefficient for OIOI on IP (c) is 0.321 ($t = 5.854, p < 0.001, significant$). $a \times b \times c = 0.033$ (*positive*). Therefore, the absorptive capability is a partial mediator and complementary mediates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, with a mediation impact of 0.106. The proportion of the total impact accounted for by the mediating impact is 24.7%, and the ratio of the mediating impact to the direct impact is 0.330.

6.2.5 Absorptive Capability – Inside-out Open Innovation and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H4b (Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between inside-out open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the mediating variable, absorptive capability, is added to the relationship between inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-10 was constructed to test the absorptive capability mediating impact.

Figure 6-10, Path Model of the Mediating Impact of AC on IOOI and IP (Model 8)

Table 6-33 shows that the SRMR value of 0.066 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.399 and 0.139, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 283.628, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.881 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-10, the R-square for IOOI to IP is 0.195, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on IP is 19.5%; the R-square for IOOI to AC is 0.128, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on AC is 12.8%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-33, Model Fit for Model 8

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.066	0.066

d_ULS	0.399	0.399
d_G	0.139	0.139
Chi-square	283.628	283.628
NFI	0.881	0.881

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-34, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-34, Convergent Validity for Model 8

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
Se1	0.868			
Se2	0.875			
Se4	0.881			
AC		0.752	0.851	0.601
PAC1	0.821			
PAC2	0.869			
PAC4	0.876			
RAC4	0.456			
IP		0.896	0.920	0.660
IP1	0.855			
IP2	0.768			
IP3	0.842			
IP4	0.863			
IP6	0.878			
IP7	0.642			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-35 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 8, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-35, Discriminant Validity for Model 8

	AC	IOOI	IP
AC	0.775		
IOOI	0.357	0.874	
IP	0.408	0.303	0.812

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-36 shows the path coefficient of 0.357 and the T statistic of 5.556, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the IOOI can positively and significantly impact AC directly. The path coefficient of 0.343 and the T statistic of 4.668, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the AC can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.181 and the T statistic of 2.329, with a corresponding p-value of 0.020, suggest that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-36, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 8

	Path	Sample	Standard	T Statistics	P	
	Coefficient	Mean	Deviation	(O/STDEV)	values	
		(M)	(STDEV)			
Direct Effects	IOOI -> AC	0.357	0.363	0.064	5.556	0.000
	AC -> IP	0.343	0.349	0.074	4.668	0.000
	IOOI -> IP	0.181	0.18	0.078	2.329	0.020
Indirect Effects	IOOI -> AC -> IP	0.122	0.126	0.032	3.822	0.000
Total Effects	IOOI -> IP	0.303	0.305	0.073	4.157	0.000

Mediation Impact Tests

The indirect effect of IOOI on IP is equal to the path coefficient of IOOI on AC (a) multiplied by the path coefficient of AC on IP (b), which is $a \times b = 0.357 \times 0.343 = 0.122$ ($t = 3.822, p < 0.001, significant$). The path coefficient for IOOI on IP (c) is 0.181 ($t = 2.329, p = 0.020, significant$). $a \times b \times c = 0.022$ (*positive*). Therefore, the absorptive capability is a partial mediator and complementary mediates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance, with a mediation impact of 0.122. The proportion of the total impact accounted for by the mediating impact is 40.6%, and the ratio of the mediating impact to the direct impact is 0.680.

6.2.6 Absorptive Capability – Coupled Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H4c (Absorptive capability mediates the relationship between coupled open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the mediating variable, absorptive capability, is added to the relationship between coupled open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-11 was constructed to test the absorptive capability mediating impact.

Figure 6-11, Path Model of the Mediating Impact of AC on COI and IP (Model 9)

Table 6-37 shows that the SRMR value of 0.071 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.454 and 0.141, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 288.143, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.880 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-11, the R-square for COI to IP is 0.251, indicating the explanatory power of COI on IP is 25.1%; the R-square for COI to AC is 0.161, indicating the explanatory power of COI on AC is 16.1%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-37, Model Fit for Model 9

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.071	0.071

d_ULS	0.454	0.454
d_G	0.141	0.141
Chi-square	288.143	288.143
NFI	0.880	0.880

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-38, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-38, Convergent Validity for Model 9

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
COI		0.832	0.898	0.747
Ac1	0.911			
Ac2	0.890			
Re1	0.788			
AC		0.752	0.851	0.599
PAC1	0.820			
PAC2	0.860			
PAC4	0.872			
RAC4	0.473			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.661
IP1	0.847			
IP2	0.773			
IP3	0.840			
IP4	0.865			
IP6	0.878			
IP7	0.653			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-39 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 9, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-39, Discriminant Validity for Model 9

	AC	COI	IP
AC	0.774		
COI	0.401	0.865	
IP	0.405	0.432	0.813

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-40 shows the path coefficient of 0.401 and the T statistic of 7.876, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the COI can positively and significantly impact AC directly. The path coefficient of 0.276 and the T statistic of 3.723, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggest that the AC can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.322 and the T statistic of 5.570, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the COI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-40, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 9

	Path	Sample	Standard	T Statistics	P values	
	Coefficient	Mean (M)	Deviation (STDEV)	(O/STDEV)		
Direct Effects	COI -> AC	0.401	0.405	0.051	7.876	0.000
	AC -> IP	0.276	0.281	0.074	3.723	0.000
	COI -> IP	0.322	0.321	0.058	5.570	0.000
Indirect Effects	COI -> AC -> IP	0.111	0.114	0.035	3.166	0.002
Total Effects	COI -> IP	0.432	0.435	0.048	8.980	0.000

Mediation Impact Tests

The indirect effect of COI on IP is equal to the path coefficient of COI on AC (a) multiplied by the path coefficient of AC on IP (b), which is $a \times b = 0.401 \times 0.276 = 0.111$ ($t = 3.166, p = 0.002, significant$). The path coefficient for COI on IP (c) is 0.322 ($t = 5.570, p < 0.001, significant$). $a \times b \times c = 0.036$ (*positive*). Therefore, the absorptive capability is a partial mediator and complementary mediates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance, with a mediation impact of 0.111. The proportion of the total impact accounted for by the mediating impact is 25.7%, and the ratio of the mediating impact to the direct impact is 0.345.

6.3 The Mediating Role of Dynamic Capabilities in the Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

6.3.1 Open Innovation Models – Dynamic Capabilities

Based on hypotheses H5a (Adopting an outside-in open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs), H5b (Adopting an inside-out open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs) and H5c (Adopting an inside-out open innovation positively impacts the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs), the construction of the open innovation models and innovation performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-12.

Figure 6-12, Path Model of the Impact of OIM on DC (Model 10)

Table 6-41 shows that the SRMR value of 0.149 suggests a relatively poorer fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 5.638 and 1.265, indicating a higher degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 2491.07, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.473 suggests a relatively poorer fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-12, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.329, indicating the explanatory power of OIM on DC is 32.9%, which means that other impact factors exist on dynamic capabilities variables. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-41, Model Fit for Model 10

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.149	0.149
d_ULS	5.638	5.638
d_G	1.265	1.265
Chi- square	2491.07	2491.07
NFI	0.473	0.473

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-42, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were not greater than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating poor reliability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the four latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were not all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was not more than 50%.

Table 6-42, Convergent Validity for Model 10

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.828			
So3	0.884			
So4	0.91			
COI		0.832	0.899	0.748
Ac1	0.901			
Ac2	0.894			
Re1	0.796			
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.764
Se1	0.882			
Se2	0.868			
Se4	0.872			

DC		0.833	0.864	0.333
ACO1	0.569			
ACO2	0.565			
ACO3	0.557			
ACO4	0.628			
ASO1	0.684			
ASO2	0.662			
ASO3	0.697			
ASO4	0.639			
ATO1	0.490			
ATO2	0.440			
ATO3	0.444			
ATO4	0.542			
ATO5	0.500			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-43 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the four latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 10, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-43, Discriminant Validity for Model 10

	COI	DC	IOOI	OIOI
COI	0.865			
DC	0.404	0.577		
IOOI	0.355	0.376	0.874	
OIOI	0.329	0.478	0.295	0.875

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-44 shows that the path coefficient 0.347 indicates a positive relationship between the OIOI and DC, 0.195 indicates a positive relationship between the IOOI and DC, and 0.221 indicates a positive relationship between the COI and DC. The T statistic of 7.192, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of OIOI on DC is statistically

significant. The T statistic of 3.097, with a corresponding p-value of 0.002, suggests that the impact of IOOI on DC is statistically significant. The T statistic of 4.541, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of COI on DC is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that the three open innovation models can positively and significantly impact absorptive capability. However, due to the model's poor fit, model 10 needs modification, and the new model is shown in Figure 6-13.

Table 6-44, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 10

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
OIOI -> DC	0.347	0.351	0.048	7.192	0.000
COI -> DC	0.221	0.223	0.049	4.541	0.000
IOOI -> DC	0.195	0.200	0.063	3.097	0.002

Figure 6-13, Path Model of the Impact of OIM on DC (Model 10) after Modification

Table 6-45 shows that the SRMR value of 0.096 suggests a relatively good fit for the model. The d_ULS and d_G are 1.253 and 0.394, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 796.138, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.737 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-7, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.283, indicating the explanatory power of OIM on AC is 28.3%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-45, Model Fit for Model 10 after Modification

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.096	0.096
d_ULS	1.253	1.253
d_G	0.394	0.394
Chi-square	796.138	796.138
NFI	0.737	0.737

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-46, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the four latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were nearly all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was nearly more than 50%.

Table 6-46, Convergent Validity for Model 10 after Modification

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.827			
So3	0.886			
So4	0.910			
COI		0.832	0.899	0.748
Ac1	0.903			
Ac2	0.893			
Re1	0.795			
IOOI		0.846	0.906	0.764
Se1	0.880			
Se2	0.877			
Se4	0.865			
DC		0.799	0.86	0.483
ACO2	0.557			
ACO4	0.547			
ASO1	0.808			
ASO2	0.808			
ASO3	0.833			
ASO4	0.802			
ATO4	0.353			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-47 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the four latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 5, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-47, Discriminant Validity for Model 10 after Modification

	COI	DC	IOOI	OIOI
COI	0.865			
DC	0.370	0.695		
IOOI	0.354	0.376	0.874	
OIOI	0.329	0.429	0.295	0.875

Note. The element on the diagonal represents
SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-48 shows that the path coefficient 0.301 indicates a positive relationship between the OIOI and DC, 0.219 indicates a positive relationship between the IOOI and DC, and 0.193 indicates a positive relationship between the COI and DC. The T statistic of 6.441, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of OIOI on DC is statistically significant. The T statistic of 3.495, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of IOOI on DC is statistically significant. The T statistic of 3.813, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of COI on DC is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that adopting each outside-in, inside-out and coupled open innovation model can positively and significantly impact the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities in technology-based SMEs based on Model 10.

Table 6-48, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 10

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
OIOI -> DC	0.301	0.304	0.047	6.441	0.000
IOOI -> DC	0.219	0.223	0.063	3.495	0.000
COI -> DC	0.193	0.195	0.051	3.813	0.000

6.3.2 Dynamic Capabilities – Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H6 (The dynamic capabilities positively impact innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs), the construction of the Dynamic Capabilities and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-13.

Figure 6-14, Path Model of the Impact of DC on IP (Model 11)

Table 6-49 shows that the SRMR value of 0.096 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_ULS and d_G are 0.847 and 0.260, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 500.702, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.810 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-13, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.159, indicating the explanatory power of DC on IP is 15.9%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-49, Model Fit for Model 11

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.096	0.096
d_ULS	0.847	0.847
d_G	0.260	0.260
Chi-square	500.702	500.702
NFI	0.810	0.810

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-50, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-50, Convergent Validity for Model 11

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
DC		0.799	0.859	0.487
ACO2	0.541			
ACO4	0.521			
ASO1	0.814			
ASO2	0.834			
ASO3	0.853			
ASO4	0.818			
ATO4	0.301			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.836			
IP2	0.760			
IP3	0.846			
IP4	0.868			
IP6	0.880			
IP7	0.670			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-51 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the two latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 11, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

**Table 6-51, Discriminant
Validity for Model 11**

	DC	IP
DC	0.698	
IP	0.398	0.814

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-52 shows that the path coefficient 0.398 indicates a positive relationship between the DC and IP. The T statistic of 6.742, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of DC on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that dynamic capabilities significantly and positively impact technology-based SMEs' innovation performance. Hypothesis H6 is fully supported by model 11.

Table 6-52, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 11

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
DC -> IP	0.398	0.410	0.059	6.742	0.000

6.3.3 Dynamic Capabilities – Outside-in Open Innovation and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H7a (Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between outside-in open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the mediating variable, dynamic capabilities, is added to the relationship between outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-14 was constructed to test the dynamic capabilities mediating impact.

Figure 6-15, Path Model of the Mediating Impact of DC on OIOI and IP (Model 12)

Table 6-53 shows that the SRMR value of 0.088 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 1.057 and 0.334, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 646.475, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.802 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-12, the R-square for OIOI to IP is 0.237, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on IP is 23.7%; the R-square for OIOI to DC is 0.183, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on DC is 18.3%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-53, Model Fit for Model 12

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.088	0.088
d_{ULS}	1.057	1.057
d_G	0.334	0.334
Chi-square	646.475	646.475

NFI	0.802	0.802
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Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-54, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were nearly all greater than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were nearly all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was nearly more than 50%.

Table 6-54, Convergent Validity for Model 12

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.817			
So3	0.891			
So4	0.914			
DC		0.799	0.86	0.485
ACO2	0.538			
ACO4	0.529			
ASO1	0.811			
ASO2	0.819			
ASO3	0.845			
ASO4	0.810			
ATO4	0.355			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.842			
IP2	0.760			
IP3	0.838			
IP4	0.859			
IP6	0.885			
IP7	0.680			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-55 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 12, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-55, Discriminant Validity for Model 12

	DC	IP	OIOI
DC	0.696		
IP	0.396	0.814	
OIOI	0.427	0.425	0.875

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-56 shows the path coefficient of 0.427 and the T statistic of 8.923, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact DC directly. The path coefficient of 0.262 and the T statistic of 3.705, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the DC can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.313 and the T statistic of 5.621, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-56, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model for Model 12

	Path	Path	Sample	Standard	T Statistics	P
	Coefficient	Mean	Deviation	(O/STDEV)	values	
		(M)	(STDEV)			
Direct Effects	OIOI -> DC	0.427	0.433	0.048	8.923	0.000
	DC -> IP	0.262	0.268	0.071	3.705	0.000
	OIOI -> IP	0.313	0.312	0.056	5.621	0.000
Indirect Effects	OIOI -> DC -> IP	0.112	0.116	0.033	3.442	0.001
Total Effects	OIOI -> IP	0.425	0.428	0.051	8.392	0.000

Mediation Impact Tests

The indirect effect of OIOI on IP is equal to the path coefficient of OIOI on DC (a) multiplied by the path coefficient of DC on IP (b), which is $a \times b = 0.427 \times 0.262 = 0.112$ ($t = 3.442, p = 0.001, significant$). The path coefficient for OIOI on IP (c) is 0.313 ($t = 5.621, p < 0.001, significant$). $a \times b \times c = 0.050$ (*positive*). Therefore, the dynamic capabilities variable is a partial mediator and complementary mediates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, with a mediation impact of 0.112. The proportion of the total impact accounted for by the mediating impact is 26.4%, and the ratio of the mediating impact to the direct impact is 0.358.

6.3.4 Dynamic Capabilities – Inside-out Open Innovation Models and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H7b (Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between inside-out open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the mediating variable, dynamic capabilities, is added to the relationship between outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-15 was constructed to test the dynamic capabilities mediating impact.

Figure 6-16, Path Model of the Mediating Impact of DC on IOOI and IP (Model 13)

Table 6-57 shows that the SRMR value of 0.088 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 1.049 and 0.349, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 693.051, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.785 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-15, the R-square for IOOI to IP is 0.186, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on IP is 18.6%; the R-square for IOOI to DC is 0.142, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on DC is 14.2%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-57, Model Fit for Model 13

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.088	0.088
d_{ULS}	1.049	1.049
d_G	0.349	0.349
Chi-square	693.051	693.051
NFI	0.785	0.785

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-58, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were nearly all greater than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were nearly all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was nearly more than 50%.

Table 6-58, Convergent Validity for Model 13

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
Se1	0.874			
Se2	0.873			
Se4	0.876			
DC		0.799	0.859	0.484
ACO2	0.568			
ACO4	0.546			
ASO1	0.806			
ASO2	0.822			
ASO3	0.839			
ASO4	0.809			
ATO4	0.293			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.841			
IP2	0.758			
IP3	0.844			
IP4	0.864			
IP6	0.883			
IP7	0.669			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-59 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 13, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-59, Discriminant Validity for Model 13

	DC	IOOI	IP
DC	0.696		
IOOI	0.377	0.874	
IP	0.399	0.300	0.813

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-60 shows the path coefficient of 0.377 and the T statistic of 6.101, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the IOOI can positively and significantly impact DC directly. The path coefficient of 0.333 and the T statistic of 4.862, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the DC can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.175 and the T statistic of 2.315, with a corresponding p-value of 0.021, suggests that the IOOI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-60, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model for Model 13

	Path	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Direct Effects	IOOI -> DC	0.377	0.383	0.062	6.101	0.000
	DC -> IP	0.333	0.340	0.069	4.862	0.000
	IOOI -> IP	0.175	0.173	0.076	2.315	0.021
Indirect Effects	IOOI -> DC -> IP	0.126	0.130	0.032	3.874	0.000
Total Effects	IOOI -> IP	0.300	0.303	0.074	4.080	0.000

Mediation Impact Tests

The indirect effect of IOOI on IP is equal to the path coefficient of IOOI on DC (a) multiplied by the path coefficient of DC on IP (b), which is $a \times b = 0.377 \times 0.333 = 0.126$ ($t = 3.874, p = 0.000, significant$). The path coefficient for IOOI on IP (c) is 0.173 ($t = 2.315, p < 0.021, significant$). $a \times b \times c = 0.022$ (*positive*). Therefore, the dynamic capabilities variable is a partial mediator and complementary mediates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance, with a mediation impact of 0.126. The proportion of the total impact accounted for by the mediating impact is 42.0%, and the ratio of the mediating impact to the direct impact is 0.720.

6.3.5 Dynamic Capabilities – Coupled Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H7c (Dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between coupled open innovation and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the mediating variable, dynamic capabilities, is added to the relationship between outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-16 was constructed to test the dynamic capabilities mediating impact.

Figure 6-17, Path Model of the Mediating Impact of DC on COI and IP (Model 14)

Table 6-61 shows that the SRMR value of 0.086 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 1.009 and 0.323, indicating a certain degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 629.923, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.803 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-16, the R-square for COI to IP is 0.252, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on IP is 25.2%; the R-square for COI to DC is 0.135, indicating the explanatory power of COI on DC is 13.5%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-61, Model Fit for Model 14

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.086	0.086
d_{ULS}	1.009	1.009
d_G	0.323	0.323
Chi-square	629.923	629.923

NFI 0.803 0.803

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-62, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were nearly all greater than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were nearly all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was nearly more than 50%.

Table 6-62, Convergent Validity for Model 14

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	C.R.	AVE
COI		0.832	0.898	0.747
Ac1	0.907			
Ac2	0.896			
Re1	0.786			
DC		0.799	0.86	0.486
ACO2	0.547			
ACO4	0.530			
ASO1	0.818			
ASO2	0.822			
ASO3	0.845			
ASO4	0.812			
ATO4	0.322			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.838			
IP2	0.767			
IP3	0.841			
IP4	0.866			
IP6	0.881			
IP7	0.670			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-63 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 14, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-63, Discriminant Validity for Model 14

	COI	DC	IP
COI	0.864		
DC	0.367	0.697	
IP	0.432	0.397	0.814

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-64 shows the path coefficient of 0.367 and the T statistic of 7.275, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the COI can positively and significantly impact DC directly. The path coefficient of 0.275 and the T statistic of 4.227, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the DC can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.331 and the T statistic of 6.842, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the COI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-64, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model for Model 14

	Path	Sample	Standard	T Statistics	P	
	Coefficient	Mean	Deviation	(O/STDEV)	values	
		(M)	(STDEV)			
Direct Effects	COI -> DC	0.367	0.372	0.05	7.275	0.000
	DC -> IP	0.275	0.281	0.065	4.227	0.000
	COI -> IP	0.331	0.330	0.048	6.842	0.000
Indirect Effects	COI -> DC -> IP	0.101	0.104	0.028	3.589	0.000
Total Effects	DC -> IP	0.275	0.281	0.065	4.227	0.000

Mediation Impact Tests

The indirect effect of COI on IP is equal to the path coefficient of COI on DC (a) multiplied by the path coefficient of DC on IP (b), which is $a \times b = 0.367 \times 0.275 = 0.101$ ($t = 3.589, p = 0.001, significant$). The path coefficient for COI on IP (c) is 0.101 ($t = 3.589, p < 0.001, significant$). $a \times b \times c = 0.033$ (*positive*). Therefore, the dynamic capabilities variable is a partial mediator and complementary mediates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance, with a mediation impact of 0.101. The proportion of the total impact accounted for by the mediating impact is 28.2%, and the ratio of the mediating impact to the direct impact is 0.305.

6.4 The Direct Impact of Cognitive Inertia on Innovation Performance

6.4.1 Learning Inertia – Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H8a (The learning inertia positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs), the construction of the Learning Inertia and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-17.

Figure 6-18, Path Model of the Impact of LI on IP (Model 15)

Table 6-65 shows that the SRMR value of 0.067 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_ULS and d_G are 0.201 and 0.089, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 185.728, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.882 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-17, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.159, indicating the explanatory power of LI on IP is 15.9%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-65, Model Fit for Model 15

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.067	0.067
d_ULS	0.201	0.201
d_G	0.089	0.089
Chi-square	185.728	185.728
NFI	0.882	0.882

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-66, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-66, Convergent Validity for Model 15

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
LI		0.768	0.865	0.682
LI1	0.775			

LI2	0.856			
LI4	0.843			
IP		0.896	0.920	0.660
IP1	0.839			
IP2	0.788			
IP3	0.833			
IP4	0.869			
IP6	0.877			
IP7	0.646			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-67 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the two latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 15, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-67, Discriminant Validity for Model 15

	IP	LI
IP	0.813	
LI	0.399	0.826

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-68 shows that the path coefficient 0.399 indicates a positive relationship between the LI and IP. The T statistic of 7.900, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of LI on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that the learning inertia significantly positively impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Hypothesis H8a is fully supported by model 15.

Table 6-68, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model for 15

Path Coefficient	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values

(M) (STDEV)

LI ->	0.399	0.404	0.050	7.900	0.000
IP					

6.4.2 Experience Inertia – Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H8b (The experience inertia positively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs), the construction of the Experience Inertia and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-18.

Figure 6-19, Path Model of the Impact of EI on IP (Model 16)

Table 6-69 shows that the SRMR value of 0.064 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.185 and 0.085, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 174.624, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.890 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-18, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.215, indicating the explanatory power of EI on IP is 21.5%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-69, Model Fit for Model 16

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.064	0.064
d_ULS	0.185	0.185
d_G	0.085	0.085
Chi-square	174.624	174.624
NFI	0.890	0.890

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-70, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-70, Convergent Validity for Model 16

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
EI		0.757	0.861	0.674
EI3	0.862			
EI5	0.84			
EI6	0.756			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.840			
IP2	0.766			
IP3	0.843			
IP4	0.865			
IP6	0.879			
IP7	0.669			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-71 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the two latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 16, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-71, Discriminant Validity for Model 16

	IP	LI
EI	0.821	
IP	0.463	0.814

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-72 shows that the path coefficient 0.463 indicates a positive relationship between the EI and IP. The T statistic of 8.052, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of EI on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that the experience inertia significantly positively impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Hypothesis H8b is fully supported by model 16.

Table 6-72, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 16

Path	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	
EI -> IP	0.463	0.467	0.058	8.052	0.000

6.4.3 Procedural Inertia – Innovation Performance

Based on hypothesis H8c (The procedural inertia negatively impacts innovation performance improvement in technology-based SMEs), the construction of the Procedural Inertia and Innovation Performance PLS structural equation is shown in Figure 6-19.

Figure 6-20, Path Model of the Impact of PI on IP (Model 17)

Table 6-73 shows that the SRMR value of 0.069 suggests a good fit for the model. The d_{ULS} and d_G are 0.216 and 0.102, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path model. The Chi-square value is 214.783, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.870 suggests a good fit for the model. Based on Figure 6-19, the R-square for innovation performance is 0.188, indicating the explanatory power of LI on IP is 18.8%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-73, Model Fit for Model 17

	Saturated model	Estimated model
SRMR	0.069	0.069
d_{ULS}	0.216	0.216
d_G	0.102	0.102
Chi-square	214.783	214.783
NFI	0.870	0.870

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-74, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$

level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the two latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-74, Convergent Validity for Model 17

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
PI		0.781	0.872	0.694
PI1	0.857			
PI3	0.879			
PI5	0.759			
IP		0.896	0.920	0.660
IP1	0.851			
IP2	0.763			
IP3	0.846			
IP4	0.864			
IP6	0.880			
IP7	0.648			

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-75 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the two latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the four latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 17, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-75, Discriminant Validity for Model 17

	IP	PI
IP	0.813	
PI	0.434	0.833

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-76 shows that the path coefficient 0.434 indicates a positive relationship between the PI and IP. The T statistic of 10.455, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the impact of PI on IP is statistically significant. Therefore, we can conclude that the procedural inertia significantly positively impacts the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Hypothesis H8c is not supported by model 17.

Table 6-76, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model for Model 17

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
PI -> IP	0.434	0.440	0.041	10.455	0.000

6.5 The Moderating Role of Learning Inertia in the Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

6.5.1 Approach for Modertaing Impact Tests

When the direction and magnitude of the relationship between two variables depend on a third variable, the third variable moderates the relationship between them. The test model is shown in Figure 6-20 below, where X is the independent variable, Y is the dependent variable, and W is the moderating variable. If the path coefficient (b) is significant, variable W moderates variable X's impact on variable Y.

Figure 6-21, Moderation Impact Tests Model

When evaluating the moderating impact of a moderating variable using the PLS algorithm, it is not accurate to base the judgement on R-square. However, instead of the utility value of the moderator (interaction term), f^2 , provided that the path coefficient of the moderator is significant. Kenny (2016) proposed a feasible assessment criterion with $0.005 \leq f^2 \leq 0.01$ being a small moderation impact, $0.01 \leq f^2 \leq 0.025$ being a medium moderation impact and $f^2 \geq 0.025$ being a significant moderation impact.

6.5.2 Learning Inertia – Outside-in Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9a (Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, learning inertia, is added to the relationship between outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-21 was constructed to test the learning inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-22, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of LI on OIOI and IP (Model 18)

Table 6-77 shows that the SRMR values of 0.062 and 0.059 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.304 and 0.270, and the d_G are 0.134 and 0.128, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 280.670 and 263.095, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.870 and 0.878 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-21, the R-square for OIOI to IP is 0.330, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on IP is 33.0%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-77, Model Fit for Model 18

Saturated Model	Estimated Model
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SRMR	0.062	0.059
d_ULS	0.304	0.270
d_G	0.134	0.128
Chi-square	280.670	263.095
NFI	0.870	0.878

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-78, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-78, Convergent Validity for Model 18

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.806			
So3	0.896			
So4	0.918			
LI		0.768	0.865	0.681
LI1	0.774			
LI2	0.856			
LI4	0.843			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.843			
IP2	0.773			
IP3	0.833			
IP4	0.860			
IP6	0.884			
IP7	0.670			
LI x OIOI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-79 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 18, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-79, Discriminant Validity for Model 18

	IP	LI	OIOI
IP	0.814		
LI	0.394	0.826	
OIOI	0.426	0.158	0.874

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-80 shows the path coefficient of 0.332 and the T statistic of 7.549, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.296 and the T statistic of 6.559, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the LI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-80, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 18

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
OIOI -> IP	0.332	0.335	0.044	7.549	0.000
LI -> IP	0.296	0.300	0.045	6.559	0.000
LI x OIOI -> IP	-0.158	-0.156	0.035	4.566	0.000

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-80 shows the path coefficient of -0.158 and the T statistic of 4.566, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000. Table 6-81 shows that the f-square of LI x OIOI to IP is 0.059, more significant than 0.025, indicating a large moderating impact. Table 6-82 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of OIOI to IP changed from 0.428 to 0.332, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 8.645 and 7.549, respectively, indicating that the moderator LI significantly negatively impacts the relationship between OIOI and IP.

Table 81, f-square for Model 18

Path	f-square
LI -> IP	0.123
OIOI -> IP	0.154
LI x OIOI -> IP	0.059

Table 6-82, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderation for Model 18

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
OIOI -> IP	0.428	0.332	0.096
(T)	(8.645)	(7.549)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low LI condition (LI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between OIOI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of LI, the impact of OIOI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high LI condition (LI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low learning inertia, an increase in the outside-in open innovation model has a more pronounced impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, for the high LI condition, the line tends to straighten, indicating that at higher levels of learning inertia, the increase in outside-in open innovation does not lead to a

similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of OIOI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher learning inertia weakens the relationship between the outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-22 highlights that the impact of OIOI on IP varies depending on the level of LI. Low LI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of OIOI on IP, while high LI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of OIOI on IP due to learning inertia.

Figure 6-23, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 18

6.5.3 Learning Inertia – Inside-out Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9b (Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, learning inertia, is added to the relationship between inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-23 was constructed to test the learning inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-24, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of LI on IOOI and IP (Model 19)

Table 6-83 shows that the SRMR values of 0.062 and 0.059 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.299 and 0.268, and the d_G are 0.140 and 0.134, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 293.643 and 275.536, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.860 and 0.869 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-23, the R-square for IOOI to IP is 0.239, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on IP is 23.9%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-83, Model Fit for Model 19

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.062	0.059
d_ULS	0.299	0.268
d_G	0.140	0.134
Chi-square	293.643	275.536
NFI	0.860	0.869

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-84, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-84, Convergent Validity for Model 19

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.764
Se1	0.867			
Se2	0.863			
Se4	0.892			
LI		0.768	0.865	0.681
LI1	0.775			
LI2	0.856			
LI4	0.843			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.661
IP1	0.843			
IP2	0.777			
IP3	0.835			
IP4	0.865			

IP6	0.882			
IP7	0.653			
LI x IOOI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-85 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 19, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-85, Discriminant Validity for Model 19

	IOOI	IP	LI
IOOI	0.874		
IP	0.302	0.813	
LI	0.286	0.397	0.826

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-86 shows the path coefficient of 0.131 and the T statistic of 1.878, with a corresponding p-value of 0.060, slightly higher than the commonly used significance level (e.g., 0.05), suggesting that we cannot establish statistical significance for this path coefficient of IOOI on IP. The path coefficient of 0.292 and the T statistic of 5.308, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the LI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-86, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 19

Path	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O /STDEV)	P values	
IOOI -> IP	0.131	0.134	0.070	1.878	0.060
LI -> IP	0.292	0.296	0.055	5.308	0.000
LI x IOOI ->	-0.182	-0.179	0.048	3.767	0.000

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-86 shows the path coefficient of -0.128 and the T statistic of 3.767, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000. Table 6-87 shows that the f-square of LI x IOOI to IP is 0.056, more significant than 0.025, indicating a large moderating impact. Table 6-88 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of IOOI to IP changed from 0.306 to 0.1312, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 4.451 and 1.878, respectively, indicating that the moderator LI significantly negatively impacts the relationship between IOOI and IP.

Table 6-87, f-square for Model 19

Path	f-square
IOOI -> IP	0.018
LI -> IP	0.099
LI x IOOI -> IP	0.056

Table 6-88, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 19

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
IOOI -> IP	0.306	0.131	0.175
(T)	(4.451)	(1.878)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low LI condition (LI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between IOOI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of LI, the impact of IOOI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high LI condition (LI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low learning inertia, an increase in the inside-out open innovation model has a more pronounced

impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, for the high LI condition, the line tends to straighten, indicating that at higher levels of learning inertia, the increase in inside-out open innovation does not lead to a similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of IOOI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher learning inertia weakens the relationship between the inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-24 highlights that the impact of IOOI on IP varies depending on the level of LI. Low LI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of IOOI on IP, while high LI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of IOOI on IP due to learning inertia.

Figure 6-25, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 19

6.5.4 Learning Inertia – Coupled Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9c (Learning inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, learning inertia, is added to the relationship between outside-in open

innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-25 was constructed to test the learning inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-26, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of LI on COI and IP (Model 20)

Table 6-89 shows that the SRMR values of 0.062 and 0.059 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.303 and 0.272, and the d_G are 0.138 and 0.132, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 290.242 and 273.655, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.863 and 0.871 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-25, the R-square for COI to IP is 0.291, indicating the explanatory power of COI on IP is 29.1%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to

analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-89, Model Fit for Model 20

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.062	0.059
d_ULS	0.303	0.272
d_G	0.138	0.132
Chi-square	290.242	273.655
NFI	0.863	0.871

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-90, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-90, Convergent Validity for Model 20

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
COI		0.832	0.898	0.746
Ac1	0.909			
Ac2	0.898			
Re1	0.779			
LI		0.768	0.865	0.681
LI1	0.774			
LI2	0.856			
LI4	0.843			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.661
IP1	0.839			

IP2	0.779			
IP3	0.836			
IP4	0.866			
IP6	0.879			
IP7	0.660			
LI x COI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-91 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 20, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-91, Discriminant Validity for Model 20

	COI	IP	LI
COI	0.864		
IP	0.433	0.813	
LI	0.323	0.396	0.826

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-92 shows the path coefficient of 0.315 and the T statistic of 6.553, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the COI can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.234 and the T statistic of 4.910, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the LI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-92, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 20

Path	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
COI -> IP	0.315	0.316	0.048	6.553	0.000
LI -> IP	0.234	0.240	0.048	4.910	0.000

LI x COI -> IP	-0.138	-0.137	0.037	3.754	0.000
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Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-92 shows the path coefficient of -0.138 and the T statistic of 3.754, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000. Table 6-93 shows that the f-square of LI x OIOI to IP is 0.043, more significant than 0.025, indicating a large moderating impact. Table 6-94 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of OIOI to IP changed from 0.433 to 0.315, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 9.183 and 6.553, respectively, indicating that the moderator LI significantly negatively impacts the relationship between COI and IP.

Table 6-93, f-square for Model 20

Path	f-square
COI -> IP	0.123
LI -> IP	0.064
LI x COI -> IP	0.043

Table 6-94, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 20

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
COI -> IP	0.433	0.315	0.118
(T)	(9.183)	(6.553)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low LI condition (LI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between COI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of LI, the impact of COI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high LI condition (LI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low learning inertia, an

increase in the coupled open innovation model has a more pronounced impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, for the high LI condition, the line tends to straighten, indicating that at higher levels of learning inertia, the increase in coupled open innovation does not lead to a similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of COI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher learning inertia weakens the relationship between the coupled open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-26 highlights that the impact of COI on IP varies depending on the level of LI. Low LI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of COI on IP, while high LI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of COI on IP due to learning inertia.

Figure 6-27, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 20

6.5.5 Experience Inertia – Outside-in Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9d (Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, experience inertia, is added to the relationship between outside-in open

innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-27 was constructed to test the experience inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-28, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of EI on OIOI and IP (Model 21)

Table 6-95 shows that the SRMR values of 0.058 and 0.057 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.266 and 0.249, and the d_G are 0.130 and 0.127, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 270.294 and 260.803, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.877 and 0.881 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-27, the R-square for OIOI to IP is 0.288, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on IP is 28.8%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-95, Model Fit for Model 21

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.058	0.057
d_ULS	0.266	0.249
d_G	0.130	0.127
Chi- square	270.294	260.803
NFI	0.877	0.881

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-96, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-96, Convergent Validity for Model 21

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.806			
So3	0.896			
So4	0.918			
EI		0.768	0.865	0.681
EI3	0.862			
EI5	0.84			
EI6	0.756			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.843			
IP2	0.763			
IP3	0.838			
IP4	0.860			

IP6	0.883			
IP7	0.677			
EI x OIOI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-97 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 21, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-97, Discriminant Validity for Model 21

	IP	EI	OIOI
IP	0.821		
EI	0.463	0.814	
OIOI	0.443	0.426	0.874

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-98 shows the path coefficient of 0.250 and the T statistic of 4.778, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.294 and the T statistic of 4.447, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the EI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-98, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 21

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
OIOI -> IP	0.250	0.252	0.052	4.778	0.000
EI -> IP	0.294	0.298	0.066	4.447	0.000
EI x OIOI -> IP	-0.106	-0.105	0.045	2.377	0.018

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-98 shows the path coefficient of -0.106 and the T statistic of 2.377, with a corresponding p-value of 0.018. Table 6-99 shows that the f-square of EI x OIOI to IP is 0.018, less than 0.025 but more significant than 0.01, indicating a medium moderating impact. Table 6-100 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of OIOI to IP changed from 0.428 to 0.250, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 8.645 and 4.778, respectively, indicating that the moderator EI significantly negatively impacts the relationship between OIOI and IP.

Table 6-99, f-square for Model 21

Path	f-square
EI -> IP	0.086
OIOI -> IP	0.068
EI x OIOI -> IP	0.018

Table 6-100, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 21

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
OIOI -> IP	0.428	0.250	0.178
(T)	(8.645)	(4.778)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low EI condition (EI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between OIOI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of EI, the impact of OIOI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high EI condition (EI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low experience inertia, an increase in outside-in open innovation model has a more pronounced impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, the line tends to straighten for the high EI condition, indicating that at higher levels of experience inertia, the increase in outside-in open innovation does

not lead to a similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of OIOI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher experience inertia weakens the relationship between the outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-28 highlights that the impact of OIOI on IP varies depending on the level of EI. Low EI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of OIOI on IP, while high EI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of OIOI on IP due to experience inertia.

Figure 6-29, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 21

6.5.6 Experience Inertia – Inside-out Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9e (Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, experience inertia, is added to the relationship between inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-29 was constructed to test the experience inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-30, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of EI on IOOI and IP (Model 22)

Table 6-101 shows that the SRMR values of 0.062 and 0.061 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.295 and 0.290, and the d_G are 0.141 and 0.140, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 291.939 and 288.717, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.864 and 0.866 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-29, the R-square for IOOI to IP is 0.228, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on IP is 22.8%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-101, Model Fit for Model 22

Saturated Model	Estimated Model
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SRMR	0.062	0.061
d_ULS	0.295	0.290
d_G	0.141	0.140
Chi-square	291.939	288.717
NFI	0.864	0.866

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-102, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-102, Convergent Validity for Model 22

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.764
Se1	0.867			
Se2	0.863			
Se4	0.893			
EI		0.757	0.861	0.674
EI3	0.862			
EI5	0.84			
EI6	0.756			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.842			
IP2	0.764			
IP3	0.842			
IP4	0.864			
IP6	0.881			
IP7	0.669			
EI x IOOI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-103 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 22, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-103, Discriminant Validity for Model 22

	EI	IOOI	IP
EI	0.821		
IOOI	0.430	0.874	
IP	0.463	0.301	0.814

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-104 shows the path coefficient of 0.114 and the T statistic of 1.509, with a corresponding p-value of 0.131, slightly higher than the commonly used significance level (e.g., 0.05), suggesting that we cannot establish statistical significance for this path coefficient of IOOI on IP. The path coefficient of 0.401 and the T statistic of 5.660, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the EI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-104, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 22

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
IOOI -> IP	0.114	0.119	0.076	1.509	0.131
EI -> IP	0.401	0.401	0.071	5.660	0.000
EI x IOOI -> IP	-0.022	-0.022	0.053	0.416	0.678

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-104 shows the path coefficient of -0.022 and the T statistic of 0.416, with a corresponding p-value of 0.678. Table 6-105 shows that the f-square of EI x IOOI to IP is 0.001, indicating no moderating impact. Table 6-106 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of IOOI to IP changed from 0.306 to 0.114, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 4.451 and 1.509, respectively, indicating that the moderator EI does not significantly impacts the relationship between IOOI and IP.

Table 6-105, f-square for Model 22

Path	f-square
EI -> IP	0.159
IOOI -> IP	0.012
EI x IOOI -> IP	0.001

Table 6-106, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 22

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
IOOI -> IP	0.306	0.114	0.192
(T)	(4.451)	(1.509)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low EI condition (EI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between IOOI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of EI, the impact of IOOI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high EI condition (EI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low experience inertia, an increase in the inside-out open innovation model has a more pronounced impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, the line tends to straighten for the high EI condition, indicating that at higher levels of experience inertia, the increase in inside-out open innovation does not lead to a similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of

IOOI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher experience inertia weakens the relationship between the inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-30 highlights that the impact of IOOI on IP varies depending on the level of EI. Low EI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of IOOI on IP, while high EI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of IOOI on IP due to experience inertia.

Figure 6-31, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 22

6.5.7 Experience Inertia – Coupled Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9f (Experience inertia positively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, experience inertia, is added to the relationship between coupled open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-31 was constructed to test the experience inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-32, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of EI on COI and IP (Model 23)

Table 6-107 shows that the SRMR values of 0.060 and 0.056 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.283 and 0.248, and the d_G are 0.135 and 0.129, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 284.641 and 265.382, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.868 and 0.877 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-31, the R-square for COI to IP is 0.312, indicating the explanatory power of COI on IP is 31.2%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-107, Model Fit for Model 23

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.060	0.056
d_ULS	0.283	0.248
d_G	0.135	0.129
Chi- square	284.641	265.382
NFI	0.868	0.877

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-108, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-108, Convergent Validity for Model 23

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
COI		0.832	0.898	0.747
Ac1	0.908			
Ac2	0.898			
Re1	0.780			
EI		0.757	0.861	0.674
EI3	0.862			
EI5	0.840			
EI6	0.756			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.840			
IP2	0.768			
IP3	0.840			
IP4	0.865			

IP6	0.880			
IP7	0.670			
EI x COI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-109 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 23, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-109, Discriminant Validity for Model 23

	COI	EI	IP
COI	0.864		
EI	0.427	0.821	
IP	0.433	0.463	0.814

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-110 shows the path coefficient of 0.225 and the T statistic of 4.496, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the COI can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.279 and the T statistic of 4.583, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the EI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-110, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 23

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
COI -> IP	0.225	0.229	0.050	4.496	0.000
EI -> IP	0.279	0.284	0.061	4.583	0.000
EI x COI -> IP	-0.155	-0.152	0.042	3.666	0.000

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-110 shows the path coefficient of -0.155 and the T statistic of 3.666, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000. Table 6-111 shows that the f-square of EI x COI to IP is 0.044, more significant than 0.025, indicating a large moderating impact. Table 6-112 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of COI to IP changed from 0.433 to 0.225, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 9.183 and 4.496, respectively, indicating that the moderator EI significantly negatively impacts the relationship between COI and IP.

Table 6-111, f-square for Model 23

Path	f-square
COI -> IP	0.054
EI -> IP	0.084
EI x COI -> IP	0.044

Table 6-112, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 23

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
COI -> IP	0.433	0.225	0.208
(T)	(9.183)	(4.496)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low EI condition (EI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between COI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of EI, the impact of COI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high EI condition (EI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low experience inertia, an increase in the inside-out open innovation model has a more pronounced impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, the line tends to straighten for the high EI condition, indicating that at higher levels of experience inertia, the increase in coupled open innovation does not lead to a

similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of COI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher experience inertia weakens the relationship between the coupled open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-32 highlights that the impact of COI on IP varies depending on the level of EI. Low EI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of COI on IP, while high EI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of COI on IP due to experience inertia.

Figure 6-33, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 23

6.5.8 Procedural Inertia – Outside-in Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9g (Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, procedural inertia, is added to the relationship between outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-33 was constructed to test the procedural inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-34, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of PI on OIOI and IP (Model 24)

Table 6-113 shows that the SRMR values of 0.063 and 0.062 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.311 and 0.299, and the d_G are 0.145 and 0.143, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 309.099 and 302.528, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.862 and 0.865 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-33, the R-square for OIOI to IP is 0.303, indicating the explanatory power of OIOI on IP is 30.3%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-113, Model Fit for Model 24

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.063	0.062
d_ULS	0.311	0.299
d_G	0.145	0.143
Chi- square	309.099	302.528
NFI	0.862	0.865

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-114, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-114, Convergent Validity for Model 24

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
OIOI		0.846	0.907	0.765
So2	0.806			
So3	0.896			
So4	0.918			
PI		0.781	0.872	0.694
EI3	0.858			
EI5	0.878			
EI6	0.759			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.662
IP1	0.849			
IP2	0.761			
IP3	0.839			
IP4	0.858			

IP6	0.884			
IP7	0.668			
PI x OIOI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-115 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 24, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-115, Discriminant Validity for Model 24

	IP	OIOI	PI
IP	0.813		
OIOI	0.427	0.874	
PI	0.43	0.258	0.833

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-116 shows the path coefficient of 0.332 and the T statistic of 7.060, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the OIOI can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.322 and the T statistic of 7.248, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the PI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-116, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 24

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
OIOI -> IP	0.332	0.334	0.047	7.060	0.000
PI -> IP	0.322	0.325	0.044	7.248	0.000
PI x OIOI -> IP	-0.083	-0.085	0.039	2.141	0.032

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-116 shows the path coefficient of -0.158 and the T statistic of 4.566, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000. Table 6-117 shows that the f-square of PI x OIOI to IP is 0.015, less than 0.025 but more significant than 0.01, indicating a medium moderating impact. Table 6-118 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of OIOI to IP changed from 0.428 to 0.332, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 8.645 and 7.060, respectively, indicating that the moderator PI significantly negatively impacts the relationship between OIOI and IP.

Table 6-117, f-square for Model 24

Path	f-square
OIOI -> IP	0.147
PI -> IP	0.134
PI x OIOI -> IP	0.015

Table 6-118, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 24

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
OIOI -> IP	0.428	0.332	0.096
(T)	(8.645)	(7.060)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low PI condition (PI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between OIOI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of PI, the impact of OIOI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high PI condition (PI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low procedural inertia, an increase in the outside-in open innovation model has a more pronounced impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, the line tends to straighten for the high EI condition, indicating that at higher levels of procedural inertia, the increase in outside-in open innovation does

not lead to a similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of OIOI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher procedural inertia weakens the relationship between the outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-34 highlights that the impact of OIOI on IP varies depending on the level of PI. Low PI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of OIOI on IP, while high PI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of OIOI on IP due to procedural inertia.

Figure 6-35, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 24

6.5.9 Procedural Inertia – Inside-out Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9h (Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting an inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, procedural inertia, is added to the relationship between inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-35 was constructed to test the procedural inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-36, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of PI on IOOI and IP (Model 25)

Table 6-119 shows that the SRMR values of 0.061 and 0.060 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.293 and 0.279, and the d_G are 0.150 and 0.147, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 319.999 and 311.832, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.854 and 0.857 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-35, the R-square for IOOI to IP is 0.226, indicating the explanatory power of IOOI on IP is 22.6%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-119, Model Fit for Model 25

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.061	0.060
d_ULS	0.293	0.279
d_G	0.150	0.147
Chi- square	319.999	311.832
NFI	0.854	0.857

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-120, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-120, Convergent Validity for Model 25

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
IOOI		0.846	0.907	0.764
Se1	0.867			
Se2	0.863			
Se4	0.893			
PI		0.781	0.872	0.694
PI1	0.858			
PI3	0.878			
PI5	0.759			
IP		0.896	0.920	0.661
IP1	0.852			
IP2	0.761			
IP3	0.844			
IP4	0.862			

IP6	0.883			
IP7	0.653			
PI x IOOI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-121 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 25, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-121, Discriminant Validity for Model 25

	IOOI	IP	PI
IOOI	0.874		
IP	0.305	0.813	
PI	0.372	0.433	0.833

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-122 shows the path coefficient of 0.135 and the T statistic of 1.893, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, slightly higher than the commonly used significance level (e.g., 0.05), suggesting that we cannot establish statistical significance for this path coefficient of IOOI on IP. The path coefficient of 0.328 and the T statistic of 6.584, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the PI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-122, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 25

Path	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
IOOI -> IP	0.135	0.137	0.071	1.893	0.058
PI -> IP	0.328	0.333	0.05	6.584	0.000
PI x IOOI ->	-0.118	-0.116	0.056	2.090	0.037

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-122 shows the path coefficient of -0.118 and the T statistic of 2.090, with a corresponding p-value of 0.037. Table 6-123 shows that the f-square of PI x IOOI to IP is 0.019, less than 0.025 but more significant than 0.01, indicating a medium moderating impact. Table 6-124 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of IOOI to IP changed from 0.306 to 0.135, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 4.451 and 1.893, respectively, indicating that the moderator PI significantly negatively impacts the relationship between IOOI and IP.

Table 6-123, f-square for Model 25

Path	f-square
IOOI -> IP	0.019
PI -> IP	0.108
PI x IOOI -> IP	0.019

Table 6-124, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 25

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
IOOI -> IP	0.306	0.135	0.171
(T)	(4.451)	(1.893)	

Simple Slope Analysis

For the low PI condition (PI at -1 SD), the line representing the relationship between IOOI and IP is much steeper, indicating that at a low level of PI, the impact of IOOI on IP is significantly stronger compared to the high PI condition (PI at +1 SD). In other words, when enterprises have low procedural inertia, an increase in the inside-out open innovation model has a more

pronounced impact on improving innovation performance. On the other hand, the line tends to straighten for the high EI condition, indicating that at higher levels of procedural inertia, the increase in inside-out open innovation does not lead to a similar change in open innovation. In this model, the impact of IOOI on IP becomes weaker or less influential. Therefore, higher procedural inertia weakens the relationship between the inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance. In summary, Figure 6-36 highlights that the impact of IOOI on IP varies depending on the level of PI. Low PI intensifies the relationship, indicating a stronger influence of IOOI on IP, while high PI weakens the relationship, indicating a reduced impact of IOOI on IP due to procedural inertia.

Figure 6-37, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 25

6.5.10 Procedural Inertia – Coupled Open Innovation Model and Innovation Performance

According to hypothesis H9i (Procedural inertia negatively moderates the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs), the moderating variable, procedural inertia, is added to the relationship between coupled open

innovation model and innovation performance, and the PLS model shown in Figure 6-37 was constructed to test the procedural inertia moderating impact.

Figure 6-38, Path Model of the Moderating Impact of PI on COI and IP (Model 26)

Table 6-125 shows that the SRMR values of 0.063 and 0.061 suggest a good fit for the saturated and estimated models. The d_{ULS} are 0.306 and 0.293, and the d_G are 0.146 and 0.144, indicating a moderate degree of freedom in this path of both models. The Chi-square values are 313.305 and 306.423, which can be used to compare the fit of different models. The NFI value of 0.856 and 0.860 suggests a good fit for both models. The estimated model performs better on all indicators and fits the saturated model better. Based on Figure 6-37, the R-square for COI to IP is 0.312, indicating the explanatory power of COI on IP is 31.2%, which means that there are other impact factors on entrepreneurial innovation performance. The Bootstrap method was then used to calculate the T statistic and p values for each model parameter and to analyse the significance of the relationship between the effects of the latent variables.

Table 6-125, Model Fit for Model 26

	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0.063	0.061
d_ULS	0.306	0.293
d_G	0.146	0.144
Chi- square	313.305	306.423
NFI	0.856	0.860

Convergent Validity

As shown in Table 6-126, the factor loadings for all latent variables containing the measures were more significant than 0.5 and significant at the $P < 0.001$ level, indicating good reliability of the measures. The Cronbach's alpha coefficients for the three latent variables were more significant than 0.5, and the reliability of the sample data was acceptable. The C.R. of the latent variables was more significant than 0.7, indicating good internal consistency and a high correlation between the latent variable measures. The AVEs were all greater than 0.5, indicating that the variation explained by the indicator variables by the latent variables was more than 50%.

Table 6-126, Convergent Validity for Model 26

	Outer Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	C.R.	AVE
COI		0.832	0.898	0.747
Ac1	0.908			
Ac2	0.898			
Re1	0.780			
PI		0.781	0.872	0.694
PI1	0.857			
PI3	0.878			
PI5	0.759			
IP		0.896	0.921	0.661
IP1	0.846			
IP2	0.767			
IP3	0.842			
IP4	0.864			

IP6	0.880			
IP7	0.659			
PI x COI	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Discriminant Validity

Table 6-127 shows that the path correlation coefficients between the three latent variables are less than the SQRT (AVE) of the three latent variables, indicating good discriminant validity in model 26, based on the Fornell-Larcker Criterion.

Table 6-127, Discriminant Validity for Model 26

	COI	IP	PI
COI	0.864		
IP	0.433	0.813	
PI	0.217	0.43	0.833

Note. The element on the diagonal represents SQRT(AVE)

Path Coefficient Analysis

Table 6-128 shows the path coefficient of 0.340 and the T statistic of 7.637, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggesting that the COI can positively and significantly impact IP directly. The path coefficient of 0.334 and the T statistic of 7.912, with a corresponding p-value of 0.000, suggests that the PI can positively and significantly impact IP directly.

Table 6-128, Path Coefficient Analysis for Model 26

	Path Coefficient	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
COI -> IP	0.340	0.342	0.045	7.637	0.000
PI -> IP	0.334	0.337	0.042	7.912	0.000
PI x COI -> IP	-0.062	-0.063	0.040	1.555	0.120

Moderating Impact Analysis

Table 6-128 shows the path coefficient of -0.062 and the T statistic of 1.555, with a corresponding p-value of 0.120. Table 6-129 shows that the f-square of PI x COI to IP is 0.009, less than 0.01, indicating no moderating impact. Table 6-130 shows the path coefficient difference before and after moderation, with the path coefficient of COI to IP changed from 0.433 to 0.340, and the T statistics for the two path coefficients are 9.183 and 7.637, respectively, indicating that the moderator PI does not significantly impact the relationship between COI and IP.

Table 6-129, f-square for Model 26

Path	f-square
COI -> IP	0.153
PI -> IP	0.145
PI x COI -> IP	0.009

Table 6-130, Path Coefficient Difference after Moderating for Model 26

Path	Path Coefficient Before	Path Coefficient After	Difference
COI -> IP	0.433	0.340	0.093
(T)	(9.183)	(7.637)	

Simple Slope Analysis

Figure 6-39, Simple Slope Analysis for Model 26

6.6 Summary of Research Hypotheses Test

Table 6-131 and Table 6-131 cont. summarise the hypotheses test results in Chapter Six. We can draw the following research findings by analysing the data of 349 technology-based SMEs. (1) Adopting open innovation by technology-based SMEs directly impacts innovation performance. Adopting an outside-in or coupled open innovation model significantly positively impacts innovation performance, fully supporting hypotheses H1a and H1b. However, the direct positive impact of adopting an inside-out open innovation model on innovation performance is not entirely significant; hence, hypothesis H1c is only partially supported by the above data analysis.

(2) Adopting various open innovation models by technology-based SMEs can positively and effectively construct and renew the absorptive capability of enterprises, no matter whether outside-in, inside-out or coupled open innovation model. Hypotheses H2a, H2b and H2c are fully supported. The

absorptive capability of technology-based SMEs can also significantly and positively impact innovation performance, which hypothesis H3 is fully supported. Moreover, the absorptive capability mediates the relationship between adopting open innovation models and the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs with a complementary mediating role in all three open innovation models. Therefore, hypotheses H4a, H4b and H4c are fully supported by data analysis.

(3) The test results for hypotheses related to dynamic capabilities are similar to absorptive capability. Adopting various open innovation models by technology-based SMEs can positively and effectively construct and renew the dynamic capabilities of enterprises, no matter whether outside-in, inside-out or coupled open innovation model. Hypotheses H5a, H5b and H5c are fully supported. The dynamic capabilities of technology-based SMEs can also significantly and positively impact innovation performance, which hypothesis H6 is fully supported. Moreover, the dynamic capabilities mediate the relationship between adopting open innovation models and the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs with a complementary mediating role in all three open innovation models. Therefore, hypotheses H7a, H7b and H7c are fully supported by data analysis.

(4) Cognitive inertia, including learning, experience and procedural inertia, can directly and positively impact the innovation performance, indicating that hypotheses H8a and H8b are fully supported, but the above data analysis does not support hypothesis H8c. Moreover, the three kinds of cognitive inertia can negatively moderate the relationship between adopting various open innovation models and innovation performance in technology-based SMEs. Learning inertia can largely moderate the relationship between adopting each open innovation model and innovation performance. Experience inertia can also largely moderate the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance.

Procedural inertia can moderate the relationship between adopting an outside-in and inside-out open innovation model and innovation performance; in the same way, experience inertia can moderate the relationship between adopting an outside-in open innovation model and innovation performance. However, experience inertia does not have a moderating role in the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance, and procedural inertia does not have a moderating role in the relationship between adopting a coupled open innovation model and innovation performance. The significance of the above two moderating impacts is not significant as well. Therefore, hypotheses H9a, H9b, H9c, H9d, H9e, H9f, and H9i are not supported; but the data analysis fully supports hypotheses H9g and H9h.

Table 6-131, Summary of the Hypotheses Test Results in Chapter 6

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6	Model 7	Model 8	Model 9	Model 10	Model 11	Model 12	Model 13	Model 14	
H1a	0.428 (0.000)			0.297 (0.000)			0.321 (0.000)					0.313 (0.000)			Fully Support
H1b		0.306 (0.000)		0.112 (0.099)				0.181 (0.020)					0.175 (0.021)		Partial Support
H1c			0.433 (0.000)	0.295 (0.000)					0.322 (0.000)					0.331 (0.000)	Fully Support
H2a					0.238 (0.000)		0.376 (0.000)								Fully Support
H2b					0.254 (0.000)			0.357 (0.000)							Fully Support
H2c					0.202 (0.002)				0.401 (0.000)						Fully Support
H3						0.408 (0.000)	0.281 (0.000)	0.343 (0.000)	0.276 (0.000)						Fully Support
H4a							CMPL (0.001)								Fully Support
H4b								CMPL (0.020)							Fully Support
H4c									CMPL (0.000)						Fully Support

H5a										0.301 (0.000)		0.427 (0.000)			Fully Support
H5b										0.219 (0.000)			0.333 (0.000)		Fully Support
H5c										0.193 (0.000)				0.367 (0.000)	Fully Support
H6											0.398 (0.000)	0.262 (0.000)	0.333 (0.000)	0.275 (0.000)	Fully Support
H7a												CMPL (0.001)			Fully Support
H7b													CMPL (0.000)		Fully Support
H7c														CMPL (0.000)	Fully Support

Table 6-131, Summary of the Hypotheses Test Results in Chapter 6 Continued

	Model 15	Model 16	Model 17	Model 18	Model 19	Model 20	Model 21	Model 22	Model 23	Model 24	Model 25	Model 26	
H1a				0.332 (0.000)			0.250 (0.000)			0.332 (0.000)			Fully Support
H1b					0.131 (0.060)			0.114 (0.131)			0.135 (0.058)		Partial Support
H1c						0.315 (0.000)			0.225 (0.000)			0.340 (0.000)	Fully Support

H2a	Fully Support
H2b	Fully Support
H2c	Fully Support
H3	Fully Support
H4a	Fully Support
H4b	Fully Support
H4c	Fully Support
H5a	Fully Support
H5b	Fully Support
H5c	Fully Support
H6	Fully Support
H7a	Fully Support

H7b											Fully Support	
H7c											Fully Support	
H8a	0.399 (0.000)		0.296 (0.000)	0.292 (0.000)	0.234 (0.000)						Fully Support	
H8b		0.463 (0.000)				0.294 (0.000)	0.401 (0.000)	0.279 (0.000)			Fully Support	
H8c			0.434 (0.000)						0.332 (0.000)	0.328 (0.000)	0.334 (0.000)	Not Support
H9a				-0.158 (0.000)								Not Support
H9b					-0.182 (0.000)							Not Support
H9c						-0.138 (0.000)						Not Support
H9d							-0.106 (0.018)					Not Support
H9e								-0.022 (0.678)				Not Support
H9f									-0.155 (0.000)			Not Support
H9g										-0.083 (0.032)		Fully Support

H9h	-0.018 (0.037)	Fully Support
H9i	-0.062 (0.120)	Not Support

Note. Numbers in the brackets indicate the significance level of the path coefficient.

CMPL is short for complementary mediating impact.

Chapter 7. Research Findings and Conclusions

Through the analysis of the data on 349 technology-based SMEs and the tests of the research hypotheses above, we can draw the following conclusions. By adopting an open innovation model, technology-based SMEs in China can effectively improve their innovation performance. There are three primary paths for technology-based SMEs to enhance their innovation performance through adopting the open innovation model: First, to directly acquire or create enterprise innovation performance through implementing the open innovation model (direct path). The second is to construct or renew the absorptive and dynamic capabilities of the enterprise through the implementation of the open innovation model and to transform internal and external knowledge into the innovation performance of the enterprise through the absorptive and dynamic capabilities (indirect path). Thirdly, through both direct and indirect paths, the innovation performance of the enterprise can be improved. Cognitive inertia can contribute to innovation performance by adopting open innovation models to improve innovation performance. However, at the same time, it can also have a significant negative moderating effect on the relationship between the adoption of open innovation models and innovation performance, thus inhibiting the improvement of open innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. The research findings are presented in this chapter, and based on that information, the conclusion and implications are shown as follows. Last but not least, a summary of the research limitations and further study plans are included in this chapter.

7.1 Research Findings

7.1.1 Findings for Direct Impact of Open Innovation Models on Innovation Performance

Adopting open innovation can benefit the innovation performance of a technology-based enterprise. The contribution of the adopting outside-in open innovation model to the achievement of innovation performance is 18.3%, the

contribution of the inside-out open innovation model is 9.4%, the contribution of the coupled open innovation model is 18.7%, and the contribution of the three open models together is 28.8%, indicating that the technology-based SMEs can create and obtain more innovation performance by adopting the three innovation models at the same time. The survey data shows that China's technology-based SMEs implement the outside-in open innovation model mainly using knowledge sourcing, the inside-out open innovation model mainly using knowledge selling strategies, and the coupled open innovation model using a combination of knowledge acquiring and revealing strategies.

7.1.2 Findings for Absorptive Capability-Related Analysis

Implementing open innovation models by technology-based SMEs contributed 26.7% to constructing or renewing absorptive capability. The coefficient of the impact of the outside-in open innovation model on absorptive capability is 0.238, the coefficient of the impact of the inside-out model is 0.254, and the coefficient of the impact of the coupled model is 0.202, suggesting that technology-based SMEs are more evenly using acquiring, sourcing, selling and revealing to influence their absorptive capability, but there is potential for further exploration. The absorptive capability has a 16.7% contribution to the creation and acquisition of innovation performance, suggesting that absorptive capability is one of the relatively essential factors in the acquisition and creation of innovation performance by technology-based SMEs. Absorptive capability is tested to have a complementary mediating role in all three open innovation models. In other words, the positive impact of adopting the three open innovation models on innovation performance is further optimised by the collaboration of absorptive capability, suggesting a synergy between the open innovation models and absorptive capability, which mutually reinforce each other and have a positive impact on innovation performance.

7.1.3 Findings for Dynamic Capabilities-Related Analysis

The contribution of implementing open innovation models by technology-based SMEs to the construction or renewal of dynamic capabilities reached 28.3%. The impact coefficient of the outside-in open innovation model on dynamic capabilities is 0.301, the inside-out coefficient of the inside-out model is 0.219, and the impact coefficient of the coupled model is 0.193, indicating that technology-based SMEs have not fully utilised the acquiring, selling and revealing strategies of the inside-out and coupled open innovation models to release resources to build up the dynamic capabilities of the enterprise. Enterprise dynamic capabilities have a 15.9% contribution to the creation and obtaining of innovation performance, indicating that dynamic capabilities are indeed one of the relatively significant factors in obtaining and creating innovation performance in technology-based SMEs. Dynamic capabilities are also tested to have a complementary mediating role in all three open innovation models, indicating that dynamic capabilities act as an intermediary mechanism that enhances the relationship between adopting open innovation models and innovation performance. In other words, dynamic capabilities amplify the positive impact of open innovation models on innovation performance.

7.1.4 Findings for the Moderating Role of Cognitive Inertia

Cognitive inertia has a significant positive effect on the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs, indicating that cognitive inertia can help the achievement of innovation performance in technology-based SMEs. Most studies have concluded that each of the three cognitive inertia has a negative direct effect on innovation performance (Fan & Gao, 2016; Li & Zeng, 2019), which is not consistent with the findings of this research. From a positive impact perspective, cognitive inertia positively impacts innovation performance because by leveraging previous experience and knowledge, individuals or organisations can tackle innovation challenges more efficiently and thus improve innovation performance. Cognitive inertia enables them to quickly identify and exploit potential innovation opportunities and translate their knowledge and resources into innovation outcomes.

However, cognitive inertia generally has a significant negative moderating effect on the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance. The moderating coefficients of learning inertia on the relationship between outside-in, inside-out and coupled open innovation models and innovation performance were -0.158, -0.182 and -0.138. The moderating coefficients of experience inertia on the relationship between outside-in and coupled open innovation models and performance were -0.106 and -0.152 but not significant for the relationship between outside-in and innovation performance. The moderating coefficients of procedural inertia on outside-in and inside-out open innovation models and innovation performance were -0.083 and -0.118, but the moderating relationship between the coupled open innovation model and innovation performance is insignificant. The above may be because the open innovation model emphasises sharing knowledge and resources with external partners and driving innovation through open communication and collaboration. However, individuals or organisations with high cognitive inertia prefer to maintain their knowledge and control in the innovation process and hold back from external innovation collaboration, thus hindering the smooth implementation of innovation collaboration and ultimately affecting the improvement of innovation performance.

7.2 Conclusions

7.2.1 Generalisability

In this thesis, the object of study is SMEs. SMEs in this context are further qualified by two qualifications, namely technology-based SMEs and China. Therefore, the generalisability of the results of this study will be analysed starting with the research object. Firstly, the theoretical and practical significance of the results of this research is based on SMEs and can be generalised to micro and small enterprises (MSEs). SMEs and MSEs have certain commonalities in terms of the size of the enterprise, the availability of capital, and the application of innovation resources. However, given some

differences between large enterprises and SMEs regarding internal R&D investment, capital availability, and enterprise visibility, this study can only be partially generalised to large enterprises.

In the study of this thesis, the primary interest is in technology-based SMEs. The reason for this is that in the previous pilot study, the executives of technology-based SMEs were more concerned about the open innovation model, but this does not indicate that the findings of this research are only applicable to technology-based SMEs. On the contrary, executives from SMEs in other industries were more prominent in the pilot study's findings, especially in cognitive inertia towards open innovation. Many executives even resisted open innovation because of cognitive inertia. Therefore, in addition to technology-based SMEs, the findings of this research paper can be generalised to other industries, but it is still necessary to analyse specific issues.

As for the research object of this paper being SMEs in China, this is because of data availability. However, caution needs to be maintained regarding the generalisability of the findings in this study across geographical areas. The culture and values of different countries may affect enterprises' attitudes and practices towards open innovation. Some countries may be more inclined to encourage collaboration, knowledge sharing and innovation, while others may emphasise competition and protecting intellectual property rights. Laws and regulations in different countries may affect enterprises' activities in open innovation. Intellectual property protection, contract regulations, antitrust laws, etc., may impact enterprises' innovation collaboration and knowledge sharing. The market environment in different countries may impact SMEs' open innovation. Factors such as the market size, the degree of competition, and consumer demand may influence whether firms are willing to open up and collaborate on innovation and with whom. National government policies and support measures may also influence SMEs' behaviour towards open

innovation. Some countries may encourage enterprises to engage in open innovation through policies that provide financial support, tax incentives, etc.

Furthermore, in the research process of this paper, the authors set the independent variables as adopting different open innovation models, the dependent variable as innovation performance, and the intermediate variables as absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities, and cognitive inertia. In this way, they established structural models for correlation studies. This type of correlation study and the quantitative analysis process included in the study can be generalised to other studies on the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance. However, for the different intermediate variables and the items to be measured in the questionnaires to which they respond, specific kinds of literature are needed to provide sophisticated measurement scales to ensure the rigour and accuracy of the study.

7.2.2 Theoretical Implications

(1) Technology-based SMEs can utilise a variety of open innovation modes to directly or indirectly create and obtain innovation performance

The research on the relationship between open innovation and enterprise innovation performance is controversial among scholars. This thesis finds through empirical tests that both coupled and outside-in open innovation strategies significantly impact enterprise innovation performance. The coupled open innovation has the most significant impact, followed by the outside-in type, suggesting that technology-based SMEs must sell their innovations faster to cover their R&D costs. Such enterprises are small in scale and have little capital, and they need to continuously shorten the commercialisation time of their R&D results to help them gain innovation performance. Through the mediating role of absorptive and dynamic capabilities, three open innovation modes of technology-based SMEs can have a significant indirect effect on

innovation performance, and absorptive and dynamic capabilities have an essential mediating role in the relationship between adopting three open innovation modes and innovation performance.

The main task of outside-in open innovation is to establish connections with external diversified knowledge sources and acquire external diversified knowledge. After the external knowledge flows into the enterprise, it needs to enter the various links of technological innovation through the knowledge management process and finally integrate with the original knowledge base of the enterprise, update the knowledge base, help the enterprise create new products or technologies, and obtain the innovation performance through the sale or disclosure of the products or technologies. Therefore, the outside-in open innovation model can transform the acquired external knowledge into a knowledge base through knowledge capability, then apply it to the process of technological innovation, and finally, according to the changes of technology and market environment, continuously adjust the allocation of knowledge resources of the enterprise to produce products and technologies to meet the market demand, to obtain the innovation performance.

Inside-out open innovation can sell underutilised technologies of the enterprises through technology trading and directly capture innovation performance through the sale of new products. However, this model may face many challenges. One of them involves intellectual property rights, confidentiality and control concerns. SMEs may face difficulties in protecting intellectual property rights, ensuring technology confidentiality and maintaining control over external innovations, which may affect their ability to obtain direct innovation revenues in the market. Second, SMEs may be relatively small and may have low market recognition, and thus may have difficulty gaining sufficient attention and recognition when selling external innovations. This may make consumers, investors and partners reserved about their innovations, thus impacting the achievement of innovation revenues. This

may make consumers, investors and partners reserved about their innovations, thus impacting the achievement of innovation revenues.

Coupled OI can generate direct economic gains through the sale of technology and new products, or it can generate strategic gains by selectively disclosing some of the enterprise's proprietary technology or intellectual property for free and making it available to external organisations and individuals. Of course, coupled OI can also capture external knowledge through knowledge search, similar to outside-in OI, and thus capture innovation performance.

(2) Absorptive and dynamic capabilities have a critical bridging role in transforming external knowledge into innovation performance in the implementation of open innovation in technology-based SMEs

Both absorptive and dynamic capabilities significantly mediate the relationship between the impact of outside-in, coupled and inside-out open innovation on innovation performance. This suggests that enterprises need the participation of absorptive and dynamic capabilities in transforming external knowledge into innovation performance, and they need to add to the transformation of external knowledge. Both absorptive and dynamic capabilities have complementary mediate roles between outside-in, coupled and inside-out open innovation models and innovation performance. Therefore, SMEs' absorptive and dynamic capabilities are critical internal mechanisms for transforming external knowledge into innovation performance and play a key bridging role.

(3) Technology-based SMEs can establish or update dynamic capabilities by utilising the open innovation model

Outside-in, coupled, and inside-out open innovation modes significantly affect enterprises' dynamic capabilities, indicating that implementing open innovation is conducive to forming dynamic capabilities by technology-based SMEs. In the process of searching for external innovation sources and purchasing external technologies, outside-in open innovation can perceive changes in the external market, technology and competitive environment, thus requiring managers to change the structure of the enterprise's internal knowledge base to enable it to integrate with external knowledge and update the existing knowledge base. Coupled open innovation considers both the integration of external knowledge and the external utilisation of internal knowledge. As a result, enterprises can both perceive changes in the external environment and capture changes in market demand in the external utilization of R&D results, thereby adjusting the channels and modes of external utilization and grasping market opportunities. Inside-out open innovation mainly perceives changes in the technology market environment, identifies technology trading opportunities, and thus effectively realises technology sales and adapts to changes in the technology market environment by releasing technology resources.

Therefore, the openness of innovation brought by the open innovation strategy enables enterprises to search and acquire from outside the source of innovative knowledge needed for enterprise R&D and also enables enterprises to continuously sell or disclose R&D results to potential customers in the market in the process generating sufficient R&D and commercialisation capabilities to adapt to changes in the external environment and to realise the transformation of internal and external innovation resources into innovation performance.

(4) Cognitive inertia hinders the process of transforming internal and external knowledge into innovation performance in open innovation in technology-based SMEs

Senior managers have cognitive limitations and are inevitably resistant to the inflow of external knowledge. In the process of open innovation, "non-local invention" and "non-local sales" fully reflect the cognitive barriers of senior management to the inflow of external knowledge and the outflow of internal knowledge in the process of technological innovation. The key to the effective implementation of open innovation and the creation of innovation performance lies in the smooth flow of external and internal knowledge across the boundaries of the enterprise, thereby enabling learning activities at the organisational boundaries. Any obstacle to knowledge flow will reduce innovation performance. Knowledge resources are essential innovation resources for enterprises, which need to search, identify, digest and utilise external knowledge in perceiving, grasping and utilising market opportunities. The cognitive inertia of corporate management will hinder the absorption and utilisation of external knowledge, thus inhibiting the formation of dynamic capabilities and reducing the acquisition of innovation performance. At the same time, cognitive inertia will affect the innovation ability and behaviour of individual members, reduce the efficiency and performance of corporate organisational learning, and then affect the innovation ability of the enterprise, hindering the acquisition of innovation performance.

7.2.3 Practical Implications

(1) Adopting multiple open innovation models can positively contribute to the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs.

From the empirical results, the primary strategy of China's technology-based SMEs adopting the outside-in OI model is sourcing, the primary strategy of the inside-out OI model is selling, and the primary strategy of the coupled OI model is acquiring and revealing. The innovation performance obtained by adopting different OI models is not the same. Among them, the coupled OI model contributes most to innovation performance, followed by the outside-in OI model and the inside-out OI model. Thus, technology-based SMEs' multiple open innovation models can enhance innovation performance.

As Chinese technology-based SMEs lack internal innovation resources and capabilities, actively seeking external innovation cooperation is the primary way to alleviate this dilemma. Due to their small size and limited resources, technology-based SMEs will choose to diversify their open innovation model rather than a single model when dealing with the changing external environment to reduce the risk of internal innovation caused by the changing environment. With limited R&D funds, technology-based SMEs need to sell their new products and technologies quickly to recover their R&D funds and profit, so they focus on using outside-in open innovation models to improve their innovation performance. While selling new products and technologies in the product and technology market, enterprises must continue acquiring new external knowledge to ensure sustained innovation performance. They must seek partnerships with enterprises that can complement their innovation processes to innovate products and technologies jointly. In addition, the selective and free disclosure of some of the enterprise's products and technologies can test the market's reaction to them and provide a basis for developing further technologies and products. The contribution of the outside-in open innovation model to innovation performance is small, as enterprises have limited R&D funds, do not purchase and search for external technologies daily, and do not have sufficient internal innovation capabilities to absorb and utilise external technologies.

Therefore, depending on the external market, technology and competitive environment, technology-based SMEs can adopt a combination of open innovation models and fully use the advantages of each open innovation model to obtain more diverse external knowledge for the innovation process, thus improving their innovation performance.

(2) Improving absorptive capability is necessary for technology-based enterprises to enhance innovation performance.

The absorptive capability has a significant positive impact on innovation performance, suggesting that absorptive capability can help enterprises to effectively absorb and transform valuable external resources, accelerate the pace of internalisation and produce products that better meet consumer demand. A test of the mediating role of absorptive capability concludes that absorptive capability plays a positive mediating role between open innovation and innovation performance. This is large because open innovation can flexibly use resources such as capital and information technology when building and integrating into innovation networks, which translates into economic or brand benefits through its strong absorptive capability. Therefore, enterprises must increase their absorptive capability through research and development, talent training and exchange. It is necessary to increase the scale and strength of enterprises' investment in research and development, build a stable team of innovative talents, establish learning groups within enterprises and encourage cross-departmental learning and exchange. At the same time, it is essential to establish a sound internal competition mechanism and create a talent think tank to provide a talent guarantee for improving the innovation performance of enterprises.

The collaborative development of open innovation and absorptive capability can drive innovation performance, and an insignificant increase in enterprise performance is likely to result from an imbalance in the development of one of these factors. If an enterprise is not well qualified and has a low absorptive capability to access external innovation resources, it will fail to transform external information effectively and find it challenging to improve its innovation performance through open innovation. Therefore, to improve innovation and increase performance, enterprises should seek to harmonise the development of open innovation and absorptive capability by taking full advantage of the size and nature of their attributes.

(3) Leveraging the mediating role of dynamic capabilities between open innovation models and innovation performance to enhance the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs

This research shows that dynamic capabilities have a complementary mediating role between the open innovation model and the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. Through an outside-in open innovation model, enterprises can transform innovations from external partners into commercialised products and services and bring them to market. Dynamic capabilities enable enterprises to respond quickly to market needs, flexibly adjust the characteristics of products and services, improve market competitiveness and thus maximise innovation performance. Through an inside-out open innovation model, innovation performance can be gained directly by selling the enterprise's new products and technologies to external markets. The ability to access new demand for products and technologies in external markets also facilitates the identification of new market opportunities and the exploitation and development of these opportunities, which requires dynamic capabilities to be transformed to realise the opportunity to performance transition. Through the coupled open innovation model, knowledge acquired from the outside still needs to be transformed into innovation performance through dynamic capabilities, while revealing internal knowledge to the outside world can perceive opportunities in the external market and thus grasp the next step in developing new products and technologies, which requires dynamic capabilities to transform that market opportunity into innovation performance.

Therefore, the key for technology-based SMEs to make full use of the mediating role of dynamic capabilities in the relationship between open innovation models and innovation performance is to make full use of entrepreneurs' social networks to establish cooperative relationships with a wide range of external institutions, organisations and individuals, and to introduce external knowledge into the enterprise through entrepreneurial capabilities to complement the internal innovation knowledge of the enterprise,

in order to effectively realise the reallocation and utilisation of resources and improve the conversion rate of innovation performance.

(4) Maintaining a moderate level of cognitive inertia to facilitate innovation performance and reduce barriers to the adoption of different open innovation models

Research shows that cognitive inertia has a significant and positive impact on the innovation performance of enterprises. In a knowledge-based economy, strong learning inertia motivates enterprises to continuously explore new sources of knowledge, acquire new and differentiated knowledge, develop new business areas, learn new scientific skills and creatively solve their challenges. Enterprises with solid learning inertia have stronger organisational adaptability and can better grasp future trends, innovate, and change promptly (Bakker &Knoben, 2015). The existence of experience inertia deepens an enterprise's understanding of and proficiency in the application of existing knowledge, which is conducive to maximising the value of existing knowledge and ensuring that the enterprise can make the most of its existing knowledge resources even in a turbulent social environment, in order to promote the continuous output of innovation (Huarng et al., 2020). The self-protection mentality brought by experience inertia will make enterprises choose new projects that match their strengths and can avoid some uncertain potential risks to improve the success rate of innovation and reduce unnecessary losses and wastage when developing new projects. Procedural inertia means enterprises have developed stable operating procedures and work processes. These procedures contain an accumulation of experience and knowledge that allows the enterprise to operate more efficiently and respond to change. This stability and accumulated knowledge are essential for innovative activities, as they provide a basis and reference for enterprises to help them make better use of resources and carry out innovative activities. Moreover, procedural inertia allows enterprises to develop an efficient automated approach to repetitive operations and activities. This allows enterprises to adapt and apply new knowledge and technologies more quickly

when carrying out innovative activities, thus reducing learning costs. By exploiting procedural inertia, enterprises can use existing resources and capabilities better, reducing the trial and error process and improving innovation performance.

However, there is a significant negative moderating impact on the relationship between adopting open innovation models and innovation performance, indicating that enterprises should also be alert to cognitive inertia while adopting the open innovation model. Enterprises relying too much on learning inertia may lead to a lack of adaptability to new open innovation models. Learning inertia makes enterprises more inclined to make judgements and decisions based on previous experience and knowledge, limiting the acceptance and application of new ideas and approaches. This may discourage the adoption of new open innovation models, thus negatively impacting innovation performance. Enterprises relying too much on experience inertia may lack flexibility towards different open innovation models. Experience inertia makes enterprises more inclined to follow previous successful experiences and resist changing and trying new ways of innovation. This may limit the adoption and application of different open innovation models and thus have a negative moderating effect on innovation performance. If enterprises rely too much on procedural inertia, this may limit the flexibility to apply different open innovation models. Procedural inertia makes enterprises more inclined to follow established procedures and protocols and may lack the flexibility and ability to adapt to new open innovation models. This may hinder the development of innovation activities and have a negative moderating effect on innovation performance. Thus, maintaining a balanced cognitive inertia is essential for technology-based enterprises to consider.

7.3 Research Limitations and Further Studies

(1) In this study, most of the variables in the model were derived from a summary of ideas from a pilot study based on grounded theory prior to the development of the formal questionnaire. Therefore, in studying the impact of the open innovation model on innovation performance, the authors have selected only some interesting intermediate impact factors that could be obtained. In the pilot study, keywords such as SMEs' concerns about the ownership of intellectual property rights and the leakage of their business secrets were also high on the list but not included in the research models. Therefore, a new study that includes intellectual property rights and leakage of business secrets as variables will be conducted in the future to research the impact of the open innovation model on innovation performance from another perspective.

(2) Due to the limited time available for the research, the data sample may not be large enough to reflect commonality. Furthermore, due to the nature and characteristics of technology-based SMEs, they are selected to be the only research subject. However, the research findings on adopting open innovation models and the impact of innovation performance by SMEs in various industries may vary. Therefore, another possible further research will cover more SMEs from different industries.

(3) In this study, the authors only considered the case of technology-based SMEs adopting a single outside-in, inside-out and coupled open innovation model. In reality, however, enterprises do not often differentiate so strictly between the open innovation models they adopt. Moreover, many combination open innovation models are also used in real production. In the combined application of these open innovation models, the inward and outward knowledge flows are not in a one-to-one ratio. Therefore, studying the impact of more complex combinations of open innovation models on innovation performance will also be a possible future research topic.

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Appendix

1. The Formal Questionnaire

Open Innovation Survey Questionnaire for Technology-based SMEs

Dear Madam/Mr:

Hello! This questionnaire investigates the impact of open innovation and innovation performance of technology-based SMEs, taking absorptive capability, dynamic capabilities and cognitive inertia as intermediate variables. There are no right or wrong answers, and the truthfulness of your answers is crucial to the study's accuracy. As the questionnaire is meant to be complete, any missing questions will be invalidated, so please answer all the questions carefully. Thank you very much!

We promise this study will be completed anonymously and not involve internal company confidentiality. All information provided by your company will be kept strictly confidential and will be used for academic research purposes only. We also promise not to release the information provided by your enterprise to any third party. Please feel free to answer as objectively as possible.

By completing and returning this questionnaire, I consent to the use of data collected for the research

A. I agree and understand the above statement (starting the questionnaire)

B. I am afraid I have to disagree with the above statement (end of the questionnaire)

Part 1, Basic information about your enterprise

1. The number of employees your company has now is ().

- A. Less than 100 people
- B. 100 – 200 people
- C. 201 – 300 people
- D. 301 – 400 people
- E. 401 – 500 people
- F. More than 500 people

2. Your enterprise has been established ().

- A. Less than one year
- B. 1 - 3 years
- C. 4 - 6 years
- D. 7 - 9 years
- E. 10 years or above

3. The proportion of scientific and technical personnel to the total enterprise employees is ().

- A. 30% (included) or more
- B. 25% (included) – 30%
- C. 20% (included) – 25%
- D. 15% (included) – 20%
- E. 10% (included) – 15%
- F. Less than 10%

4. The following description suits your enterprise's technological innovation process ().

- A. always rely on the enterprise's technology for research and development
- B. often purchase technology and intellectual property from the market for product development
- C. often look for external organisations to cooperate in research and

development

D. often sell technology and intellectual property that the enterprise does not use

E. selective or free disclosure of proprietary technology or knowledge of the enterprise's products to outside parties

Part 2, Measuring Open Innovation Strategies in Enterprise

	Item	1 = strongly disagreed 5 = strongly agreed				
Ac1	Enterprises regularly purchase and utilise new technologies or intellectual property from other enterprises or institutions	1	2	3	4	5
Ac2	Enterprises have a high proportion of outsourced R&D	1	2	3	4	5
So1	Enterprises regularly search for external ideas that have the potential to add value to the company	1	2	3	4	5
So2	The enterprise has a robust system for searching for external technology or intellectual property	1	2	3	4	5
So3	Enterprises are proactive in approaching external players for better technical knowledge or products	1	2	3	4	5
So4	Enterprises tend to develop closer relationships with external players and rely on their innovations	1	2	3	4	5
Se1	The enterprise proactively manages the flow of outgoing knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
Se2	Enterprises sell technical knowledge or intellectual property on the market in a formal way	1	2	3	4	5
Se3	Enterprises have a dedicated department for	1	2	3	4	5

	the commercialisation of intellectual assets					
Se4	The enterprise also welcomes other organisations or individuals to purchase and use the enterprise's technological knowledge or intellectual property	1	2	3	4	5
Se5	Enterprises rarely share their technical knowledge or intellectual property with external organisations	1	2	3	4	5
Re1	Enterprises often disclose proprietary information or knowledge about the products they develop for free	1	2	3	4	5
Re2	Enterprises may selectively relinquish some intellectual property for more significant gain	1	2	3	4	5

Part 3, Measuring Absorptive Capability Strategies in Enterprise

No.	Item	1 = strongly disagreed 5 = strongly agreed				
PAC1	Finding relevant industry information is a daily task for enterprises	1	2	3	4	5
PAC2	Enterprises obtain industry information through various channels	1	2	3	4	5
PAC3	External knowledge is acquired through contact with customers, suppliers, other enterprises or organisations	1	2	3	4	5
PAC4	Ideas and problems can be shared across departments within the enterprise	1	2	3	4	5
PAC5	Regular meetings are held to share achievements and problems that have arisen in the course of the enterprise's development	1	2	3	4	5
RAC1	The enterprise can identify opportunities from external knowledge quickly	1	2	3	4	5

RAC2	Employees can use external knowledge and apply it in their daily work	1	2	3	4	5
RAC3	Employees can link existing knowledge with new external knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
RAC4	The enterprise supports the development of new products and services	1	2	3	4	5
RAC5	The enterprise regularly considers technical issues and adapts to new knowledge	1	2	3	4	5

Part 4, Measuring Dynamic Capabilities Strategies in Enterprise

No.	Item	1 = strongly disagreed 5 = strongly agreed				
ASO1	Participation of enterprises in the activities of professional associations or conferences	1	2	3	4	5
ASO2	The enterprise uses established processes to identify target markets, changes in customer needs and user innovations	1	2	3	4	5
ASO3	Best practices can be observed in the enterprise sector	1	2	3	4	5
ASO4	Gathering of economic information on business operations and business environment management	1	2	3	4	5
ACO1	The enterprise is willing to invest in helping customers find solutions	1	2	3	4	5
ACO2	The enterprise adopts best practices in the sector	1	2	3	4	5
ACO3	The enterprise responds to deficiencies identified by employees	1	2	3	4	5
ACO4	Strong businesses change current practices when customers give them a reason to change	1	2	3	4	5
	The frequency with which, in the last five	1 = very infrequent				

	years, the following activities have occurred in the enterprise.	5 = very frequent				
ATO1	New or substantially changed enterprise strategies are implemented	1	2	3	4	5
ATO2	Implement new management methods	1	2	3	4	5
ATO3	New or substantially changed marketing methods or strategies	1	2	3	4	5
ATO4	Substantial renewal of business processes	1	2	3	4	5
ATO5	The new or material change in the way business objectives are achieved	1	2	3	4	5

Part 4, Measuring Cognitive Inertia in Enterprise

No.	Item	1 = strongly disagreed 5 = strongly agreed				
LI1	Enterprises will provide opportunities to learn new ideas or new methods	1	2	3	4	5
LI2	The enterprise will try to solve new problems in new ways	1	2	3	4	5
LI3	Enterprises try to learn new ideas to change the way they think and act	1	2	3	4	5
LI4	Enterprises often use different approaches to solve problems	1	2	3	4	5
LI5	Enterprises actively seek out new sources of knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
EI1	Enterprises are accustomed to using the same sources or channels to acquire knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
EI2	Enterprises rely heavily on past knowledge or experience	1	2	3	4	5
EI3	Previous knowledge and experience increase the efficiency of the department's work	1	2	3	4	5

EI4	Enterprises will use past experience to solve new problems	1	2	3	4	5
EI5	Enterprises often learn from past experience	1	2	3	4	5
EI6	Previous knowledge and experience affect the extent to which the enterprise accepts new knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
PI1	Enterprises will use the same procedures and methods to solve practical problems as in the past	1	2	3	4	5
PI2	Enterprises are not good at using insights to solve problems	1	2	3	4	5
PI3	The enterprise's strict operating procedures are not flexible and innovative	1	2	3	4	5
PI4	Enterprises are not keen to learn new ideas to change their thinking and behaviour	1	2	3	4	5
PI5	The enterprise's problem-solving strategies are predictable	1	2	3	4	5

Part 5, Measuring Innovation Performance in Enterprise

No.	Item					
IP1	New product quality for enterprises (1=very poor, 5=very good)	1	2	3	4	5
IP2	Number of new products in the enterprises (1=very little, 5=very much)	1	2	3	4	5
IP3	The proportion of enterprise new product sales to total sales (1=very low, 5=very high)	1	2	3	4	5
IP4	The speed at which the enterprise also develops new products (1=very slow, 5=very fast)	1	2	3	4	5
IP5	Cost of new product development for the	1	2	3	4	5

	enterprise (1=very low, 5=very high)					
IP6	The success rate of new product development in the enterprise (1=very low, 5=very high)	1	2	3	4	5
IP7	Number of patent applications or registrations by enterprises, too (1=very few, 5=very many)	1	2	3	4	5
IP8	Number of industry standards the enterprise has led in developing (1=very few, 5=very many)	1	2	3	4	5

This questionnaire ends here. We once again thank you for your generous and helpful support for this study, and we wish you a pleasant working day!

2. Questionnaire for the Polit Survey based on Grounded Theory

Open Innovation Survey Questionnaire for Chinese SMEs

Dear Madam/Mr:

Hello! This questionnaire investigates the impact of open innovation and the innovation performance of technology-based SMEs. There are no right or wrong answers, and the truthfulness of your answers is crucial to the study's accuracy. As the questionnaire is meant to be complete, any missing questions will be invalidated, so please answer all the questions carefully.

Thank you very much!

We promise this study will be completed anonymously and not involve internal company confidentiality. All information provided by your company will be kept strictly confidential and will be used for academic research purposes only. We also promise not to release the information provided by your enterprise to any third party. Please feel free to answer as objectively as possible.

By completing and returning this questionnaire, I consent to the use of data collected for the research

A. I agree and understand the above statement (starting the questionnaire)

B. I am afraid I have to disagree with the above statement (end of the questionnaire)

Question 1

What is your enterprise's primary business?

Question 2

Has your enterprise ever innovated a product (in any form)? What were the inputs and outputs, and are you satisfied with your innovation experience?

Question 3

Has your enterprise ever practised closed innovation, and does it have a dedicated innovation team? What is the research and innovation team's approximate annual input and output?

Question 4

Has your enterprise ever practised open innovation? Has it worked with universities or specialised research institutes on a long-term or short-term basis, and what is the approximate annual input and output to the research and innovation team?

Question 5

If your enterprise has not practised open innovation, is there any intention to do so?

Question 6

(Assuming) Your enterprise is practising open innovation; what are your expectations of open innovation?

Question 7

(Assuming) Your enterprise is practising open innovation; what are your biggest concerns?

Question 8

(Assuming) Your enterprise insists on closed innovation (refuses to do open innovation); what would be your reasons for this?

Question 9

Do you have any other personal opinions about open innovation versus closed innovation?

This questionnaire ends here. We once again thank you for your generous and helpful support for this study, and we wish you a pleasant working day!